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**3rd National Conference on
Challenges and Opportunities in Management Science**

DEPARTMENT OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

2nd March 2018

St. Ignatius Loyola

LOYOLA COLLEGE

**Vettavalam – 606 754
Tiruvannamalai District, Tamil Nadu, India**

ABOUT THE COLLEGE

LOYOLA COLLEGE was established in the year 2009 with 6 UG courses and 2 PG courses (M.A., English and M.Sc. Mathematics) at Vettavalam, Thiruvannamalai District. It is a venture of the Chennai Mission of the Jesuit Madurai Province. It is run and administrated by the Society of Jesus (SJ), who are known as Jesuits. The Jesuits involve themselves in empowering the rural youth from the marginalized communities by providing quality education.

ABOUT THE DEPARTMENT

The Department of Business Administration was established in the year 2009. The department with its Motto "We build Versatiles", aims to impart the students, the essential knowledge of the corporate world along with the fundamentals of administration. The Department has been successfully running the department association that provides opportunities in skill development activities for students and also creates placement facility. The department has successfully organized one international conference (2016), a National Conference (2017) and now the third National Conference (2018).

MESSAGE

Dear Friends,

I am very glad to know that the Department of Business Administration is planning to host a Conference with the theme, “**Challenges & Opportunities in Management Science**”. The department has chosen a very apt theme to reflect about the current developments and needs in the field of Management Science.

Managing our life – personal and social, resources, relationships, business activities and our jobs - is increasingly full of challenges and issues. Success depends very much on proper and effective management in these areas of our life. When we fail to manage, stress and other problems begin to affect and haunt us as shadows in our daily life.

Life in the modern society is no longer simple. The complex reality beckons us to evolve effective ways and good practices to cope with the demands and challenges of present society. All the business concerns and entrepreneurship efforts face challenges due to speedy technological changes at the global level. The larger business concerns and companies are in an advantageous position to face the challenges with the help of experts who have specialized in management science. Such an advantage is not there for smaller and rural enterprises. The conference has to reflect and come out with solutions and effective practices for such enterprises. As of now, Management Science seems to be more urban oriented. It is our duty to make it more rural oriented so as to empower the rural business initiatives and rural development efforts.

I wish you all success with good participation and a successful outcome.

Rev.Fr. Maria Joseph, S.J.

*Superior
Loyola College*

MESSAGE

I am delighted to know that the Department of Business Administration is organizing A National Seminar on 'Challenges and Opportunities In Management Science' on March 2, 2018 which is of national importance in today's international context. I am also happy to note that the Department is bringing a Journal which contains of scholarly articles written by Scholars. This kind of publication will surely boost students to read, think, write and enrich their knowledge in Management Science. The topic is very pragmatic one in the line of long-range planning by focusing why it is needed; and what is needed to do in future which could be considered a major opportunity for, and challenge to, Management Science. I am sure, the National Seminar on "Challenges and Opportunities In Management Science" will be addressing the key issues and giving a futuristic solutions.

The department of Business Administration, though Under Graduate, has brought a lot of laurels to Loyola College not only in academic excellence but also in forming students men and women for others. I am proud to acknowledge that the students of BBA are well placed in reputed companies due to the constant motivations and conducting meaning State and National conferences by the Staff. Their efforts are always appreciated by the Jesuit Management.

I do appreciate and congratulate the Staff and Students of The Department of Business Administration of our college for having taken efforts in conducting this National Conference and bringing about a Journal in the subject of Management Science. My greetings and best wishes for all participants of the Conference and success in their learning processes of becoming best Managers in future.

Thank you and God bless our staff and students.

Rev. Dr. Fr. Rajrathinam, SJ, MA, Phil, Ph.D
Secretary
Loyola College

MESSAGE

My hearty congratulation to the members of the department of BBA and the students for having organized the National Conference on “Challenges and Opportunities in Management Science”.

Forming oneself is very important to succeed in the field of administration. As a student of BBA, it is better to create an order or discipline within one self which will enhance you to face life. Once you complete the degree, you will be facing the real world with challenges and difficulties. To face the reality in administration in your future endeavor, seminars like this will equip you with knowledge about managerial skills.

As the student of Business Administration, you should learn to stand on your own legs. Do not imitate others. Develop the skill to organize and delegate responsibilities to others. Create team spirit which will promote success to your organization.

I hope that this conference will bring out new ideas to enable the participants by acquiring new skills in their business administration.

Best Wishes,

Rev. Dr. V. Gilbert Camillus, S.J.
Principal
Loyola College

MESSAGE

The Department of Business Administration is really happy to organize The National conference on “CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITES IN MANAGEMENT SCIENCE”.

There have been great improvements in the fields of Management and Administration. Today's busy world is vastly driven by principles of globalization that offers an intensified and easier transfer of goods for people across the borders, thus creating more opportunities for the business people to move and interact.

I strongly believe that this conference will surely help a lot to create a forum for the researchers, Entrepreneurs, Industrialists and students to share their ideas among themselves.

I wish to thank the Management, Staff, Editorial board, Advisory Committee, Students, Well-wishers, Publisher and each and every individual involved in this process of hosting the 3rd National Conference.

My special thanks to all the sponsors who helped the department of Business Administration in hosting the conference and partaking in our mission of building Versatiles for the business Future.

Prof. Stanley Vincent
Head of the Department
Department of Business Administration
Loyola College, Vettavalam
01-02-2018

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A STUDY ON STRESS MANAGEMENT IN ORGANISATION

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Abstract

Stress is a reality of regular daily existence, we've all felt it. Now and then it goes about as a positive power and in some cases as a negative power. On the off chance that you encounter worry over a delayed timeframe, it could wind up plainly ceaseless, till you make some move. Around 500 million individuals worldwide are accepted to be experiencing masochist, stretch related and mental problems. The test can, be that as it may, be handled by joint activity between life sciences, sociologies, urban arranging, design and governmental issues. This article features the causes, impacts and administration of stress also, in this way could be useful for individuals who need to figure out how to respond to worry in a more helpful, proactive way.

Introduction

Long working hours, night shifts and a sedentary lifestyle make people employed at information technology companies prone to heart disease and diabetes, the report said. There have also been growing reports of mental depression and family discord in the industry. Infosys Technologies Ltd., India's second-largest software exporter, has a 24-hour hot line for employees suffering from depression to access psychiatrists. Infosys introduced a work-life balance plan after a 24-year-old employee suffered a heart attack several years ago. India's per capita health spending of \$7 is one of the lowest in the world and is a fraction of what the United States spends -- \$2,548, according to a 2006 WHO report.

Several recent studies have highlighted the links between work-related stress, violence at work, the abuse of drugs and alcohol and tobacco consumption. These studies tend to suggest that stress at work plays an important role in the development of negative individual and organizational factors and forms a common element linking working conditions, substance abuse and violent acts. Stressful work may contribute to the development of a desire among workers to reduce tension by drinking, using drugs and other harmful substances. Thus in my project work done at HCCBPL is focusing on the topic Stress management in HCCBPL, how does stress affect employees of HCCBPL and how do they cope up with stressful conditions.

Definitions

“Job stress can be defined as the harmful physical and emotional responses that occur when the requirements of the job do not match the capabilities, resources, or needs of the worker. Job stress can lead to poor health and even injury.” (United States National Institute of Occupational Safety and Health, Cincinnati, 1999) “Stress is the reaction people have to excessive pressures or other types of demand placed on them.” (United Kingdom Health and Safety Commission, London, 1999).

Types of Stress

There are three types of stress. They are:

- **Eu-Stress**-Stress caused due to sudden good news or positive aspects

- **Distress**-Stress caused due to negative aspects.
- **Mild Stress**- A minimum and desirable level of stress.

Causes of Stress

Causes of Stress: Causes can be broadly divide in to three,

Organizational Factors	Personality Factors	Work family interaction Factors
Job it shelf	Age	Work demands
Poor physical working conditions	Sex	Family demands
Work overload	Headache	Work flexibility
Time pressures	Personality	Pressures at work
Long working hours	Control & decision making capacity	Support at work

Symptoms of Stress

- Speech problems
- Impulsive behavior
- Crying for no apparent reason
- Laughing in a high pitch and nervous tone of voice
- Increasing smoking and use of drugs and alcohol
- Being accident prone
- Perspiration/Sweaty hands
- Increased heart beat
- Nervous
- Irritating and moody
- Diarrhea
- Indigestion
- Vomiting
- Butterflies in stomach
- Head aches
- Psychological and Behavioral changes

Sources of Stress in HCCBPL

- Night Shifts
- Long Working Hours
- Heat
- Lack of management support
- Work load

Statement of the Problem

In this generation in every one’s life face challenges to complete their tasks and work they need to be very competitive so by doing more and getting tension like work burden, workload, changes in the technology and lack of training they are facing stress. They were not able to

produce optimum results. So it is problems to the company and their career. This organization by recognizing the problems, they were giving and providing good facilities and giving analysis to the employees. So lots of employees are satisfied with these and they are coming out from the stress.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand the stress management practices in Hindustan Coca-Cola Beverages Pvt.Ltd.
- To identify the potential causes of stress in Hindustan Coca-Cola Beverages Pvt.Ltd.
- To analyze the impact of stress on the performance of employees.
- To evaluate the effectiveness existing stress management practices.
- To make suitable suggestions in managing the stress.

Need for the Study

The study is to know the stress levels faced by the employees in the organization. The stress levels of the employees increases due to the changes in the technology, work overload and lack of training to the employee's. When the stress levels of the employees increased that may affect the job performance of the employees, by this study the counseling is given to increase the levels of job performance. To know the behavior of the employees in the organization. It is very important for very organization to know about the stress management and counseling program conditions and its impact on the performance

Scope of the Study

Stress will badly affects the employees both at work and in personal life. If stress is managed properly it will be beneficial to employee as well as the organization in terms of production, employee satisfaction , increased productivity , improved relationships both on and off the job, better teamwork and communication, improved morale, retention of valued employees but if it's not managed properly it will create bad impact on employee's health, behavior, and psychologically. Bad on an employee means bad on organization too. Stress can be a reason for employee turnover, absenteeism, and low productivity. Thus stress affecting working of the entire organization.

Industry Profile

Introduction

Employees attitudes are important to human resource management, because the effect organizational behavior. In particular attitudes relating to job satisfaction and organizational commitment are of major interest to the field of human resource management. Now this study reveals job satisfaction level of employee in a Hindustan COCA-COLA Beverages Pvt. Ltd. which is a located in Chittoor District. Hindustan Coca-Cola Beverages Pvt. Ltd is one of as there are different wings in this Organization it becomes difficult to update the information regarding job satisfaction or any matters.

The study is bounded up to the job satisfaction only and to focus the effectively, best source and satisfactory rate a study was conducted with a well-structured questionnaire and consult with employees in Coca-Cola. After that a final analysis was conducted to elaborate the statement of the problem and to give the conclusion about the study.

NARTD Non - Alcoholic ready to drink market can be divided into fruit drink & soft drink can be further divided into carbonated and non-carbonated drinks. Mango drinks come under

noncarbonated category and carbonated drinks comprises of different coal, lemon and orange flavor drinks.

Major Player in Soft Drink Industry

Coca Cola Pvt. Ltd.

It entered into Indian market by signing an agreement with Parle exports limited. Its brands are Coca-Cola, Fanta, and Sprite etc. On September 25th the chairman brother signed an agreement with Coke selling their best brands like Thumps-Up, Limca, Maaza and Gold Spot.

Pepsi foods Private Limited.

It came into Indian in 1956 and left country in 1961 due to unsuccessful operations, in the year 1990 if re-entered into Indian market in collaboration with Punjab Agro Industry Corporation.

Other Players

Besides these established manufacturers there are more than 200 units of independent manufactures of soft drink industry. They constitute very small market share around 4% of the entire soft drink industry.

Company Profile

The Coca-Cola Company

Coca-Cola the Coca - Cola Company traces its beginning to 1886, when an Atlanta Georgia Pharmacist, Dr. John Pemberton, began to produce Coca-Cola syrup for sale in the fountain drink. However with the exemption of an independent bottling operation established in 1894 in Viking, Mississippi, the history of large scale bottling did not begin until 1899 when two Chattanooga business men, Joseph. B. whitehead and Benjamin.F.Thomas, secured the exclusive rights to bottle and sell Coca-Cola for most of the United States from the Coca-Cola Company.

Management Philosophy

Corporate Area

The major concept of the management Philosophy is to remain in the beverages industry and not diversify into other areas. The management believes in investing in non Capital - intensive areas. In fact, the beverage industry requires little capital, and produces maximum returns. The returns from the foreign markets are tapped to the most.

Financial Area

The corporate objectives are to increase the share owner's value. The management believes that in increasing the shareholders value, it requires consistent growth in financial results complemented by effective use of the cast flow.

Marketing Area

Here the management is committed to superior market place execution. This is achieved by decentralized operating structure that places the responsibilities, authority and the accountability as close to the customer and consumer as possible.

Company's Mission

Coca-Cola exists to create value for their share owners on a long -term basis by building a business that enhances the Coca-Cola Company's trademarks. This also is the ultimate commitment. As the world's largest beverage company Coca-Cola refreshes that world Coca-Cola do this by developing superior soft drinks, both carbonated and non-carbonated, and profitable non alcoholic beverage systems that create value for the company, the bottling partners and to

the customers. In creating value, Coca-Cola succeeds or fail based on the company's ability to perform as worthy stewards of several key assets.

1. Coca-Cola the world's most powerful trade mark and other highly valuable "TRADEMARKS".
2. The World's most effective and pervasive DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM.
3. Satisfied CUSTOMERS, who make a good profit selling Coca-Cola Products.
4. The people who are working are ultimately responsible for building this enterprise.
5. The abundant RESOURCES, which must be intelligently allocated.
6. The strong global LEADERSHIP in the beverage industry in particular and in the business world in general.

Review of Literature

(1) Anitha.A.et.al (2013) has conducted a research on faculty's perception of stress and coping strategies. This study has investigated stress and coping strategies adopted by faculties in some selected colleges in five states. The result of a chi-square analysis revealed that male and female colleges were significantly different in stress experience. And the study also found that male and female and married and single respondents were significantly different in their coping strategies.

(2) Jins Joy. Pet.al (2013) study objective is to know occupational stress experienced by Tile industry employees in Kannur and Calicut District of Kerala State. Actually in this research paper it was checked that what upon employees. And the results says that occupational stress is found higher among Kannur district Tile industry employees compared to Calicut district employees. Employees cannot afford the time to relax and "wind down" when they are faced with work variety, discrimination, favoritism,delegation and conflicting tasks.

(3) SoumyaSankaret. al (August, 2013) have conducted a study on 200 Veterinarians in Animal Husbandry Department of Kerala. Some elements like job satisfaction, teamwork, security etc.....were selected as stressors for the study. The result of the study revealed that majority of the respondents had medium level of stress due to various stressors on the work place. It also shows that job satisfaction was perceived as the most important cause of stress on the work place.

(4) M.Kaveriet. al (June,2013) have conducted the study for the purpose to identify the impact of work stress factors faced in the organization on employee's job performance in leather goods manufacturing companies at Vellore District .The results shows that increased workload and improper work schedule and lack of supervisory support are having a positive and significant relationship with employees job performance.

(5) RuchiSinha (2012) has conducted a study on comparative study of selected public and private sector. Occupational stress has been recognized as a major health issue for modern work organization. It has become predominant and people have come up with balanced monitored concepts to minimize stress. This paper proceeds to explain stress the causes and the ways to minimize stress.

Research Methodology

Primary Data

Primary data is one, which is collected by the investigator himself for the purpose of a specific inquiry or study. Such data is original in character and is generated by survey conducted by individuals or research institution or an organization.

Secondary Data

Secondary data are those data which have been already collected and analyzed by some earlier agency for its own use; and later the same data are used by a different agency.

Data Collection Methods

Primary Data

- Well-Structured Questionnaire
- Interview Method

Secondary Data

- Journals
- Manuals of HCCBPL
- Newspapers
- Textbooks
- Websites
- Previous records of HCCBPL

Period of the Study: The study was conducted over a period of 2 months i.e., from February to April.

Population Size: The workers and employees together in HCCBPL, srikalahasti are 349.

Sample Size

Sample size means the number of sample units selected from the total population for collecting primary data. I have selected 100 samples from total population by using Random Sampling Method.

Random Sampling

A method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller groups known as strata. In random sampling, the strata are formed based on members shared attributes or characteristics. Random sample from each stratum is taken in a number proportional to the stratum's size when compared to the population. These subsets of the strata are then pooled to form a random sample.

Type of Question

- Close ended questions

Type of Study

Descriptive Research Study

Descriptive research studies are those studies which are concerned with describing the characteristics of particular individuals or a group of studies concerned with specific predictions, with narration of facts and characteristics concerning individual, group or situation are examples of descriptive research studies. Most of the social research comes under this category For this study I used Descriptive Research Method.

Tools for Analysis

- Simple Percentage Method
- Weighted Average Method

Simple Percentage Method

Percentage refers to a special kind of ratio percentage issued in making comparisons between two or more series of data; percentage method is used to describe the relationship.

$$\% \text{ of Respondents} = \text{No. of Respondents} / \text{Total no. of Respondents} \times 100$$

Weighted Average Method

The weights are assigned to each response of every table the weights were multiplied with the corresponding respondents and this was divided by total number of respondents.

$$\text{Weighted Average} = \Sigma (\text{Weights} * \text{No. of respondents}) / \text{Total no. of respondents}$$

Limitations

The study suffered from the following limitations:

1. This study is limited to HCCBPL.
2. Some of the employees were not cooperative in giving necessary information due to their busy schedule.
3. Employees took many days to give back their filled up questionnaires due to tight work schedule.
4. Due to time constraint the researcher failed to do an in depth study.
5. The data collected not exact. Because the respondents might gave answers based on their mood and situation.
6. The findings of the study are not universally applicable.

Findings

1. Some of the respondents viewed every time there is stress with work, few of the respondents are to some extent feeling stress at work, some of the respondents are to great extent feeling stress at work and rest of them viewed never.
2. Few of the respondents strongly agree that stress affects their performance, some of the respondents agree that stress affects their performance, most of the respondents are neutral, some of the respondents disagree that stress affects their performance, veryfew of the respondents strongly disagree that stress affects their performance.
3. Most of the respondents are negatively affected by stress, few of the respondents are to great extent negatively affected by stress, some of the respondents are to some extent negatively affected by stress, and few of the respondents are never negatively affected by the stress.
4. Very of the respondents are highly satisfied with the working condition provided by the organization, some of the respondents are satisfied with the working condition provided by the organization, rest of the respondents are partially satisfied with the working condition provided by the organization, few of the respondents are dissatisfied, and rest of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the working condition provided by the organization.
5. Some of the respondents viewed that stress helps in boosting their performance, most of the respondents viewed that almost, few of the respondents viewed sometimes and few of the respondents viewed always stress helps in boosting their performance.
6. Majority of the respondents viewed that rarely stress has become a reason for absent with the mean of 3.

7. Most of the respondents viewed that output is affected by stress, few of the respondents viewed to an extent, some of the respondents viewed too much and very few of the respondents viewed never output is affected by stress
8. Some of the respondents feel tensed when deadlines are given, few of the respondents viewed sometimes, most of the respondents viewed not much and very few of the respondents viewed never feel tensed when deadlines are given.

Suggestions

1. More stress management programs should design and implemented in the organization.
2. Physical environment stress in HCCBPL should be minimized.
3. Employer should take care of the employees problems also.
4. Yoga and stress control programs must be conducted, in the organization then the employees can handle the stress situation.
5. Work distribution should be done by basing on the interest of the employees.
6. Management response should be much better in HCCBPL.
7. The workers may feel work burden until the new machinery and technology completely brought in to HCCBPL.

Conclusion

Hence I conclude that stress is so wide spread high cost for individual, organization, families and for society also. It creates greater strain even in family relationship. Hence it may results in depression, suicide etc.... For the organization, the cost of stress may take many parameters like frustration and less success in achieving individual goals. Thus a study on stress will be useful to organization and community at large.

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Understanding the Importance of Stress Management

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6. QUESTIONNAIRE

Stress Management

Employee Name: Designation:

Experience: Age:

1. Do you feel stress at work?
 - i) Always iii) To great extent
 - ii) To some extent iv) Never
2. Whether stress affects your performance?
 - i) Strongly agree iii) Neutral
 - ii) Agree iv) Disagree v) Strongly Disagree
3. Does stress affect negatively at work?
 - i) Always iii) To some extent
 - ii) To great extent iv) Never
4. Opinion about working condition provided by organization?
 - i) Highly satisfied iii) Partially satisfied
 - ii) Satisfied iv) Dissatisfied v) Highly Dissatisfied
5. Do you think stress helps in boosting your performance?
 - i) Never iii) Sometimes
 - ii) Almost iv) Always
6. Does ever stress become a reason for absent?
 - i) Very often iii) Rarely
 - ii) Occasionally iv) Never
7. Do you think the output is affected by stress?
 - i) Very much iii) Too much
 - ii) To an extent iv) Never
8. Do feel tensed when deadlines are given?
 - i) Very much iii) Not much
 - ii) Sometimes iv) Never
9. Does stress causes any psychological impact on you?
 - i) Very much iii) Not much
 - ii) To an extent iv) Never
10. "Stress creates health problems" -what is your opinion ?
 - i) Strongly agree ii) Neutral iii) Agree iv) Disagree v) Strongly Disagree

INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS: AN ANALYSIS OF ACADEMICIANS' PERCEPTION

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Abstract

Globalization has laid down a way for all the countries to implement a single set of accounting standards for bringing equality in the financial statements and financial reporting system. The International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) represents a radical change in accounting for transactions and reporting of financial statements and it is one of the recent developments in the field of accounting, with the aim of making accounts more consistent, comparable and bringing harmonization in the accounting policies and principles. Many developed and upcoming economies on the world economic map including India have their own set of national accounting standards which are different on many counts especially on the legal, socio-economic, and cultural norms and now they decided to converge to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). The understanding and implementation of IFRS is not easy, the transition will be a tough challenge for the country as it requires a shift in the academic approach, along with regulatory challenges. As the major problem to cope up with convergence is the lack of timely and whole hearted acknowledgement to the need and importance of convergence by the academician and regulation authorities. As to cope up with this pressure of convergence, the only solution is to train the trainers and most importantly the academicians. That is why, this paper attempts to study the need and importance of convergence from the eyes of academicians involved in teaching finance and accounting.

Key Words: Accounting Standards, GAAP, IFRS, IASB.

Introduction: Indian Accounting Standards, IAS and IFRS

In India, the Central Government prescribes accounting standards in consultation with the National Advisory Committee on Accounting Standards (NACAS) established under the Companies Act, 1956. NACAS has been engaged in the exercise of examining Accounting Standards prepared by ICAI. It has adapted the international norms established by the International Financial Reporting Standards issued by the International Accounting Standards Board. The Central Government notified 28 Accounting Standards (AS 1 to 7 and AS 9 to 29) in December 2006 in the form of Companies (Accounting Standard) Rules, 2006, after receiving recommendations of NACAS. The Government has adopted a policy of enabling disclosure of company accounts in a transparent manner at par with widely accepted international practices, through a process of convergence with the International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). The initiative for harmonization of the Indian accounting standards with IFRS, taken up by NACAS in 2001 and implemented through notification of accounting standards by the Central Government in 2006.

The Indian corporate accountant today, while presenting financial statements, prepares them as per AS (Indian Accounting Standards), US GAAP if the stocks are listed in USA, or other standards depending on where the stocks are listed. This is also true of MNCs who establish their shop in India, which is one of the most sought after destinations for setting up their business operations. Further, different reporting frameworks in various countries lead to inconsistent treatment and presentation of economic transactions by entities. This can cloud the outlook and perspective of investor's vis-à-vis the entities, which, in turn, results in capital market inefficiencies across the world.

Such increasing complexity of business operations and globalization of capital markets makes mandatory a single set of high quality reporting standards. This space can aptly be filled in with the emergence of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), as formulated by the International Accounting Standards Board. IFRS has emerged as a new force in aligning the global firms on a single line.

International Financial Reporting Standards are set by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB). The mission of IASB is to develop, in the public interest, a single set of high quality, understandable and International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) for general purpose financial statements. IASB is an independent standard-setting board, appointed and overseen by a geographically and professionally diverse group of Trustees of the IASC Foundation who are accountable to the public interest. It is supported by an external advisory council (SAC) and an interpretations committee (IFRIC) to offer guidance wherever divergence in practice occurs. The IASB cooperates with national accounting standard setters to achieve convergence in accounting standards around the world.

Review of Literature

Muniraju and Ganesh (2015) describes that the companies will find comfort in using accounting standards converged with IFRS if their accountants, auditors, shareholders and other stake holders along with the rating agencies and investment analysts are conversant with such new standards. It is true that during the transition period some problems may have to be faced by any of the aforesaid persons due to lack of adequate knowledge and experience. But such problems can be mitigated if the professional institutes and industry groups take initiative for imparting intensive training to the accounting and auditing professionals on the practical implications and applications.

Reena Rani and Manisha Gupta (2014) recognized that the measures taken by ICAI and the other regulatory bodies to facilitate the smooth convergence to IFRS are commendable and give the positive idea that the country is ready for convergence. IFRS training and education should be given to the professionals and its implementation should start soon as many countries are adopting this and completed the Phase I of its adoption. Since the cost of compliance with IFRS would be very high for medium size industry. There are some challenges in implementing IFRS like non-compatible legal and regulatory environment, concern over SMEs, economic environment, level of preparedness, alternative treatments, education needs of auditors, frequent change to the IFRS and translation issues.

Partap Singh and ShifaliGarg (2013) tested that Convergence of Indian Accounting standards with IFRS comes as a relief for many Indian firms that could have been forced to re-audit their financial statements as per IFRS or halt operations.

Chinwuba Okafor and Killian Osikhena Ogedu (2011) the study found that International Financial Reporting Standards have the potential for yielding greater benefits than current GAAP, improve business performance management and impact on other business functions apart from financial reporting.

Amarjeet Kaur Malhotra (2011) argued that the understanding and implementation of IFRS is not easy, the transition will be a tough challenge for the country as it requires a shift in the academic approach, along with regulatory challenges. The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India would need to impart special training to its students and members alike as the academicians

involved in imparting education on financial reporting standards strongly support the need of introducing the IFRS.

ZabihollahRezaee et al (2010) concluded that effective convergence to a set of globally accepted accounting standards would be beneficial to preparers, users, auditors, analysts, and standard setters. Convergence in accounting standards can require extensive and possibly costly changes to the standard setting infrastructure and enforcement process in the US and other countries, and will also require proper training for management, auditors, and investors. Convergence to IFRS is expected to improve the comparability of financial reports and thus benefit global investors.

Joshi et al (2008) pointed that there will be a growing demand for detailed application guidance for IFRS and also, it appears that nationalism may well continue to be a major impediment to global adoption of IFRS. The major advantages of global adoption of IFRS higher than locals, and the means for challenges and disadvantages were higher for locals. National accounting bodies were viewed as having an important role in global adoption and implementation of IFRS.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the level of awareness among academicians about convergence of Indian Accounting Standards to IFRS
- To study the need and benefits of convergence of Indian Accounting Standards to IFRS from academicians perspective.

Research Methodology of the Study

The present study is based on the both primary and secondary data, an exploratory in nature, was conducted in Visakhapatnam city. Ninety eight respondents were selected who teach accounting and finance and taxation papers. Purposive sampling technique was used. Teachers sample represent 13 junior Lecturers, 20 Senior Lecturers, 18 Associate professors, 21 Assistant professors, and 26 Professor thus, bringing total respondents number to 98. A structured questionnaire containing different questions relating to various aspects of awareness of convergence of Indian Accounting Standards to IFRS has been used. The SPSS 16.0 version was used to interpret and analyze the data. The techniques of frequencies, percentage and ANOVAs applied to derive the results.

Analysis and Interpretations

Table.1: Age Group-wise Distribution of Respondents

Age in years	Frequency	Percent
Below - 30	9	9.2
31-40	23	23.5
41-50	41	41.8
50 and Above	25	25.5
Total	98	100.0

Table.1 presents age wise distribution of the respondents. Out of the total respondents 41.8% are in the age group of 41-50 years, 25.5% are in the age group of 50 and above years. Further, 23.5 per cent are in the age group of 31-40 years and 9.2 per cent are aged below 30 years.

Table.2: Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	66	67.3
Female	32	32.7
Total	98	100.0

Table.2: depicts gender-wise distribution of respondents. It can be observed from the sample that majority of the respondents i.e., 66 out of 98 total respondents representing 67.3 per cent belongs to male category whereas the remaining 32 respondents representing 32.7 per cent belongs to female category.

Table.3: Academic Qualifications of the Respondents

Academic Qualifications	Frequency	Percent
Ph.D.	53	54.1
M.Phil.	15	15.3
Master	30	30.6
Total	98	100.0

Academic Qualifications of the sample respondents is presented in table: 3. Out of the total sample 53 respondents representing 54.1 per cent possess Ph.D. as their academic qualification, followed by 30 respondents representing 30.6 per cent are having Master's

Degree as their academic qualification and 15 respondent's representing 15.3 per cent possess M.Phil. Degree as their academic qualification.

Table.4: Professional Qualifications of the Respondents

Professional Qualifications	Frequency	Percent
Commerce	91	92.9
Management	7	7.1
Total	98	100.0

Table.4: depicts the Professional Qualifications of the Respondents. It can be observed from the sample that majority of the respondents i.e., 91 out of 98 total respondents representing 92.9 per cent

possess Commerce as their Professional Qualifications whereas the remaining 7 respondents representing 7.1 per cent possess Commerce as their Professional Qualifications.

Table.5: Designation of the Respondents

Designation	Frequency	Percent
Junior Lecturer	13	13.3
Degree Lecturer	20	20.4
Assistant Professor	18	18.4
Associate Professor	21	21.4
Professor	26	26.5
Total	98	100.0

Table.5: shows the Designation of the respondents. Out of the total sample 26 respondents representing 26.5 per cent their designation is Professor, followed by 21 respondents representing 21.4 per cent their designation is Associate Professor, whereas 20 respondents representing 20.4 per cent their designation is Degree Lecturer, 18 respondents representing 18.4 per cent their

designation is Assistant Professor and the remaining 13 respondents representing 13.3 per cent their designation is Junior Lecturer.

Table.6: Work Experience of the respondents

Work Experience	Frequency	Percent
Below 5 years	11	11.2
6-10 years	32	32.7
11-15 years	23	23.5
16-20 years	10	10.2
21 years and above	22	22.4
Total	98	100.0

Table.6: presents the Work Experience of the respondents. Out of the total sample 32 respondents 32.7 per cent representing their work experience is 6-10 years followed by sample 23 respondents 23.5 per cent representing their work experience is 11-15 years, whereas 22 respondents 22.4 per cent

representing and 11 respondents 11.2 per cent representing their work experience is 21 years and above and below 5 years and 10 respondents 10.2 per cent representing their work experience is 16-20 years.

Hypothesis: there is no significant difference in opinions for different category of academicians regarding advantages of introduce IFRS in India.

Table.7: ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
There is a possibility of international capital flow in India	Between Groups	4.139	4	1.035	.686	.604@
	Within groups	140.361	93	1.509		
	Total	144.500	97			
Foreign investors are to invest in firms whose accounting is similar to their country	Between Groups	.962	4	.241	.536	.710@
	Within groups	41.742	93	.449		
	Total	42.704	97			
Increase the professional opportunities for Indian accountant	Between Groups	5.350	4	1.412	.2.929	0.025**
	Within groups	44.850	93	.482		
	Total	50.500	97			
The IFRS will increase the growth of the multinational companies	Between Groups	1.292	4	.323	.436	.782@
	Within groups	98.882	93	.741		
	Total	70.173	97			
Provide better information for Governments for economic planning	Between Groups	3.326	4	.831	2.384	.057@
	Within groups	32.439	93	.349		
	Total	35.765	97			
Facilitate the growth of direct foreign investments in India.	Between Groups	3.463	4	.866	1.074	.374@
	Within groups	74.996	93	.806		
	Total	78.459	97			
Greater understanding of operation of multinational companies	Between Groups	5.165	4	1.291	2.047	0.094@
	Within groups	58.672	93	.631		
	Total	63.837	97			

Elimination of multiple reporting costs.	Between Groups	.024	4	.006	.010	1.000@
	Within groups	55.323	93	.595		
	Total	55.347	97			
IFRS provide quality reporting audit report.	Between Groups	1.258	4	.315	.717	.582@
	Within groups	40.793	93	.439		
	Total	42.051	97			
For investing easier to diversity portfolios	Between Groups	7.429	4	1.857	4.608	.002*
	Within groups	37.479	93	.403		
	Total	44.908	97			
Tax authorities will find it easy to assess tax payers for payment and collection	Between Groups	2.679	4	.670	1.751	.145@
	Within groups	35.566	93	.382		
	Total	38.245	97			
There is a possibility of Job Creation and Poverty Alleviation	Between Groups	9.413	4	2.353	2.799	.031**
	Within groups	78.475	93	.844		
	Total	87.888	97			
Costs savings for education and training with a single accounting regime	Between Groups	2.059	4	.515	.884	.477@
	Within groups	54.145	93	.582		
	Total	56.204	97			

** - Significant at 5% level, * - Significant at 1% level, @ -Not Significant.

It can be noted that the obtained significance value for Increase the professional opportunities for Indian accountants (0.025), there is a possibility of Job Creation and Poverty Alleviation (0.031) are significant at 5% level. Hence it can be concluded that there is significant difference of opinions on Increase the professional opportunities for Indian accountants, Greater understanding of operation of multinational companies, there is a possibility of Job Creation and Poverty Alleviation based on the different category of academicians.

It can be observed that the obtained significance value for investing easier to diversity portfolios (.002) is significant at 1% level. Hence it can be concluded that there is a significant difference of opinions on for investing easier to diversity portfolios based on their different designations.

It can be noted that the obtained significance value for there is a possibility of international capital flow in India (.604), Foreign investors are to invest in firms whose accounting is similar to their country (.710), The IFRS will increase the growth of the multinational companies(0.782),

Provide better information for Governments for economic planning(0.057), Facilitate the growth of direct foreign investments in India (0.374), Greater understanding of operation of multinational companies (0.094), Elimination of multiple reporting costs (1.000), IFRS provide quality reporting audit report (.582), Tax authorities will find it easy to assess tax payers for payment and collection (.145), Costs savings for education and training with a single accounting regime(.477) is not significant. Hence it can be concluded that there is no significant difference of opinions on there is a possibility of international capital flow in India , Foreign investors are to invest in firms whose accounting is similar to their country, The IFRS will increase the growth of the multinational companies, Provide better information for Governments for economic planning, Facilitate the growth of direct foreign investments in India, Elimination of multiple reporting costs, IFRS provide quality reporting audit report, Tax authorities will find it easy to assess tax payers for payment and collection, Costs savings for education and training with a single accounting regime based on the different category of academicians.

Suggestions and Recommendations

- For initiating conversion of AS to IFRS will require formulation of human Capital strategies. The company will have to assess the level of in-house experience /expertise and the types of training that will be need.
- There is great need of organizing training sessions for academicians.
- Academicians should use of journals, e-journals or books as much as possible so that they cope up with the challenges of convergence.
- It should be overcome the problem of slow pace of conversion in India. Indifference attitude of ASB, Lack of openness, reference for status quo, Government inclusion in Financial Reporting Area, Lack of Accounting Research are critical issues.
- Adopting the IFRS will need careful study of the changes and its impacts.
- The company willing to adopt conversion will require thoughtful communication plan for the board of directors, shareholders and other key stakeholders.
- Indian Companies are lacking in providing some important information like material event, estimated changes, effect of changes etc. By giving such information, Indian companies can improve their standard of disclosing practices.
- The process of conversion will demand well designed and efficient change management initiated and championed by a company`s leadership.

Conclusion

The Study reveals that there is a clear difference in awareness level for different category of academicians. A very small percentage of academicians make efforts to contribute in research in IFRS area. There is a need of to be changed in academic curriculum in accounting principles. There is slow pace of conversion in India due to Indifference attitude of ASB, Lack of openness, reference for status quo, Government inclusion in Financial Reporting Area, Lack of Accounting Research. The convergence with IFRS may bring significant variations in the value of total non-current assets, total current assets, total assets, equity, total liabilities, revenue, operating profit/Loss and profit/loss after Tax. Besides, we would need IFRS-trained professionals in India for which the Institute of Chartered Accountants of India would need to impart special training to its students and members alike as the academicians involved in imparting education on financial reporting standards strongly support the need of introducing the IFRS . Though, respondents were aware that

the there is some kind of difference between Indian GAPP and IFRS but no one could answer precisely, leading to conclusion that there is urge for training of academicians for successful convergence of Indian GAAP to IFRS. There was a strong consensus among academicians involved in accounting and finance that the convergence to IFRS will lead to increased trust of foreign investors in the Indian companies and also the reports generated with the help of IFRS will be globally comparable.

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NATIONAL SERVICE SCHEME AND STUDENT YOUTH DEVELOPMENT IN THE JURISDICTION OF ASSAM UNIVERSITY

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Abstract

The study is conducted among the NSS volunteers of Assam University and its affiliated Colleges to study and examine the motivational factors that lead students of Assam University and the students of its affiliated Colleges. It studied the views and opinions of the NSS volunteers about NSS as a programme and their level of awareness about this scheme on why it is important for a student to be part of National Service Scheme. The study revealed the wide range of NSS activities and programmes carried by the NSS units of Assam University and its affiliate colleges. An attempt has also been made to understand the substantial contribution of each of these programmes and activities on the NSS volunteers' development. The present study was also carried out to identify the various problems and challenges encounter by the NSS volunteers while implementing the scheme at the University and the college level and tried to understand the various strategies adopted by them to overcome these challenges. An attempt has been made to understand the major contribution of NSS on the college level by interviewing the College principals and the other stake holders. Most importantly the present study focused more on identifying positive development of NSS volunteers that they have gained after joining NSS. The research is the outcome a minor project sponsored by Rajiv Gandhi National Institute of Youth Development.

Keywords: *NSS, Youth, Positive development*

Introduction

National Service Scheme (NSS) is one of the youth schemes introduced by the Central Government with the help of the various State Governments for the development of youth. It is now an accepted fact all over the world that the development of any country depends upon the youth of the country. The NSS is the scheme where, youth power is used for solving the social problems like environment, water conservation, AIDS and basically for engaging in the different service activities of the rural development. The implementation of the scheme is being operated at present at the plus two level schools known as junior colleges and the degree-level colleges.

National Service Scheme is a voluntary organisation of young people in colleges Universities and at +2 levels working for a campus-community linkage. The cardinal principle of NSS programme is that it is organised by the student themselves and that has allow them to participate actively in the community and through their active participation in the community services, get sense of involvement in the tasks of nation building.

NSS aimed at developing student's personality through community services. Over the years, NSS has been able to tap the youth energy at their formative years of college and higher education and helped in igniting the young mind towards selfless service to the society and shaping their individualism.

Therefore it is utmost important to understand how much student are benefiting from being the NSS volunteer. Apart from personality development what other positive development student have gained from NSS. It is also important to understand from Volunteers perception point of regarding the implementation of the scheme at the college or university level and the initiative

taken by the college and University to implement the scheme in such a way that it impacts the student personality.

The quest of this research is what positive development has impacted on the NSS volunteers as well as at community level through NSS programmes in the educational jurisdiction of the Assam University. It is claimed that the North Eastern States of India has been ignored in many development aspects and often the common people of these states are isolated from other parts of the country. Assam is fathomable for ethnic revolutionary uprising and communal riots. The leaders behind the uprising and riots pull the youth towards them to achieve their purposes. The state ranks low in many development indicators when compared with other states of the country.

The NSS programme encourages the youth students to voluntarily dedicate themselves to associate with the community and to provide their services for nation building. Hence the role of the youth is community building at state level is very crucial. The discontentment aroused was that why a prominent development has not tangibly resulted through NSS in Assam region. Indeed, whether the student volunteers of the NSS in the Assam University and its affiliated colleges have evolved a remarkable change in the society as well as in their personal lives or not. How far their commitment, involvement and contribution in NSS activities, the factors contributing for the success of the NSS programme impacts and the factors constraint to achieve the desired results are major subjects of this study.

Research Methodology

The researcher has selected Assam University and its affiliated colleges as the field of study and the study is specifically conducted in four Districts namely; Cachar, Hailakandi, Karimganj, Dima Hasao of Assam state.

Objectives of the Study

1. To observe the motivational factors that enables the students to join the National Service Scheme (NSS).
2. To analyse the range of the NSS activities implemented by the Assam University and its affiliated colleges.
3. To assess the outcomes, impacts and challenges of the NSS on the student volunteers and the community services in Assam State.
4. To find out the positive development of NSS student volunteers in community services.

Research Design

The present study employed descriptive research design to garner information on the positive development of NSS on student volunteers and the overall impact of NSS on community development. This study ascribes the socio-economic background of NSS volunteers. This research design was chosen for this study as it aims to identify the motivational factors in joining NSS, assessed the frequency of activities undertaken by the University/ College, observe the level of participation of NSS volunteers, identify the loopholes encountered while implementing the scheme in the hope to rectify and bring about significant changes in implementation the scheme. The level of awareness and opinions of respondents are described in detail.

Sample Design

Universe: The universe of this study includes all the NSS volunteers under the Jurisdiction of Assam University. As per the available record of NSS cell of Assam University the number of students who had enrolled in NSS was 3606 in 2017. This datum has been considered as the Universe of this study.

Population: From the list of NSS units under the jurisdiction of Assam University 18 NSS units were selected for this study. The total number of NSS volunteers from 18 NSS units was 2232. This has been considered as a population size of this study.

Sample Size: As the Population of this study was 2232a minimum of 418 sample size was selected for the purpose of this study from 18 NSS units.

Sampling Techniques:

Stage 1: From the list of the NSS unit under the Jurisdiction of Assam University 18units were selectedby using convenient sampling technique.

Stage 2: Selection of Respondent was done by using Probability Sampling technique. To select the respondent Simple Random technique was employed. The respondent was selected randomly from the each unit.

Sources of Data Collection

The primary data for the study was collected from the NSS volunteers of selected the NSS units from 4 districts under the Jurisdiction of Assam University. Face to face interview was conducted using the interview schedule. Secondary source data concerning the subject matters of the study were collected from journals, books, edited books, reports, documents and websites. The collected literature reviews were utilised for identifying the gaps in the studies and for developing the tool.

Tools of Data Collection

The interview schedule was used as the primary tool of data collection. Interview schedule was constructed based upon the objectives and research questions to collect field level data. The NSS Volunteers are the primary respondents of this study.

Pre-test

Constructed interview schedule was pre-tested for reliability and validity. Content validity and face validity were administered to collect appropriate responses to measure the intended objectives and to avoid misinterpretation of the questions, respectively. Twenty respondents were interviewed to check the responses and after crosschecking the data it resulted, that the interviewed scheduled was effective.

Analysis and interpretation of the data

The collected and collated data were codified, fed into the computer and analysed. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences was used for data feeding and analysis. The analysed tables and statistical tests were presented with suitable interpretation.

Major finding: The followings are the major finding the study:

Motivational Factors

- The present study found that majority of the Respondents 87.6% of them got to know about NSS from their teachers and it was the teachers who encouraged them in joining NSS.
- Majority of the Respondents 95.5% joined NSS because they wanted to understand the community better, 95.7% joined NSS to learn more about the world through new and different learning experience, and 98.1% joined out of their desire to work for National Integration, 93.8% to empower the less privilege or the vulnerable section of the society.
- The present study also found that 56.9% of the respondents joined NSS in order to fulfill their academic requirements and 85.6% joined NSS to be associated with their Co- NSS volunteers. Majority of the Respondents 85.6% expressed that they also joined NSS because they like the NSS program officer in their college.

Level Awareness of Respondent about NSS, its programme and activities

- The present study found only 35.9% were aware about the minimum hours (240 hours) they have to devote as NSS volunteers for consecutive of two years.
- Majority of the respondents 59.8% were aware about the adopted villages that their NSS unit has adopted for implementation of National Service Scheme..
- Majority of the Respondents 72.5% were not aware about the variety of NSS awards.
- It was observed that 62.2% of them were well aware about NSS Regular activity.

Opinion of the Respondent about the Scheme and Other Important Indicators in Implementation of National Service Scheme

- The present study found that Majority of the Respondent 57.4% opined that participating in NSS would strengthen their career opportunities.
- Majority of the respondents 63.6% opined that they were strongly agree that NSS contributes to the development of the country.
- The present study found a vast majority of the respondents 99.3% opined and felt that there is a need to encourage the other Youth to join NSS.
- The present study found that majority of the respondents 97.8% opined and expressed that they became more sensitive towards community issues after joining NSS.
- The present study found 94.3% of the respondents opined that an equal opportunity was given to every NSS volunteers to participate in NSS activities.
- It is observed that majority of the respondents 57.4% opined that NSS improved National unity to greater extend and promote National integration among the youths in India.
- The present study found that majority of the respondents 86.8% opined that the Program officers in various colleges performed their role adequately.
- The opinion of the respondents 90.0% indicated that NSS program officers had significantly contributed in shaping the personality of NSS volunteers.
- It is observed that NSS program officers from 18 NSS unit under Assam University Jurisdiction had significantly taken initiatives in implementation of NSS activities.
- The study also found that majority of the respondents 81.6% opined that NSS student leaders performed his/her role adequately and found that NSS student leaders also had a crucial role in the process of shaping the personality of NSS volunteers during their tenure. It is observed

that 85.4% of the respondents opined that NSS student leaders took initiatives in implementation of the NSS activities at the college level.

Frequency of NSS Programmes and Activities under taken by the University/ College

- It is observed that Tree plantation, Swach Bharat Abhiyan, Campaigns, observation the National days were some of the major activities which were conducted regularly by NSS unit under Assam University, Silchar jurisdiction.
- However, it is also observed that each unit has got different variety of programmes and activities based on needs of the area of implementation of the scheme.
- Majority of the respondents 49.0% expressed that Youth festivals was conducted occasionally.
- The present study also found that Blood donation is organized occasionally by the NSS units under the jurisdiction of Assam University.
- Majority of the respondents 62.4% expressed that Conference/workshop/training was organized occasionally by their NSS units.
- Majority of the respondents 77.0% responded that NSS organized and celebrated National Days regularly.
- The present study also found that 63.2 % NSS unit organized various Campaigns on regularly basis.

Participation of Respondents

- It is found that majority of the respondents 58.9% have participated in environment enrichment and conservation programmes organized by NSS. Majority of the respondents 57.2% had never participated in any production oriented programmes
- This study also found that most of the respondents 44.5% participated in awareness programmes on improvement of the status of women.63.4% had also participated extremely in Social Service Programmes.
- Majority of the respondents 82.6% had never participated in any inter-state youth exchange programme as this kind of opportunity are very limited and only few volunteers got to participated.
- Majority of the respondents 61.7% had never participated in any National Integration Camp.
- This finding of this study also observed that majority of the respondents 60.8% received orientation programme and this orientation programme helped them got familiar with the concept of NSS and its programmes and activities.
- Majority of the respondents 58.1% had attended Training on Disaster Management and trained themselves to involve in Rescue and Relief when any Natural disaster occurred.

Impact of NSS on NSS volunteer and Community

- This study found that most of the respondents 62.7% agree that NSS increased their readiness to serve for a Nation.
- Around 64.4% of the respondents were strongly agree that through their association with NSS they have gained confidence to work in a team.
- The present study found that more than 61.7% of the respondents express that NSS enabled them to maintain their self discipline and around 63.4% of them were strongly agree that NSS enabled them to become responsible.

- The present study found that NSS is having a great significant impact in the community. The present study found 61.2% of the respondents agree that NSS improved the awareness among the community about health and sanitation issues in the community.
- 66.0% of the respondents expressed that NSS enable the local people to utilize the community resources properly.

Challenges in carrying NSS activities

- Majority of the respondents 54.8% of the respondents express that inadequate allocation of time to engage in NSS is another a moderate challenges they faced in carrying the NSS activities as most of the time they are fully occupied with their curriculum and found little time for NSS activities.
- It is observes that lack or inadequate orientation programme given to NSS volunteers is another challenges for effective implementation the NSS activities.
- Despite the funds allotted to the NSS units is very limited to organized NSS programmes and activities, irregularity of allocation the funds on time is one of the major challenges that every Units were facing.

Positive Development of NSS Volunteers

Competency

- 56.9% of the respondents had critical awareness about Social issues to a better degree.
- Majority 57.4% of the respondents had improved their academic scoring significantly to better extend.
- More than half of the respondents 54.8% had gained communication skills to better extend.
- A sizeable of 51.4% of respondents had improved their leadership skills to better extend

Confidence

- Majority of the respondents 53.1% of them had developed confidence to face the challenges to a great extend.
- Most of the respondents that is 53.6% expressed that their association with NSS enabled them to gained better self esteem to better extend.
- The present study found that around 62.7% of the respondents had increased their confidence and shared that their association with NSS increased their capacity to produce any expected tasks to better extend.

Connection

- The result of this study found that 52.6% of the respondents stated that NSS improved their relationship with the family to great extend.
- A proportionate of 48.3% of the Respondents expressed that their relationship with their immediate society has improved to better extend.
- Most of the respondents 58.9% stated that their association with NSS had improved their relationship with the working team having members of different socio-economic to great extend.

Character

- It is observed that majority of the respondents 58.9% stated that NSS enabled them to be able to highly respect and value the disadvantaged people of different socio-economic backgrounds to great extend.
- Most of the respondents 52.6% they showed and were highly respectable towards the framed rules of a set up.
- It is found that majority of the respondents 57.9% expressed that through NSS experiences they were able and willing to accept the responsibility for their wrong action to great extends.

Caring

- The present study found that a proportionate 58.9% were highly empathetic and felt pity towards people in distress to great extend.
- A sizeable number of 57.9% of the respondents shared that they were highly able to understand the shared feeling of people in distress to great extend.
- This study also found that majority of the respondents 61.0% were able to help the people in distress to great extend.

Suggestion

Government

- An effective monitoring mechanism needs to be in place for enhancing the effective functioning of NSS at the college and the University level.
- An Adequate fund needs to be allotted to the University in time and accordingly University will distribute the funds to the colleges.

College/ University

- Many NSS Volunteers from most of the Colleges were from school of Social Sciences. The University and Colleges needs to take the initiative and reach out the student from other stream or professional courses as well.
- It is suggested that the enrolment of student in college and university needs to reach out and encourage student from Schedule Tribe, Schedule Caste and other minority student to enroll in NSS.
- Coordination and networking with Government departments, NGOs or any support agencies etc will improve and enhance the implementation of NSS activities efficiently.
- Women Programme Officers should be increased, which will be helpful for Participation of girl's volunteer.
- A regular Orientation programme of students is a must, because students should be capable of analyzing the things between.
- Orientation programme should also be given to the other faculty members in the college by the NSS program Coordinator in order to sensitize them about the seriousness of NSS.
- It is observed that there are some NSS units under the Jurisdiction of Assam University who have not organized any Special camp. All NSS unit need to organize Special Camp regularly there must be powerful mechanism using in evaluation and assessment by Assam University to monitor the functioning and implementation of the scheme at the college level.

Conclusion

National Service Scheme plays a major role in contributing to inclusive model, simply because volunteers are the bridges between development and the community. The proximity of volunteers to the people sensitizes them to their needs, thus they can channelize projects to meet societal needs. The students enrolled under NSS have shown better understanding of social issues and have exhibited volunteerism at times of need. NSS unite the youth of all backgrounds in a common cause and help address many unmet social needs. The motto of the National Service Scheme is "Not Me, But You". Never before has the country needed to mobilize the enormous energies and talents of Indians through national service

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SPEECH RECOGNITION (AUDIO SIGNAL) AND VIDEO STREAMING PART (AUDIO SIGNAL) COMPRESSION BASED ON –DE DUPLICATION TECHNIQUES IN CLOUD COMPUTING

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Abstract

An existing voice recognition searching techniques could be fetching index block related data only. But this searching may not be feasible to all the users because utilizing Internet includes blind users also. The existing searching technique allows all to view video streaming part. The blind users mostly did not access text related resources. This paper enhances different searching techniques for a blind user for searching voice signal wave based. The voice signal wave is useful for comparing video streaming part. The blind users recognize audio signal wave 'sonly but not video signal. Those result also can be possible on replication data. It is also complicate of searching video for blind user. In this situation we can avoid duplication data in a simple algorithm manner. The algorithm based on which audio streaming part has more replicating words based on count based to fetch a data from the server in could computing.

Keywords: Introduction, Speech Recognition, Speech Recognition Cloud Storage, Algorithms, Pattern Matching Algorithms. MFCC Algorithm, DeDuplication Algorithm.

Introduction

Speech processing is one of the existing technologies of signal processing. The goal of speech recognition area is to develop technique system which enable us to communicate with a human. The speech is one of the natural forms of communication. The upcoming technology has made it possible for searching a resource in voice recognition manners. Speech recognition of a person that enable machine to understand and recognize system with help of an Algorithm. A speech recognition methods can be divide into

Text independent, and text dependent methods. Mostly people use the Speech recognition technique for security purpose and a few people to search a resource over the internet. The paper enlighten a blind user to search resource of voice signal wave with the existing matching pattern technique. The voice signal to matchin a text content after we get a result. But here proposal for this system of voice signal did not go to any text matching pattern. It is to enhance the next level searching technique the user can search a resource voice audio signal way those audio signal information going to match in database both of the audio signals is matching the user can retrieve the information. In this technique we reduce searching technique because in existing technique, the user voice Converting with a text in a data base text both of them are equal in what we are getting results for the user. But in this proposal searching technique it is going directly matching to data base audios this searching way we reduce time for computation and mainly the blind user to feasible for searching resources in a web. The other aspects of speech recognition which people use to interact with a machine is very complicated because human normally communicate with different sounds. Essentially humans pronoun a word in mouth and deliver the words in a different

slang and other problem is while using to interact with a computer arising following this kinds of problems like as (Background noise, Speech interference, Sound reflection, Non stationary events, Signal degradation, Unknown words, unusual circumstance, and Secker sound artifacts) in this complicate problem to resolving MFCC algorithm. While the blind user to searching a resources to voice recognition based may not getting accuracy results because more much of replication could be arising the audio searching technique. In this situation we can avoid this Complexity of problem. Here we are going to apply data de-duplication techniques. the different types of de-duplication technique to resolve this problem but predicting block level de-duplication technique for the reason we are may not searching index based text resource so block level technique to feasible user here avoiding replication data to implementing with a algorithm manner.

Speech Recognition

Language is most important for communication and speech. Language contributes to our understanding of the production, perception, processing and learning use. Spoken interaction between humans and machines is certainly fixed in the laws and conditions of Communication, Speech recognition, or speech-to-

text, involves capturing and digitizing the sound waves, and contextually analyzing the words to ensure correct spelling for words that sound alike. Speech Recognition is the ability of a computer to recognize general, naturally flowing sounds from a wide variety of users. Early attempts to design systems for automatic speech recognition were mostly following acoustic-phonetics, the phonetic essentials of speech the basic sounds of the language and goes These elements include the phonemes and the corresponding place and manner of pronunciation used to produce the sound in various phonetic slangs. The above speech recognition system model to the human can to record resource analog signal wave format those signal wave to store on database. The Acoustic preprocessing it is resolves communication channel problem user can pronounce a word different context frequency and phonetic slangs those complexity of problem to resolve the DFT and MFCC algorithm. Time warping used to recognize. Spoken words by comparing their feature vectors with a database.

Acoustic pre-processing

The user produces speech sounds, the air flow from a speaker lungs first passes the glottis and then throat and mouth. Those acoustic pronounce problem overcome to following certain possible ways.

Voiced Excitation

The glottis is closed. The air pressure forces the glottis to open and close periodically thus generating a periodic pulse train range frequency from 80Hz to 350Hz.

Unvoiced Excitation

The glottis is open and the air passes a narrow passage in the throat or mouth. This results in a

turbulence which generates a noise signal. The spectral shape of the noise is determined by the location of the narrowness.

Transient excitation

A closure in the throat or mouth will raise the air pressure. By suddenly opening the closure the air pressure drops down immediately. ("plosive burst") depends upon the shape the sounds is moderate

Speech recognition Algorithms

The different problem arising while human to interact with computer those problem can be resolve following algorithms are RCC, MFCC, LPC, LPCC and PLPC. These are the most commonly used technique in many application for feature extraction especially in speaker recognition, speech recognition, biometric systems etc. This section provides a brief overview of the above algorithms.

- RCC (Real Cepstral Coefficients)
- MFCC (Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients),
- LPC (Linear Predictive Coding)
- LPCC (LPC-Derived or Linear Predictive Cepstral Coefficients)
- PLPC (Perceptual Linear Predictive Cepstral Coefficients)
- PCA (Principal Component analysis) LDA (Linear Discriminant analysis) ICA (Independent Component Analysis)

Speech processing are commonly to following depending on criteria

Speech Recognition

- Isolated Word Reorganization (IWR), Continuous Speech
- Recognition (CSR), Key-Word Recognition (KWR), Speech
- Understanding **Speaker Recognition:**
- Speaker Verification (SV), Speaker Identification (SI)
- Language Identification (LI).

Speech Coding and Digitization

- Waveform Coding,
- Source Coding Using Analysis/Synthesis,
- Vector Quantization (VQ),

Multiplexing

- Speech Enhancement Noise Reduction
- Interference
- Reduction,
- Speech Transformations (Rate and Pitch)
- Distortion Compensation

Speech Synthesis

- Synthesis from Coded Speech

- Synthesis from Text

Pattern Matching Algorithms

The proposal system through audio signal wave search those audio signal is going to compare data base audio wave those searching technique both audio wave while a matching the human getting accuracy results consist of matching pattern techniques. The pattern matching technique or classification will be done more application in most speech processing application. Some of the algorithm are VQ, HMM, GMM, SVM, MLP, DTW etc.

VQ (Vector Quantization)

It is the classical quantization technique of signal processing which permits the modeling of probability density functions by the dividing of prototype vectors. The process starts by splitting a large set of points into clusters or groups having approximately the same number of points nearest to them. Centroid point represents each group. The density matching property of this quantization technique is very powerful, mainly in the density of large and high-dimensional data identification. Data points are shown by their closest centroid indexing, frequently occurring data have low error, and rare data high error. Hence, this method is also appropriate for loss data compression.

HMM (Hidden Markov Models)

HMM is a popular statistical tool for modeling a huge range of time series data. In the context of natural language processing (NLP), HMMs are usually applied with great success to problems such as part-of-speech tagging and noun -phrase chunking. This powerful statistical tool is also used for modeling generative sequences that can be distinguished by an underlying process generating an observable sequence. HMMs have wide range of applications especially interested in signal processing which is more particular about speech processing and it has been used with success in low level NLP processes such as phrase chunking, extracting necessary information from documents and part-of-speech tagging.

GMM (Gaussian Mixture Model)

GMM is a probabilistic model used for density clustering and estimation. This model can be regarded as a special continuous HMM which has single state. GMMs are very effective in modeling multi-modal distributions. GMMs training and testing requirements are very less compared to the requirements of a general continuous HMM. GMM is based on the hypothesis that all the vectors are independent.

SVM (Support Vector Machines)

SVMs have proven to be most powerful method for pattern classification. SVM maps the input into a high-dimensional space and then distinguishes the classes with a hyper plane. A crucial aspect of opting SVMs successfully is due to the design of the inner product, the kernel, caused by the high dimensional mapping. The application of SVMs can be speaker and language recognition. It is a two-class classifier or also called as binary classifier. SVM can be considered as competitive and complimentary system to other approaches, such as Gaussian mixture models (GMMs).

MLP (Multi-Layer Perceptron's)

MLPs are neural network based classifiers. They are used mainly for the powerful structure in

classifying complex, nonlinear instances and in regression. Critical parameters such as learning rate, size of hidden layer, transfer functions in both hidden and output layers can be well optimized to get best results for the specific purpose.

DTW (Dynamic Time Warping)

DTW is one of the Dynamic Programming technique based algorithm. This algorithm is mainly used for measuring similarity between two time series which may change in time or speed. This method is also used to find the optimal alignment between two time series if one time series may be “warped” non-linearly by stretching or shrinking it along its time axis. This warping between two time series can further be used to determine similar regions between the two time series or to find the similarity between the two time series.

MFFC and DTW Algorithms

The most of the problem arising the correlation of the signal wave regarding those correlation problem we can use for two more efficient algorithms (MFFC and DTW).

MFFC Algorithm

The extraction of the best parametric representation of acoustic signals is an important task to produce a better recognition performance. The efficiency of this phase is important for the next phase since it affects its behavior. MFCC is based on human hearing perceptions which cannot perceive frequencies over 1Khz. In other words, MFCC is based on known variation of the human ear’s critical bandwidth with frequency. MFCC has two types of filter which are spaced linearly at low frequency below 1000 Hz and logarithmic spacing above 1000Hz. A subjective pitch is present on Mel Frequency Scale to capture important characteristic of phonetic in speech.

MFCC consists of seven computational steps. Each step has its function and mathematical approaches further to discussing about all steps.

Step 1: Pre-emphasis

This step processes the passing of signal through a filter which emphasizes higher frequencies. This process will increase the energy of signal at higher frequency.

$$Y[n] = X[n] - 0.95 X[n-1]$$

Let’s consider $a = 0.95$, which make 95% of any one sample is pre-summed to originate from previous sample.

Step 2: Framing

The process of segmenting the speech samples obtained from analog to digital conversion (ADC) into a small frame with the length within the range of 20 to 40 msec. The voice signal is divided into frames of N samples. Adjacent frames are being separated by M ($M < N$).

Step 3: Hamming windowing

Hamming window is used as window shape by considering the next block in feature extraction processing chain and integrates all the closest frequency lines. The Hamming window equation is given as: If the window is defined as $W(n)$, $0 \leq n \leq N-1$ where

N = number of samples in each frame
 $Y[n]$ = Output signal
 $X(n)$ = input signal
 $W(n)$ = Hamming window, then the result of windowing signal is shown below:
 $Y_n X_n W_n$
 $w(n) = 0.54 - 0.46 \cos \left(\frac{2\pi n}{N-1} \right)$

Step 4: Fast Fourier Transform

To convert each frame of N samples from time domain into frequency domain. The Fourier Transform is to convert the convolution of the glottal pulse $U[n]$ and the vocal tract impulse response $H[n]$ in the time domain. This statement supports the equation be-low:

$$Y(w) = FFT \{ h(t) * X(t) \} = H(w) * X(w) \tag{4}$$

If $X(w)$, $H(w)$ and $Y(w)$ are the Fourier Transform of $X(t)$, $H(t)$ and $Y(t)$ respectively.

Step 5: Mel Filter Bank Processing

The frequencies range in FFT spectrum is very wide and voice signal does not follow the linear scale. The bank of filters according to Mel scale is then performed. The filtering is upcoming it reduce based on plenty of algorithm is implements the scale of voice measuring depends upon the pitch to different form one user to another users.

Mel scale filter bank this figure shows a set of triangular filters that are used to compute a weighted sum of filter spectral components so that the output of process approximates to a Mel scale. Each filter’s magnitude frequency response is triangular in shape and equal to unity at the center frequency and decrease linearly to zero at center frequency of two adjacent filters. Then, each filter output is the sum of its filtered spectral components. After that the following equation is used to compute the Mel for given frequency f in HZ

$$F(Mel) = 2595 \log_{10} \left(1 + \frac{f}{700} \right)$$

Step 6: Discrete Cosine Transform

This is the process to convert the log Mel spectrum into time domain using Discrete Cosine Transform (DCT). The result of the conversions is called Mel Frequency Cepstrum Coefficient. The set of coefficient is called acoustic vectors. Therefore, each input utterance is transformed into a sequence of acoustic vector.

Step 7: Delta Energy and Delta Spectrum

The voice signal and the frames changes, such as the slope of a formant at its transitions. Therefore, there is a need to add features related to the change in cepstral features over time. 13 delta or velocity features (12 cepstral features plus energy), and 39 features a double delta or acceleration feature are added. The energy in a frame for a signal x in a window from time sample t_1 to time sample t_2 , is represented at the equation below Suppose we have two time series Q and C , of length n and m respectively, where:

$$Q = q_1, q_2, \dots, q_i, \dots, q_n \tag{1}$$

$$C = c_1, c_2, \dots, c_j, \dots, c_m \tag{2}$$

To align two sequences using DTW, an n -by- m matrix where the (i th, j th) element of the matrix contains the distance $d(q_i, c_j)$ between the two points q_i and c_j is constructed. Then, the absolute distance between the values of two sequences is calculated using the Euclidean distance computation.

MFFC input flow diagram

DTW Algorithm

DTW algorithm is based on Dynamic Programming techniques as describes in this algorithm is for measuring similarity between two time series which may vary in time or speed. This technique also used to find the optimal alignment between two times series if one time series may be “warped” non-linearly by stretching or shrinking it along its time axis. This warping between two time series can then be used to find corresponding regions between the two time series or to determine the similarity between the two time series.

DWT Time Flow Diagram

Monotonic Condition

The path will not turn back on itself, both i and j indexes either stay the same or increase, they never decrease.

Continuity condition

The path advances one step at a time. Both i and j can only increase by 1 on each step along the path.

Boundary Condition: The Path starts at the bottom Left and ends at the top right.

Adjustment Window Condition

A good path is unlikely to wander very far from the diagonal. The distance that the path is allowed to wander is the window length r .

Slope Constraint Condition

The path should not be too steep or too shallow. This prevents very short sequences matching very long ones. The condition is expressed as a ratio n/m where m is the number of steps in the x direction and n is the number in the y direction. After m steps in x you must make a step in y and vice versa.

De-duplication Algorithm

The user can searching a resources in a voice signal wave to compare to with help of matching pattern technique. The results to produce all equaling Matching signal in this situation to the results to Producing lot of reduplication data. We can avoiding those replication data to following certain algorithms. Here we can searching a resources from a database block level de -duplication .the block level de duplication there are did not referring to index reference. In a database user can search audio resource only all the audio resource in particular in block to segregated. Those part of resource to searching user in speech recognition way. While user to giving Commends process following matching pattern technique all the equivalent resource in a audio parts which words is more than time using audio streaming on particular data only to fetching a database.

De-duplication proposal algorithm

Start

Step1: input commends

Step2: MFFC and DWT radios

Step3: matching pattern techniques

Step4: higher priority matching words

Step5: accuracy results

Stop

In this algorithm implementation we can to reduce to De-duplications data.

Conclusion

The main purpose of this paper to essay way searching resource a blind user over the web in could. The blind user searching a resources with help of speech recognition technique. The existing speech recognition technique to covert user analog input commend text way pattern matching based on process but the proposal technique did not matching a text matching pattern in this algorithm only to matching audio based resources in this way to increasing searching method is very high speed. The de-duplication technique algorithm to reduce a replication data in simple algorithm manner to getting accuracy result for blind user and feasible to searching a resource over the web.

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VIRTUAL CONNECT - A SPECIAL REFERENCE TO CHENNAI CITY

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Abstract

Virtual connect is a multimedia communication protocol in a server-client environment. The various connections of communication are Short Messaging Service (SMS), Email and Social Network Sites (SNS). Given the fact that communication is one of the basic necessities to human life, it has been considerably improved and enhanced for ease and expedience in every era right from the earliest known communication. Apart from face to face communication, other forms of communication can only be made successful by an intermediary. People have therefore invented media technologies that attempt to circumvent these limits to allow remote forms of communication. This is what is meant by Mediated Communication. It is any kind of communication that uses some form of intermediary for it to be accomplished. The emergence of Internet and cell phone communication in the current age of information has triggered a lot of interest from researchers. The focus of this paper is on the adaptation and use of the internet and the mobile phones among college students. The starting point is that the spread and frequency of the use of the internet and the mobile phones has increased rapidly and over a short time primarily along with the adaptation of smart phones. We find that the main argument for using the internet and the mobile phone is that it is possible, easy and convenient with the proper handset and subscription.

Keywords: SMS, Email, Social Networking Sites, Gender differences

Introduction

A **social network service** or **social networking service**, most often called SNS, is a medium for establishing social networks of people who share interests and/or activities. Social networking sites allow users to share ideas, activities, events, and interests within their individual networks. Most social network services are web based and provide means for users to interact in various ways, such as e-mail and instant messaging. SNS includes WhatsApp, instant messaging, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, You tube, Orkut, BlogSpot, Tumblr, Pinterest, Instagram, Flickr, Skype, Myspace, Meetup, etc

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the various aspects with respect to awareness, usage and purpose of virtual media and place of use of internet by college students of both gender.
2. To analyze the difference between boys and girls with respect to usage of virtual media, frequency of usage, no. of connections and no. of online friends.
3. To study the problems of virtual media and satisfaction level of the respondents in its usage.

Limitations of the Study

This study limited only to 100 respondents and they all belongs to the age category of 17 -20 Years and also it concentrated only Chennai city College Students.

Review of Literature

Article titled “Assessing Middle School Students’ Knowledge of Conduct and Consequences and Their Behaviors Regarding the Use of Social Networking Sites” was researched by Stacey I.kite, Robert cable, and Lawrence filippelli. Cyber bullying and threats of Internet predators, not to mention the enduring consequences of postings, may lead to dangerous, unspeakable consequences. Cyber bullying and threats of Internet predators through social networking sites and instant messaging programs are initiating numerous problems for parents, school administrators, and law enforcement on a national level.

Article titled “College students Facebook stalking of ex-partners” was researched by Amy Lyndon, Ph.D., Jennifer Bonds-Raacke, Ph.D., and Alyssa D. Cratty, B.A. There are abundant anecdotes and warnings of inappropriate behaviors on social networking sites, particularly about Facebook. So, this examined, whether individuals obsessively monitor or harass their ex-partners on Facebook (related to general ‘Facebook stalking’) and, if so, whether those individuals would also engage in cyber obsessional pursuit (COP) and obsessive relational pursuit (ORI), which are categories of cyberstalking and stalking.

Research Methodology

Sample size of the study is 100. The samples were collected from the college students in Chennai city between 17- 20 Years. The structures Questionnaire were collected through Google Forms. Random sampling technique was used to select a samples. Due to time Constraints Percentage method used to analyze the study.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Gender Profile of Respondents

S.No	Gender	No of Respondents	Percentage
1	Boys	50	50
2	Girls	50	50

The above table depicts the profile of respondents with respect to Gender. 100 respondents are taken for the study, out of which 50 respondents are boys and 50 are girls each. They are all under graduate students in age group of 17 - 20 years.

Table 2: Hours of usage of Media per day (in percentage)

S.No	Media	< 1 hr	1 - 2 hrs	2 - 3 hrs	3 - 4 hrs	> 4 hrs	Never
1	News paper	78	-	-	-	-	22
2	Television	9	17	15	21	34	4
3	Radio	29	5	-	1	5	60
4	Internet	14	25	35	10	16	-
5	Mobile phone	4	13	12	21	50	-

From the above table, it is evident that 78% of respondents read newspapers for less than an hour and 22% of the students never read newspaper at all. Likewise, listening to radio has almost become obsolete among today’s teens with 60% of them stating that they do not listen to radio. 50% of the respondents spend more than 4 hours on mobile phones for sending Short messaging service, for chatting with their friends or using the social networking sites on the mobile phones. Internet usage per day is in the range of 2 or 3 hours for 35% of the respondents. Also 34% of the respondents watch TV for more than 4 hours per day.

Table 3: Awareness of Services

S.No	Virtual connect Services	%
1	Short Messaging Service (Text)	100
2	E-mail	92
3	Social Networking Sites	
	a Facebook	94
	b You tube	93
	c WhatsApp	96
	d Orkut	80
	e Twitter	71
	f Skype	66
	g Instant messenger	53
	h LinkedIn	28
	i Blog Spot	28
	j Flickr	22
	k My Space	19
	l Instagram	56
	m MeetUp	12
	n Tumblr	10
	n Pinterest	6

Table 4: Hours of usage per day

S. No	Types of Virtual Connect	Hours of Usage per day (in percentage)				
		< 30 mins	30 mins - 1 hr	1 hr - 2 hrs	2 - 4 hrs	> 4 hrs
1	Short Messaging Service (Text)	6	8	12	34	40
2	Email	76	14	10	0	0
3	Social Networking Sites (SNS)	22	32	18	12	16

The above table indicates the awareness of virtual connect services among college students. Noticeably, all the students are aware about Short Messaging Services, but only 92% of the students are aware about e-mail. With respect to the various Social Networking Sites, 94% of the students are aware about Facebook, followed by 96% WhatsApp and 93% about You Tube, 80% about Orkut, 71% about Twitter, 66% about Skype and 56%

about Instant messenger. However, only less than 30% of the respondents are aware of the rest of the SN sites with the least awareness for MeetUp (12%), Tumblr (10%) and Pinterest (6%).

The above table indicates that most of the college students (40%) use mobile phones for Short Messaging Service more than 4 hours in a day. Only 6% of them use Short Messaging Service for less than 30 minutes per day.

In the case Social Networking Sites of Email, most of them (76%) chat & send Email for less than 30 minutes in a day. However, no one uses it for more than 2 hours in a day. In the case of logging on to these sites for 30 minutes to one hour in a day is done by 32% of the respondents, followed by 22% of them who visit Social Networking Sites for less than 30 minutes in a day. Only 12% of the respondents visit Social Networking Sites for 2-4 hours in a day.

Table 5: Place of use of Internet

S.No	Place of use of Internet	Percentage
1	System / Laptop @ home	67
2	Friend's house	9
3	Browsing Centre	15
4	Mobile phone	78
5	Relative's house	13

The above table indicates that most of the students prefer using internet on their mobile phones or system at home (78% and 67% respectively). Only 9% of the students use internet in their friend's house. Usage in Browsing centers and relative's houses are also comparatively less (15% and 13% respectively).

The above table indicates that, 100% of both boys and girls use Short messaging service, but more number of boys (88%) use Email, than girls (78%). It is also depicted in the above table that with respect to Facebook and You Tube, more number of boys (96% and 90% respectively) uses them than girls. However, interestingly the most noticeable difference between boys and girls is with respect to Orkut and Instant messenger. Boys (76%) use Orkut more than girls (20%), whereas girls use Instant messenger (44%) more than boys (16%). Boys do not use Flickr, BlogSpot, LinkedIn,

MySpace and Tumblr at all, but there are a small percentage of girls who use all these services. With respect to Pinterest and Meetup, both boys and girls do not use them at all.

Table 6: Usage of Services

S.No	Virtual connect Services	Boys (%)	Girls (%)
1	Short Messaging Service (SMS)	100	100
2	Email	88	78
3	Social Networking Sites (SNS)		
	a Facebook	96	84
	b You tube	90	82
	c WhatsApp	92	94
	d Orkut	76	20
	e Skype	44	48
	f Twitter	34	32
	g Instant messenger	16	44
	h Flickr	0	12
	i Blog Spot	0	8
	j Instagram	6	8
	k LinkedIn	0	4
	l My Space	0	2
	m Tumblr	0	2
	n Pinterest	0	0
	o Meetup	0	0

Table 7: Frequency of Usage

S.No	Types of Virtual Connect	Frequency of Usage (in Percentage)											
		Constantly Online (24*7)		Several times a day		Once in a day		Once in 3 days		Once in a week		Rarely (< Once in a week)	
		Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
1	SMS	28	28	21	16	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	2
2	Email	0	2.41	1.2	4.82	14.46	12.05	14.46	2.41	15.66	9.64	13.25	9.64
3	SNS	0	11.33	13.33	10.8	43	7	5.33	5.14	12.66	4.67	10.33	9.11

The above table indicates the frequency with which the students log on to the above services. In case of SMS, 28% of both boys and girls are constantly on, in order to connect with their friends. Only 1% of boys use SMS once in 3 days and 2 % of girls use Short messaging service less than once a week. In the case of email, 15.66% of the boys and 9.64% of the girls use it once a week followed by 14.46% of the boys and 12.05% of the girls using it once a day. Only 2.41% of the girls and 1.2%

of the boys use it constantly and several times a day respectively. Thus more number of both genders uses it once a day.

In the case of SNS, 12.66% of boys and 43% of the boys use it once a week and once a day respectively. None of the boys use Social networking sites on a 24*7 basis, while 11.33% of the girls are online all the time.

Findings

- The most popular media seems to be mobile phones followed by internet and TV, with usage of more than 2 hours per day. Noticeably 60% of the respondents never listen to radio and 78% of the respondents read newspaper for less than 1 hour per day.
- Most awareness about WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram among the students.
- Majority of the respondents use Short Messaging Service (40%) for more than 4hours, Email(70%) for less than 30 minutes and Social Networking Sites (32%) for 30 minutes to 1 hour in a day.
- Majority (28% each) of both boys and girls are constantly on, in order to chat or send forwards to their friends through Short messaging services (Text). Noticeably majority of boys (14.46%) and girls (12.05%) use Email once in a day and 13.33% of boys and 10.8% girls use social networking sites several times a day.

Conclusion

From this study, it concludes that almost all the girls and boys are aware about the SMS, Email and Social Networking Sites as because of the usage of Smart Phones and the word of Mouth and the Present environment. And the usage SMS has reduced as because of the intervention of Social Networking Sites. The usage of Social networking sites is there among the boys and girls but the usage is more among girls when compared to boys. Radio and television usage also get reduced as because of Smart phones advancement. Finally, Advancement in the technologies replacing the old technology as they are getting the features inbuilt in the new technologies.

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A RESEARCH STUDY - IMPACT OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE ON LEARNING EFFECTIVENESS OF STUDENTS

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Abstract

A well balanced life is one where we spread our energy and effort - emotional, intellectual, imaginative, spiritual and physical between key areas of importance. The neglect of one or more areas, or anchor points, may threaten the vitality of the whole. In past few years, there is a lot of researches were conducted to analyse the linkages between work and family and/or personal life and its affecting factors. The main objectives of the study is to know whether work-life balance / imbalance have an impact on the learning effectiveness of the students, analyze whether the anxiety of getting a job (i.e. perceived employability) affects their learning effectiveness / performance of the students and evaluate whether family expectations / dependency have an impact on the learning effectiveness / performance of the students. The sample for the present study constituted 250 students of both UG & PG from different colleges in Cuddalore of Tamilnadu State, India. The age groups of the sample are between 20-23 years. The respondents were administered with Work-life balance questionnaire constructed by the researchers and the data was obtained. The data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis. Work-life balance remains an issue that requires considerable attention from society. The changing nature of the global economy, where organizations expects the employees to operate on a 24/7 schedule and technological advances have made it possible for an employee to be connected at all times, has ushered the work-life balance issue into the forefront of the minds of many, including students.

Keywords: Work Life Balance, Learning Effectiveness, Performance, Family Expectations, Emotions, Intellectual etc,

Introduction

In the last few decades, there have been a lot of researches which creates the greater understanding about the connectivity between work and family and/or personal life. The term 'Work-life balance' was first started to shuttle from 1986 in reaction to the unhealthy choices occurred in favour of the work place, as they choice to discriminate family, friends and leisure activities in the pursuit of corporate / work goals. A balanced life is one where we spread our energy and effort - emotional, intellectual, imaginative, spiritual and physical - between key areas of importance. This may threaten the vitality of the whole if the employee neglects anything. Work-life balance thus refers to, "The extent to which individuals are equal proportionate involved in-and equal proportionately satisfied with-their work role and their family / personal role ^[9]. "work- family balance provides low levels of inter-role conflict and high levels of inter-role facilitation ⁽⁸⁾". Work-Family Blurring means to "The extent of confusion or difficulty in dividing one's professional work from one's family / personal roles in a given setting which these roles are seen as highly integrated, such as doing paid work at home^[5].

Work-Family Border Theory

Work-family border theory is contributed only to work and family domains. The outcome of interest in this theory is work-family balance, which refers to satisfaction and good functioning at work and at home with a minimum of role conflict ^[4]. It also differs from boundary theory in that its definition of borders encompasses not only those psychological categories but also tangible boundaries that divide the times, place and people associated with work versus family ^[5].

Work-family border theory describes that how individuals manage and negotiate the work and family spheres and the borders between them in order to attain balance. Central to this theory is the idea that 'work' and 'family' constitute different domains or spheres, which influence each other. Given their contrasting purposes and cultures, work and home can be likened to two different countries where there are differences in language or word use, differences in what constitutes acceptable behaviour, and differences in how to accomplish tasks ^[4]. The number of hours worked are an objective indicator of work-life balance. Undeniably, rationality would dictate that the more time an individual puts into one sphere of life, the less time the individual will have for all other spheres.

Connective Mechanisms

A variety of linking mechanisms have been proposed that explain the nature of the relationship between work and family /personal roles , the most prominent of which are conflict (or interference), accommodation, enrichment, compensation, and segmentation. Work-family conflict or interference refers to simultaneous pressures from the work and family domains that are mutually incompatible in some respect such that meeting the demands of one role makes it difficult to meet the demands of the other role. Sometimes referred to as negative spill-over, work-family conflict can take different forms and can originate either in the work domain or the family domain.

Forms of Work-Family Conflict

There are three major forms of work-family conflict that are mentioned in the literature: time-based, strain-based and behaviour-based conflict ^[9]. A time based conflict occurs when the time spent on demands of the one role makes it difficult to fulfil the obligations and requirements of the other role. This type of conflict can occur in two different forms: time pressure associated with attendance in one role domain makes it physically impossible to attend demands in the other role. Time-based conflict can also occur, if a person is physically present but mentally preoccupied with demands from the other domain, so that he or she is not truly concerned with the present situation. Another kind of conflict is the strain-based conflict, which involves role-produced strain. It exists when strain in one role affects one's performance in another role. For example, if an employee who had particularly stressful day at work comes home in a bad mood and takes it out on his family. The third form of conflict is the behaviour-based conflict. It becomes likely, when behaviours that have to be shown in the one domain are incompatible with the behaviours that are accepted in the other domain. The conflict arises when the person fails to recognize the need to adjust his or her behaviour to the culture of the other domain.

Sources of work-family conflict

There are different sources of work-family conflict that can be categorized in three major categories that is

- home demands
- work demands
- Self-imposed demands.

Home demands occur at the home front and cover sources like having small children, large families, number of hours the spouse works a week, conflicts within the family or disagreement about family roles, like different views concerning the duties at home or the importance of the woman's career. Additional to this physical or - in the case of domestic help - material sources, there are the interpersonal demands at home, like caring and loving of the family members.

Work demands include ambiguity or conflict within the work role, workload (hours worked per week, amount and frequency of overtime), inflexibility of work schedule, career stage, low task challenge/variety/importance and high task autonomy.

Self-imposed demands refer to the expectations that a person imposes on his or her own. They occur from the person itself, as they include perfectionism, workaholics and over-achievement drive, which share some overlapping variance with Type A Behaviour, often known as coronary-prone behaviour. Result of this self-imposed demand is a feeling of guilt, which occurs if one cannot live up to one's own expectations. While home and work demands are related to the directional dimensions of the conflict, which is if work interferes with family or family interferes with work, the self-imposed demands can be compared with the dimension of the generation of the conflict, like externally or internally created conflict. Work-family accommodation refers to the process by which individuals reduce their involvement in one role to accommodate the demands of the other role.

Models and Perspectives on Work-Family Balance

Reference [9] mention's different perspectives on the theoretical relationship between work and family. Based on a review of different findings they show the linkage of the career and family domains and the impact of the experiences in one domain (e.g. family) and the outcomes in the other (e.g. work). Two of these perspectives shall be explained here.

The role conflict perspective focuses on the limited resources that an individual has and how multiple roles create strain, when they strive for these resources. It can be compared with the scarcity hypothesis on work family conflict, which postulates that the quantity of human energy is fixed and limited. Therefore, multiple roles create a conflict, the demands of the roles compete about the existing resources and there is less energy for each single role. Role accumulation proposes that multiple roles can be energizing by mutually benefiting each other. Unlike conflict or interference, it refers to the process by which one role strengthens or enriches the quality of the other role. It describes the notion that a variety of resources from work and family roles have the capacity to provide positive experiences in the other role. This perspective on work-family balance is related to the spill over theory, mostly to the positive spill over. This theory suggests that emotions and behaviours in one sphere would carry over to the other. Spill over refers to impacts caused in one domain but experienced in another domain. These emotions can be positive as well as negative, so that multiple roles can be mutually beneficial as well as influence each other in a negative way.

As a result Reference [9] describes three different life-styles that a working woman has to opt for and that depend on the priorities a woman sets in her life. These are career primary orientation, where a woman is strongly committed to her career and subordinates' personal and social life, family-primary orientation, where the emphasis lies on the family the career is pursued

within constraints of family demands, and career-and-family orientation, where an equal emphasis is shown and which is likely to produce a high self-imposed role conflict. These life-styles will be changed and adjusted during the lifetime of the woman manager. There is a limited / scarcity of studies on work-life balance with regard to students. The available literature shows that the graduating students, while looking for a job gives priority to whether the job can provide them the balance between their personal and professional life than the financial package. Also it was found that students look for the working atmosphere, which is more casual, hours more flexible, and better incentives are offered such as better maternity leave or appealing office locations. This is followed closely by an employer that is an industry leader, has high ethical standards, is innovative, has a strong corporate culture and is socially responsible. The present study thus attempts to explore upon how work-life balance / imbalance have an impact on the learning effectiveness of the students and about whether the anxiety of getting a job (i.e. perceived employability) affects their performance. II.

Objectives of the Study

- To know whether work-life balance / \rightarrow imbalance have an impact on the learning effectiveness of the students
- To analyze whether the anxiety of \rightarrow getting a job (i.e. perceived employability) affects their learning effectiveness / performance of the students
- To evaluate whether family expectations \rightarrow / dependency have an impact on the learning effectiveness / performance of the students

Methodology

Sample: The sample for the present study constituted 250 students of both UG & PG from different colleges in Cuddalore of Tamilnadu State, India. The age groups of the sample are between 20-23 years.

Sources of data: The respondents were administered with Work-life balance questionnaire constructed by the researchers and the data was obtained during the period of July September, 2015, this is how primary data was collected and secondary data was collected through reference of Journals, Magazines, Books, etc., Statistical techniques used: The data obtained were subjected to statistical analysis such as Mean, Regression analysis, Correlation, Chi-square and simple percentage analysis.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Showing the Regression analysis between, spending time for part time job outside college hours and percentage of marks of the students

	Co-effecient	Standard deviation	't' value
Spend time for part time job vs. Percentage of Marks	2.371	0.71	-1.001
	-0.83	0.83	

Source: Primary Data

Table2 showing the regression analysis between feeling stressed, as dependency of family and percentage of marks of the students

	Co-efficient	Standard deviation	't' value
Feel stressed as my family is dependent on me vs. Percentage of Marks	1.824	0.336	5.433
	.289	0.180	1.605

Source: Primary Data *** Significant at 0.10 level

Table 3 showing the correlation value between not inclined to study at home and percentage of marks of the students

Variables	Correlation coefficient
Not inclined to study at home vs. Percentage of Marks	0.166

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 showing the correlation value between students' feeling anxious about getting job and time spent on leisure activities

Variables	Correlation coefficient
Feel anxious about getting job vs. time spent on leisure activities	-0.058

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 showing the cross tabulation values between students' feeling anxious about getting job and number of arrear papers

	Feel anxious about getting job	True	False	Total
		No. of arrear papers upto this semester	Nil arrear	149
	One arrear	26	4	30
	Two arrear	23	4	27
	More than 2 arrear	12	3	15
Total		210	40	250

Source: primary data

Table 6 showing the cross tabulation values between percentage of marks of the students and additional time they spend on studies

	No additional time	< 1 hour	1-2 hours	>2 hours	Total	Percentages
<70	8	29	22	12	71	28.4%
70-75	6	26	18	18	68	27.2%
75-85	5	18	29	11	63	25.2%
>85	0	7	20	21	48	19.2%
Total	19	80	89	62	250	--
Percentage	7.6%	30.0%	35.6%	24.8%	-	100%

Source: Primary Data

Table 7 showing chi-square value for the above table

Chi-square	df	Table Value	Significance
27.01163	9	16.91	0.00139

Source: Primary Data

Table 8 showing the cross tabulation values between students’ feeling stressed due to family dependent on him / her and number of arrears

Feel stressed/ Arrear papers	Nil arrear	1 arrear	2 arrear	>2arrear	Total	Percentage
True	25	4	8	7	44	17.6%
False	153	26	19	8	206	82.4%
Total	178	30	27	15	250	---
Percentage	71.2%	12.0%	10.8%	6%	---	100%

Table 9 showing chi-square value for the above table

Chi-square	df	Table Value	Significance
13.36	3	7.81	0.00392

Source: Primary Data

Discussion and Conclusion

1. From Table-1, it was found that there exists an inverse relationship between time spent on part time job and the percentage of marks / performance of the students. This might be due to the division of attention on the part of students, to different chores, which impacts the balance.
2. From Table-2, it was found that there exists linear relationship between stress due to family dependency and percentage of marks. Since the family is dependent on some of the students, they were found to perform better in their studies to meet their expectations and excel in their career.
3. From Table-4, it was found that there exists inverse relationship between the students’ feeling anxious about getting a job and the time they spend for leisure activities. Since the students feel more anxious and preoccupied with the thought of getting a job in the future, they are not involved or not interested in leisure activities.
4. From Table-5 it was found that 84% of students’ feelings of anxiousness about getting a job and /or the level of employability perceived by them has an impact on the performance of the students. But among 250 students 149 (59.6%) were found to have nil arrear in spite of they being anxious about getting a job. It can be inferred that, since students are more concerned about getting a job after their graduation, they might be more concentrating on their studies.
5. From Table-3, 6 & 7 it can be inferred that the percentage of marks or the learning effectiveness of the students is related to the additional time they spend on their studies (besides the college timing) and/ or spending time for studies at home. More, the students revisit what has been taught in the classroom, higher the retention and percentage of marks.
6. From Table- 8 & 9, it can be inferred that the level of feeling stressed about family being dependent on him / her influences the learning effectiveness or the performance of the students / number of arrears in the exams. But 178 (71.2%) of students who feel stressed about their family dependent on them were found to have no arrears. This might be due to the fact that, since their family and future is more dependent on their performance in the exams or how they excel in the exams, they might be focusing on their studies.

Conclusion

- Work-life balance / imbalance have an impact on the learning effectiveness of the students
- The feelings of anxiety of getting a job (i.e. perceived employability) affects their learning effectiveness / performance of the students and the time spent on leisure activities
- Family expectations / dependency have an impact on the learning effectiveness / performance of the students.

Thus, Work-life balance remains an issue that requires considerable attention from society. The changing nature of the global economy, where organizations expects the employees to operate on a 24/7 schedule and technological advances have made it possible for an employee to be connected at all times, has ushered the work-life balance issue into the forefront of the minds of many, including students. Although work-life balance may be viewed as a utopian dream, society must not fail to respond to the needs of individuals when dealing with complex issues arising from work and the rest of life, especially among individuals further along in their lives and careers.

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A PERCEPTION ON OCCUPATIONAL STRESS OF WOMEN TEACHERS IN ENGINEERING, ARTS AND SCIENCE & POLYTECHNIC COLLEGES

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Abstract

This study examined the perception of occupational stress of Women teachers in Engineering, Arts and Science & Polytechnic colleges. The intervening source of stress and its associated aspects are conferred. The perceived level of stress and its relationship with age and work time of women teachers of above mentioned institutions are discussed.

Keywords: occupational stress, Women teachers

Introduction

The **stress** related to one's Profession is known as occupational Stress. It is occurred due to unexpected responsibilities and strain happened in work place Occupational stress can increase when an employee felt that they are not supported by supervisors, colleagues and other from the work environment. In general, occupational stress is caused by a mismatch between perceived effort and perceived reward, or a sense of low control in a job with high demands. Low social support at work and job insecurity can also increase occupational stress. Psychosocial stressors are a major cause of occupational stress.

Review of literature

Smith et al. (1995) the author studied stress on faculty, they differentiated role-based stress which is resulting from unclear responsibilities and criteria for evaluating success, task based stress which is resulting from work overload and person or system-based stress which is resulting from high self-expectations and pressure to compete. They concluded that stress appears to play a negative role in university faculty work lives and that work overload is a major source of the stress experienced. Factors like discipline, rank and sex were significant in explaining task-based stress. Their result showed that associate professors and women report relatively higher levels of stress.

Moncrief et al. (1997) have examined the precursors and consequences of salesperson job stress. According to authors, there are a number of organizational variables including met expectations, role conflict, role ambiguity, job satisfaction, organization commitment and intention to leave which influence job stress.

Burke and Greenglass (1999) from this study they found that job stressors and work demands are the strongest predictors of work-to-family conflict. Role demands play an important role in aggravating WFC. Work role characteristics associated with work demands refer primarily to pressures arising from excessive workload and time pressures. Findings of that research showed that work demands such as number of hours worked, workload, and shift work were positively and strongly associated with WFC.

Lease (1999) examined the stress experienced by tenure-track faculty at some universities and found that satisfaction with salary, working hours, and perceived support of colleagues directly influence the level of stress and indirectly affects satisfaction.

Lois Bryson. Penny Warner-smith, Peter brown, Leanne fray (2007) High level stress for women especially are associated with the dual earner family in three way, his job, her job & family responsibilities, and the stress is associated with the job strain, time issue to balance the paid & unpaid work.

Wilkinson (2008) conducted a research. It was concluded that the consequences of an imbalance between work and personal or family life is emotional exhaustion, cynicism and burnout.

Kinman and Jones (2008) found that imbalance is one of the reasons of work stress among the employees. In their study, schedule flexibility and the autonomy of the employee in his work were found to be a key predictor of work- life balance reported that work related stress has increased in the educational sector. They reported heavy workload and resource and time limitations as the most nerve-racking aspects of academic work.

Santhanalakshmi.K and SanthoshKumar.N (2011) revealed working women in educational institution undergo severe stress. Continued work pressure results in poor performance. Women teachers in educational institution strive to balance between family members and their students. In this task they neglecting their health and mind which causes both family and educational institution will suffer. The result of this study indicates that the work life balance is challenge for lower level staff than higher level staff in the educational institutions. Educational institutions adopt a holistic approach to design and implement the policies to support the work life balance of teaching staffs.

Melanie Palmer, Dennis Rose, Methane Sanders, Fiona Randle (2012) this article study about the occupational related demand, family related demand work and family conflict and perception of parenting programmers, occupational task overload their children behaviour problem. This study find few occupational stress is significantly predicted conflict between work and family roles. Stress related to work overload an increased work hour. Occupational related demands predicted more experienced teachers have higher level of FWC. Family related demands correlate with children hyperactive and difficult behaviours and the no. of parents in the household. Stress reduction strategy may promote teachers well-being and reduce stress related to work overload child management strategies are generated into classroom context the teachers have a different reaction for particular action done by the children in the classrooms and their own children. By reducing workload the work family conflict may be managed better by the New Zealand teachers.

MadhusudhanGoud.V and Nagaraju.K (2013) the study indicated that majority of the faculty feeling stress due to dependents, role clarity, co-worker support, family culture, working hours, flexibility, head support. If the educational institutions management think over the issue of providing employee friendly policies to faculties in order to balance their professional and personal life, definitely it can achieve competitive advantage in terms of student quality of education and faculties may turn into good organization citizens.

Anil kumar.S, Hagargi (2013) this study pinpoints various problem related to working with BPO like, health problems, sleeping disorders, Digestive system related problem, Hearing ailments, cultural shift, personal habits, Discipline and behavioral and detachment from family. There are various reasons for this imbalance is pressure to cope up with family or work, speed of advancement of information technology and increasing competition in the talent supply market. The effect of imbalance affects the employees physically as well as psychologically, like heart ailments, cardio vascular problem sleep disorder, depression etc., time management prioritizing

task & planning are is some of the best solution which can help to reduce the imbalance of work life and personal life.

Victor - Devadoss A, J. Bafia Minnie (2013) carried out the study on work life stressor affect work harmony and work efficiency for every individual. The stressor is anything that causes the release of stress hormones. They are classified into physiological and psychological stressor which affects human body and mind. Non reachable supervisor results in poor performance & long working hour, and also left unreported to their supervisor for any reduction.

Objective and Limitation

The main aim of this study is determine the relationship of occupational stress on work life balance and the grounds for stress of women teachers in higher educational institution. The findings of the study is applicable only for the study period .Due to time constraint the entire population is not taken into consideration.

Research methodology

Descriptive research design is applied in this proposed study .secondary data is collected from journals, articles and web sources. Survey method is adopted to obtain primary data and Questionnaire is used to collect the information. Tiruvannamalai, Villupuram and Vellore Districts are the study area and women faculties of higher educational institutions in the above mentioned districts are sample unit of the study. The sample size chosen for this study is 500 and Stratified Random sampling technique is adopted for this study.

Data analysis and Discussions

Causes of Occupational Stress

Table Occupational Stress for Women Faculties

S.No.	Causes of Occupational Stress	Mean	SD	Status
1	Faculty attendance timing and late management	4.62	0.14	High Stress
2	Subject allotment based on likes and dislikes	4.14	0.12	Moderate Stress
3	Salary inequity	4.44	0.11	Moderate Stress
4	Pressure on result	4.68	0.13	High Stress
5	Promotional policies	4.12	0.10	Moderate Stress
6	Colleagues relationship	3.32	0.16	Low Stress
7	Management control on student behavior	3.96	0.11	Moderate Stress
8	Admission work	4.60	0.14	High Stress
9	Non-related works	3.18	0.16	Low Stress
10	Extend time of work	4.22	0.12	Moderate Stress

Source: Primary Data

The results show that the women teachers perceive that faculty attendance timing and late management, pressure on result and admission work are the sources of high stress, while, colleagues relationship and non-related works are the source of low stress. Meanwhile, subject allotment based on likes and dislikes, salary inequity, promotional policies, management control on student behavior and extend time of work are the sources for moderate stress.

Table Occupational Stress among the Women Teachers in Engineering, Arts and Science and Polytechnic Colleges -ANOVA

Source	SS	Degrees of Freedom	MS	F	Sig
Between Groups	7.028	2	3.514	6.593	0.00
Within Groups	264.926	497	.533		
Total	271.954	499			

Source: Primary Data

The F-value of 6.593 is significant at one per cent level indicating that there is a significant difference between level of occupational stress among the women teachers in Engineering, Arts and Science and Polytechnic Colleges. Hence, there is a significant difference between level of occupational stress among the women teachers in Engineering, Arts and Science and Polytechnic Colleges.

Relationship Between Age and Occupational Stress

Table Age of Women Teachers in Engineering, Arts and Science and Polytechnic Colleges and Occupational Stress-ANOVA

Source	SS	Degrees of Freedom	MS	F	Sig
Between Groups	17.524	5	3.505	6.702	0.00
Within Groups	258.178	494	.523		
Total	275.702	499			

Source: Primary Data

The F-value of 6.702 is significant at one per cent level indicating that there is a significant difference between age of women teachers in engineering, arts and science and polytechnic colleges and occupational stress. Hence, there is significant difference between age of women teachers in engineering, arts and science and polytechnic colleges and occupational stress.

Type of Work Time and Occupational Stress

Table Type of Work Time of Women Teachers in Engineering, Arts and Science and Polytechnic Colleges and Occupational Stress-ANOVA

Source	SS	Degrees of Freedom	MS	F	Sig
Between Groups	2.326	1	2.326	4.102	0.00
Within Groups	282.528	498	.567		
Total	284.854	499			

Source: Primary Data

The F-value of 4.102 is significant at one per cent level indicating that there is a significant difference between type of work time of women teachers in engineering, arts and science and polytechnic colleges and occupational stress. Hence, there is a significant difference between type of work time of women teachers in engineering, arts and science and polytechnic colleges and occupational stress.

Conclusion

The result of the study indicates that the perception of stress is differing for women teachers. They perceive high stress on faculty attendance timing and late management, pressure on result

and admission work. The perception of stress is low in case of colleague's relationship and non-related works and they perceived moderate stress on subject allotment based on likes and dislikes, salary inequity, promotional policies, management control on student behavior and extend time of work. There is a significant difference between occupational stress and age in addition to that there is a significant difference between occupational stress and work time of women teachers in Engineering, Arts and Science & Polytechnic Colleges .

Scope for future research

This study has examined the perception of occupational stress and its association with certain intervening variables. The future studies may focus on various strategies to overcome occupational stress and its related issued.

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A STUDY ON 360 DEGREE PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL SYSTEM AND ITS EFFECT ON THE EMPLOYEES IN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY, TAMIL NADU, INDIA

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Abstract

The 360-degree feedback is intended to provide employees with as accurate a view of their performance as possible by getting input from all angles. It is said to be useful because it allows managers to identify and compare their strengths and weakness as identified by key constituents from different organizational levels which include supervisors, peers or colleagues, subordinates or direct reports and internal and/or external customers. The main purpose of the study is To facilitate fair and equitable compensation based on performance. The main objective of the study is to study the employee's performance measurement using 3600 degree performance appraisal system among the employees of effect on the employees in Pharmaceutical industry, Tamilnadu, Methodology The research has used various methods to collect the primary data like Observation method, Interview method, Questionnaire method, A sample of 120 employees has been selected Primary data are measured observed and recorded as a part of an original study For data gathering, we chose questionnaire by 5 choices Likert scale with 40 questions, we analyzed the data by the method of chi square to compare the means Findings: The findings depicted the dominance of recognizing the 360 degree performance appraisal system in selected Pharmaceutical industry conclusion: Evaluation is a continuous process an appraising the employees is not only to review his performance but also help him to develop himself, Transparency into the system should be ensured through the discussion about the employee's performance

Keywords: *360-degree, performance appraisal, feedback, employees*

Introduction

The current process of 360 performance appraisal system is much more open and gives some scope for self-appraisal by the employee. The self-appraisal is followed by a joint discussion with superior and then a decision is taken by the department head on his promotion, pay hike etc. The feedback relating to his performance is directly given to the employee.

The basis of organizational capacity lies with the capacity of each employee, of each manager that handles the smallest unit in an organization. How they respond to adversity is the basis of consistently creating outstanding results. In this fast growing world where they are exposed to, each day demands greater speed, capacity and capabilities. And because managers assume multifaceted tasks, it is inevitable for them to encounter hard times along with exposure to different people of different organizational levels in the company. Their performance can be affected by many factors that surround them including people. In turn they also affect several employees above or below the organizational structure or even those in the same level with them. So, it is important to use a multi-source assessment or 360-degree feedback process to determine the level of performance of a middle manager. The 360-degree feedback is intended to provide employees with as accurate a view of their performance as possible by getting input from all angles.

Statement of the Problems

If the 360 degree performance appraisal system is not rightly done it may lead to poor industrial relations, lack of complete integration between employees and the company, lack of commitment and lack of jobs satisfaction in this context, an attempt has been made to make an in depth study of 360 degree performance appraisal system and its effect on the employees of effect on the employees in Pharmaceutical industry, Tamilnadu.

Objective of the study

Primary objective

To study the employee's performance measurement using 360⁰ degree performance appraisal system among the employees of effect on the employees in Pharmaceutical industry, Tamilnadu,

Secondary objective

- To evaluate 360 degree feedback on how other perceive on employee.
- To recommend the management for persistence performance appraisal system.

Research Methodology

Sample Design

Sample design is also a critical component of marketing research and employee research for many organizations. Probability Sampling is a method of sampling that enables the researcher to specify for each case in the population the probability of its inclusion in the sample.

Sample Method

The sample has to include employees from all levels. Stratified random sampling technique was selected while preparing questionnaire as this was the only technique that helped to draw conclusions accurately.

Sample size

A sample of 120 employees has been selected in Race Pharmaceuticals, Tamilnadu, India. Although it looks to be a small sample keeping in view the large number of employees it has to be limited because of time constraint (4 weeks).

Method of data collection

Collection of data

Primary data are measured observed and recorded as a part of an original study. secondary data can be obtained from journals, reports, records, government publications of research organizations, trade and professional bodies etc.

Statistical Design

Chi - Square test

The chi-square is computed on the basis of frequencies in a sample and thus the value of chi-square so obtained is a statistic.

Research Hypothesis (H₀)

H₀- there is no significant relationship between Demographic factor and Self-evaluation factor.

H₀- there is no significant relationship between Demographic factor and Peers factor.

H₀- there is no significant relationship between Demographic factor and Supervisor factor.

H₀- there is no significant relationship between Demographic factor and Subordinate factor.

H₀- there is no significant relationship between Demographic factor and Customer/client relation factor.

Limitations of the Study

During the course research work the researcher encountered with some of the limitations, which to some extent curtailed the freedom in exploring fully fledged response from the respondents.

1. The company did not allow asking some important question which is many create problems. They Examined research's questionnaire before distribution and also they restricted some.
2. The company has restricted to ask questions to the employee but they allow limited questions about the relationship with company to the employees.
3. The company allowed limited time so the researcher to visit the factory so, the researcher could not able to study the full atmosphere.
4. The researcher had limited time so the researcher used random sampling technique and used limited statically tools.
5. Because of the questionnaire method most of the employees have choose true value.

Review of Literature

Stark, Kornstein & Karani (2008) highlighted on the degree of effect 360 degree feedback has on the comfort level of faculty and their skills. It was found that 360 degree feedback provides best results when it is used for training purpose. The limitation of the study was they were not able to figure out the differences in attitudes. Now- a-days MNCs are investing more resources and attention towards the cultural training for improving the performance of their international assignees and using 360 degree feedback as a tool to monitor the effectiveness of that training.

Drew (2009) highlighted on individual leadership development by using 360 degree feedback. The author analyzed that 360 degree feedback has favourable influence in different universities as well as also in knowledge based entities in the aspect of leadership. Here "People engagement" was thoroughly checked by gaining well defined feedback. 360 degree feedback is considered as an adding value to individuals where in individuals looks into their self and work on it for their own development there by meeting the organization's objective.

Robertson (2010) highlighted on the impact of gender differences on seniority level by using 360 degree assessments which has a behavioural impact on influencing, leadership and team behaviours. The author suggested that in every organization the employees should be well familiar with the influential factors of change process as well with the hierarchical systems of authority. The study also imparted on development of leadership system in an organization to make well conversant with the change in different level of positions both from the aspect of male and female which ultimately lead to growth in organizational performance.

Samaduzzaman (2013) discussed that 360 degree feedback is an effective performance evaluation method to measure the efficiency of a person. The feedback helps in removing the misconceptions or wrong perceptions where in the author failed to focus on the type of the organizations where 360 degree feedback has been used and has made an impact. There are three basic considerations to be made in 360 degree feedback i.e. who should be rated and by whom and the rating scales to be used.

Concept of the Study

Definition

A 360-degree performance appraisal is an employee evaluation tool that includes feedback from a supervisor, subordinates, colleagues and customers. The purpose is to create a broader view of the employee's performance based on the impact of relationships with key stakeholders.

An employee evaluation can consist of a technique called *360-degree feedback*, which involves gathering performance-based feedback from a dozen or so anonymous raters in the workplace – all of whom have had work-related dealings with the employees being evaluated. These raters could include peers, subordinates, and additional members of management, customers, and vendors. You can learn a great deal about the performance, productivity, and overall effectiveness of your employees by using the 360-degree feedback technique. - By Ken Lloyd

The Purpose of the Study

The feedback is often used as a benchmark within the employee's development plan. In a team-focused atmosphere, 360 degree feedback surveys can be very effective.

- To help the superiors to have proper understanding about their subordinates.
- To facilitate fair and equitable compensation based on performance.
- To facilitate for testing and validating selection tests, interview techniques through comparing their scores with performance appraisal

Findings for chi-square Test

In Self-evaluation factor Compared with gender, Three variables null hypothesis was accepted (Interaction with employee, Ensure error free work, adapt change) and Two variables Null hypothesis was rejected (set standard for work factor, Team expectation).

In Peers factor Compared with gender, Three variables null hypothesis was accepted (Team roles maximize output, Easy to work with team, Share information) and two variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Team support, Attitude of peers).

In Supervisor factor Compared with gender, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Good listening, Discuss with superior, Dealing staff, Decision on promotion) and one variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Supervisor relation).

In Subordinate factor Compared with gender, Five variables null hypothesis was accepted (Recognition, Support/Encouragement, Direction on new project, Feel fear, Mutual respect).

In Customer/Client factor Compared with gender, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Learning customer, Quality factor, Customer service, Useful of technology with client) and one variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Time of delivery).

In Self-evaluation factor Compared with Marital status, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Ensure error free work, Set standard for work factor, Team expectation, Adapt change) and one variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Interaction with employee).

In Peers factor Compared with Marital status, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Team roles maximize output, Easy to work with team, Share information, Attitude of peers) and one variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Team support).

In Supervisor factor Compared with Marital status, Five variables null hypothesis was accepted (Good listening, Discuss with superior, Dealing staff, Supervisor relation, Decision on promotion).

In Subordinate factor Compared with Marital status, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Recognition, Support/Encouragement, Direction on new project, Mutual respect) and One variable null hypothesis was rejected (Feel fear).

In Customer/Client factor Compared with Marital status, Five variables null hypothesis was accepted (Learning customer, Quality factor, Customer service, Useful of technology with client, Time of delivery).

In Self-evaluation factor Compared with Age, Two variables null hypothesis was accepted (Set standard for work factor, Adapt change) and Three variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Interaction with employee, Ensure error free work, Team expectation).

In Peers factor Compared with Age, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Team roles maximize output, Team support, Share information, Attitude of peers) and One variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Easy to work with team).

In Supervisor factor Compared with Age, Two variables null hypothesis was accepted (Dealing staff, Supervisor relation) and Three variables null hypothesis was rejected (Good listening, Discuss with superior, Decision on promotion).

In Subordinate factor Compared with Age, Five variables null hypothesis was accepted (Recognition, Support/Encouragement, Direction on new project, Feel fear, Mutual respect).

In Customer/Client factor Compared with Age, Three variables null hypothesis was accepted (Learning customer, Quality factor, Customer service) and two variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Useful of technology with client, Time of delivery).

In Self-evaluation factor Compared with Qualification, Three variables null hypothesis was accepted (set standard for work, Team expectation, adapt change) and two variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Interaction with employee, Ensure error free work).

In Peers factor Compared with Qualification, Five variables null hypothesis was accepted (Team roles maximize output, Team support, Easy to work with team, Share information, Attitude of peers).

In Supervisor factor Compared with Qualification, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Good listening, Dealing staff, Supervisor relation, Decision on promotion) and One variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Discuss with superior).

In Subordinate factor Compared with Qualification, Five variables null hypothesis was accepted (Recognition, Support/Encouragement, Direction on new project, Feel fear, Mutual respect).

In Customer/Client factor Compared with Qualification, Three variables null hypothesis was accepted (Learning customer, Quality factor, Customer service) and Two variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Useful of technology with client, Time of delivery).

In Self-evaluation factor Compared with Experience, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Interaction with employee, Ensure error free work, Set standard for work factor, Team expectation, Adapt change) and one variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Interaction with employee).

In Peers factor Compared with Experience, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Team roles maximize output, Team support, Share information, Easy to work with team) and One variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Attitude of peers).

In Supervisor factor Compared with Experience, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Good listening, Dealing staff, Supervisor relation, Decision on promotion) and One variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Discuss with superior).

In Subordinate factor Compared with Experience, Three variables null hypothesis was accepted (Support/Encouragement, Direction on new project, Mutual respect) and Two variable null hypothesis was rejected (Recognition, Feel fear).

In Customer/Client factor Compared with Experience, Four variables null hypothesis was accepted (Learning customer, Quality factor, Customer service, Time of delivery) and One variables Null hypothesis was rejected (Useful of technology with client).

Suggestions

From the fore going analysis and findings it is clear that,

- To develop the performance of the employees, the organisation has to adopt new method of work environment for team members.
- In self-evaluation, The employees are have different opinion and they are expecting some salary, promotion based on recognition and implement guidelines are generates performance of employees work.
- Teams are important for success at the same time the relationship of superior and subordinates have to better than the present scenario.
- More training program can be conducts to bring the desirable change and improve better performance in new project.
- The organization structure has to be more flexible to have better human relation so as easy to understand the employee mind-set.

Conclusion

Evaluation is a continuous process an appraising the employees is not only to review his performance but also help him to develop himself, Transparency into the system should be ensured through the discussion about the employee's performance with the employee concerned and try to find out the grey areas so that training can be implemented to improve on that. The better human relations are required which most incorporates both the work performance as well as resolve personal attributes.

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HUMAN RESOURCE ACCOUNTING - AN APPRAISAL

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Abstract

To ensure growth and development of any organization, the efficiency of people must be augmented in the right perspective. Without human resources, the other resources cannot be operationally effective. The original health of the organization is indicated by the human behaviour variables, like group loyalty, skill, motivation and capacity for effective interaction, communication and decision making. Human Resource Accounting is an accounting for people as the organizational resources. It is the process of identifying and measuring data about human resources and communicating this information to the interested parties. It is the measurement of the cost and value of people to the organization. This paper summarizes the development of the concept of human resource accounting, importance of human resource accounting, valuation of human resources and the limitations of the human resource accounting.

Introduction

Human resource is an important asset in the organization whose value goes on increasing with its right placement, application and development in the organization. In spite of vast physical resources with latest technology, an organization may quite often find itself in financial crisis if it does not have the right persons to manage its affairs. Thus, human resources is a very valuable asset for the organization which aims to progress in all directions amidst heavy competition.

The success or otherwise of an organization depends on how best the scarce physical resources are utilized by the human resource. What is important here is that the physical resources are being activated by the human resources as the physical resources cannot act on their own. Therefore, the efficient and effective utilization of inanimate resources depends largely on the quality, caliber, skills, perception and character of the people, that is, the human resources working in it. The term Human resource at macro level indicates the sum of all the components such as skills, creative abilities, innovative thinking, intuition, imagination, knowledge and experience possessed by all the people. An organization possessed with abundant physical resources may sometimes miserably fail unless it has right people, human resources, to manage its affairs. Thus, the importance of human resources cannot be ignored. Unfortunately, till now generally accepted system of accounting this important asset, viz., the human resources have not been evolved. Human Resource Accounting is an accounting for people as the organizational resources. It is the process of identifying and measuring data about human resources and communicating this information to the interested parties. It is the measurement of the cost and value of people to the organization.

Development of the concept of human resource Accounting

Human Resource Accounting is the offshoot of various research studies conducted in the areas of accounting and finance. Human resource is an asset whose value gets appreciated over the period of time provided placed, applied and developed in the right direction. Till the recent past, organizations took few efforts to assign monetary value to human resource in its accounting

practice. Behavioral scientists-initiated efforts to develop appropriate methodology for finding out the value of human resource to the organization. They were against the conventional accounting practice for its failure to value the human resource of an organization along with physical resources.

The traditional concept suggested that expenditure on human resource is treated as a charge against revenue as it does not create any physical asset. At present there is a change in this concept and the expenses incurred on any asset (as human resources) should be treated as capital expenditure as it yields benefits which can be derived for a long period of time and could be measured in monetary terms.

The productivity of a company's investment is known from the rate of return it gives. So far, these rates of productiveness considered in respect of Physical assets only. To find out the productivity of investment on human beings in any organization human resource accounting emerged as a supporting tool. The Human Resource Accounting is a scating tool that generates and reports quantitative control information about the contribution of human resource for promontory industrial productivity.

Features of human resource accounting

- It is a system of accounting in which identification of human resources is made.
- All categories of people employed in the organization from top management to bottom are include in human resources.
- Investments made in human resources are recorded.
- Measurement of cost and value of human resources made.
- Record is also maintained for the changes occurring in human resources over a period of time.
- Information generated about human resources is communicated through financial statements to the interested parties.

Objectives of human resource accounting

- Human Resource Accounting helps in determining the return on investment on human resources.
- Human being cannot be owned like other physical assets. They, therefore, cannot command any value.
- It helps in knowing whether the human resources have been properly utilized or not.
- It provides quantitative information on human resources which will help the managers as well as investors in making decisions.
- To communicate the worth of human resources to the organization and the society at large.
- There is no generally accepted model for valuation of human resources. The mode of presentation has also yet to be codified.

Importance of human resource accounting

Improvement in Internal Management Decisions: Human Resource Accounting helps in making internal management decisions better. For instance, the transfer of an employee from one department to another or promotion of an employee to higher position.

Motivation of Employees for Production Purposes: Human Resource Accounting helps in finding the time cost of human asset. If hourly time cost of this asset is brought the knowledge of

various classes of employees, it is hoped that they may devote there every second for productive purpose only.

Improvement in Decision-Making Process: If human resource data are included in financial reporting, the management gets information about the value of human resources and this information given by human resource accounting improves the decision-making process.

Impact on Investor's Decisions: Human Resource Accounting helps in finding out rate of return on investment. Though rate of return on investment can be found out under traditional system of accounting also but this rate under human resource accounting is better than the rate of traditional accounting system all expenses on human resources are treated as revenue while under human resource accounting some of these expenses are treated as revenue and others as deferred revenue and these are written off over a certain period of time.

Valuation of human resources

Methods based on cost

Historical Cost Method

Historical method relies primarily on accounting techniques which have been in common use for many years. It is easy to develop and operate these systems. Management also has little difficulty in interpreting the meaning and the information supplied by cost-based systems since the underlying concepts are consistent with those of the conventional accounting data. It simply involves an extension of the concept of proper matching of costs with revenue. Historical cost of human resources is treated very much like the cost of fixed assets. The same principles of capitalization and amortization are applied.

Replacement Cost Method

Replacement Cost Method incorporates the current value of the company's human resources. It takes into account the fluctuations of the job market and the general rise in price level. Replacement costs have the advantage of being present oriented. The cost of replacing employees is used as the measure of company's human resources.

Opportunity Cost Method

Opportunity Cost method is which determines the value of human resource on the basis of an employee's value in alternative uses. Accordingly, the value of an employee is based on his opportunity cost the price other divisions are willing to pay for the service of an employee is based on his opportunity cost the price other divisions are willing to pay for the service of an employee working in another division of an organization.

Methods based on value

Economic Value Added

The value of an object is the present value of the services that it is expected to render in future. Similarly, the economic value of human resources is the present worth of the services that they are likely to render in future. This may be value of individuals, groups or the total human organization.

Hermanson's Adjusted Discounted Future Earnings Model

Hermanson (1964) proposed this method in this pioneering work at Michigan State University (USA). Hermanson suggested the discounting of wage payments to people as a measure of a

person's value to an organization. However, he suggests the adjustment of his discounted future wage stream by an efficiency factor.

Lev and Schwartz Present Value of Future Earnings Model

This Model is also as the Compensation Model. Given the uncertainty and the difficulty associated with determination of the value of human capital, Baruch Lev and Aba Schwartz suggested the use of an individual employee's future compensation as a surrogate of his value.

Limitations of human resource accounting

Non-Availability of Standard

Certain standards are needed to measure the human resources. At present adequate standards are not available for such measure.

Variety of Methods

For valuation of human resources there are various methods, hence they create confusion so far as adoption of a particular model is concerned.

Expenditure on Human Resource Accounting

When Human Resource Accounting is adopted, it is certain that additional expenditure will be incurred on it and this additional expenditure will reduce the profit if it does not help in increasing the profit to the same extent. It is desirable to assess the cost-benefit ratio of introduction of human resource accounting.

Lack of perfect knowledge about future earnings of human resource

No perfect knowledge about future earnings of human resource can be made during these days when world as a whole is full of uncertainties. Valuation of human resource based on this uncertain event not is of great use.

Design of hr accounting process for each of the hr sub-system

There is much debate as to whether the human resources of an organization can be considered as an asset and treated accordingly in the accounting system. There are two schools of thought. One says that human resource is an asset and the other does not agree with this. Asset is anything which is owned by the entity to derive service in future and should have legally enforceable claim. As such there is no guarantee of deriving benefits from the existing human resources in future and has no sales value like other assets. Therefore, legally, human resource is not an asset claims one school of thought. Besides, company law also does not consider it as an asset. But the other school is of the opinion that the human resource is an asset. This school of thought puts forth two contentions in favor of its opinion as follows:

- There is a legal ownership on the human resource which could in practice prevent him from joining the other organizations unless properly relieved by complying with some formalities like giving advance notice of resignation etc.
- Uncertainty of deriving benefits is a common problem to all assets, not only with the human resources. Deriving future benefit may be a big question mark in other assets too due to many factors.

- An asset needs maintenance and development support from the organization so as to derive benefits over a long period of time. Similarly, human resources as an asset also is in need of training and development in order to maintain the service potential for the employer.

Conclusion

Human Resource Accounting is an era of globalization and cost cuts, therefore, Human Resource Accounting would give an organization a correct vision towards the way forward. Due to the increasing importance of manpower role in the development and promotion and achievement of organization goals, management requires a comprehensive system for determining the value of services provided by manpower. Because acquiring precise and accurate information about human resources expenses and the effectiveness rate of these expenses can play an important role in attracting resources and development and improvement of organizations. It is an attempt to identify and quantify the investments made in human resource of an organization. Human Resource Accounting helps to measure the value of employees, which helps management in decision making.

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ECONOMIC REFORMS AND AGRICULTURAL GROWTH IN INDIA

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Abstract

Agriculture plays a vital role in Indian economy. The rapid growth of agriculture is important for inclusiveness. Agriculture in India has undergone rapid transformation in the past two decades. The policies of globalization and liberalization have opened up new avenues for agricultural modernization. Due to its importance in national output and employment, agriculture was given special attention by Indian policy makers and development planners, which helped this sector to play an important role in economic development and improving living standard of vast population through increasing income. This study is in descriptive method and it used the exploratory technique. The data for the study were collected from the secondary sources. Non-price factors such as capital formation in agriculture (with an important role for irrigation), rural credit, and research and extension services were not given adequate importance in the post-reform period. The increase in the credit-deposit ratio, as well as the share of priority sector and agriculture in total outstanding credit since 2001 were largely due to definitional changes benefiting large agri-business corporations and large cultivators. Expectations regarding improvements in terms of trade for agriculture did not materialise after the reforms. Besides, agricultural trade liberalisation has exposed domestic producers to the volatilities of international prices of agricultural commodities that have turned agriculture into an unviable occupation.

The inevitable never happens. It's the unexpected always.

-John Maynard Keynes

Agriculture is not crop production as popular belief holds - it's the production of food and fibre from the world's land and waters. Without agriculture it is not possible to have a city, stock market, banks, university, church or army. Agriculture is the foundation of civilization and any stable economy.

- Allan Savory

Introduction

Agriculture plays a vital role in Indian economy. The rapid growth of agriculture is important for inclusiveness. Agriculture in India has undergone rapid transformation in the past two decades. The policies of globalization and liberalization have opened up new avenues for agricultural modernization. Due to its importance in national output and employment, agriculture was given special attention by Indian policy makers and development planners, which helped this sector to play an important role in economic development and improving living standard of vast population through increasing income. However, several challenges have surfaced are becoming more and more severe with the passage of time during last one and a half decade. The growth rate has turned lower than the growth in population dependent on agriculture implying the per capita income in agriculture is falling. Economic liberalisation entails a set of measures that are unfavorable to petty production in general, and agriculture in particular. In that sense, these policies have a distinct class bias against petty producers and the poor. These policies resulted in a reduction of public investment in rural infrastructure, including irrigation, agricultural research

and extension services and a decline in the supply of rural credit to small and poor cultivators, and the pursuit of agricultural trade liberalisation.

Objective

Objective of the present study is to study the impact of economic reforms in agricultural growth in India.

Methodology of the Study

This study is in descriptive method and it used the exploratory technique. The data for the study were collected from the secondary sources such as reports, journals, articles published online and offline on various newspapers and websites. This has been published and focused on various aspects of agricultural growth.

Growth Rate of Agriculture

High growth of the agricultural sector is crucial for overall development of economy. In India, its importance is heightened with a substantial section of the population dependent on agriculture for employment. As per the National Sample Survey Office (NSSO), about 59 per cent of male workers and 75 per cent of women workers were dependent on agriculture in 2011-12 (NSSO 2014). High agricultural growth is important to reduce rural poverty. It was argued that doubling of the rate of agricultural growth from 2 per cent to 4 per cent along with 9 per cent rate of growth of the economy will reduce income disparities between the agricultural and non-agricultural sectors (Planning Commission, 2006). In this context, it will be worthwhile to analyse growth rates of the agricultural sector, and evaluate its performance in the context of the overall economy, after the initiation of the reforms in 1991-92.

Table 1 Growth Rate of GDP of Agriculture Sector and GDP of the Economy, 1981-82 to 2013-14

Periods	(in per cent)	
	Growth Rate of Agriculture	GDP Growth Rate
1981-82 to 1989-90	2.9	4.7
1990-91 to 1999-00	2.8	5.3
2000-01 to 2009-10	2.4	6.8
2010-11 to 2013-14	2.1	3.7

Source: Handbook of Statistics, Reserve Bank of India, Various years.

The growth rate of gross domestic product (GDP) of agriculture has declined since the initiation of economic reforms in India. However, during this period, growth rates of GDP have been increasing except for two years between 2010-11 and 2013-14. The table shows an increasing divergence between growth rates of GDP of agriculture and economy between 1990-91 and 2009-10 (Table 1), thereby indicating the declining importance of agriculture in the growth trajectory of India. Declining contribution of agriculture is also reflected in terms of a steady decline in the share of agriculture in overall GDP.

Table 2 Growth of Area, Production and Yield of Major Crops, 1981-82 to 2014-15
(In percentage)

Crops	1981-82 to 1989-90			1990-91 to 1999-2000			2000-01 to 2009-2010			2010-11 to 2014-15		
	Area	Production	Yield	Area	Production	Yield	Area	Production	Yield	Area	Production	Yield
Foodgrains	-0.2	2.8	3.02	-0.37	1.75	2.13	0.02	1.03	1.01	-0.75	0.66	1.4
Rice	0.39	3.66	3.25	0.56	1.9	1.33	-0.64	0.47	1.12	0.46	1.77	1.31
Wheat	0.66	3.23	2.55	1.3	3.31	1.99	1.01	1.49	0.47	1.27	0.47	-0.7
Coarse cereals	-1.31	1.25	2.58	-2.1	-0.75	1.4	-0.88	0.77	1.67	-3.15	-0.77	2.46
Total cereals	-0.2	2.95	3.15	-0.12	1.94	2.05	-0.26	0.9	1.19	-0.26	0.8	1.07
Pulses	-0.2	1.24	1.43	-1.53	-0.6	0.94	1.35	2.85	1.47	-2.63	-0.12	1.5
Oilseeds	2.1	3.81	1.67	0.05	1.07	1.02	1.32	3.04	1.69	-1.12	-3.85	-2.76
Ground nut	1.78	1.29	-0.49	-1.88	-3.51	-1.64	-1.78	-1.6	0.14	-4.35	-4.5	-0.16
Rapeseed and Mustard	1.36	6.31	4.9	0.42	1	0.6	2.24	4.66	2.38	-3.45	-5.06	-1.67
Soyabean	18.73	20	0.87	9.28	10.54	1.15	4.25	6.55	2.22	2.93	-3.73	-6.47
Cotton	-0.52	4.2	4.75	1.59	1.6	0	1.73	9.7	7.8	3.07	1.46	-1.6
Sugarcane	0.84	2.14	1.31	1.35	2.19	0.82	-0.33	-0.12	0.2	1.04	0.97	-0.06

Source: Handbook of Statistics, Reserve Bank of India, Various years.

The growth rates of production and yield of most of the major crops have declined in the years following the initiation of economic reforms as compared to the 1980s. Exceptions to this general trend were observed for pulses and cotton (2000-01 to 2009-10) for which growth rates of production and yield have increased, and sugar cane and wheat (1990-91 to 1999-2000) whose production increased marginally as compared to the 1980s. Growth in production of foodgrains between 1981-82 and 2014-15 was largely due to the growth rate of the yield. In the period under study, highest growth rates in the yield of foodgrains were in the 1980s, the second phase of green revolution. Since the 1990s, growth in production of foodgrains was mainly driven by rice and wheat. The increase in growth rate of production of wheat, more pronounced since 2000-01, was largely due to expansion in area under cultivation. The decline in area under coarse cereals in all the sub-periods between 1981-82 and 2014-15, has been sharper with the onset of reforms (Table 2). It can be argued that increase in the acreage under wheat and rice cultivation has taken place at the expense of coarse cereals. The decline in area under cultivation of coarse cereals did not translate into a steep decline in production due to growth registered in yield rate in all the sub-periods. According to Dev and Pandey (2013: 82), growth in yield rate of coarse cereals can largely be attributed to adoption of the new seed technology.

There was a sharp rise in the production of oilseeds in the late 1980s and early 1990s due to quantitative restrictions on imports and technological modernisation programme of the government as part of Technological Mission on Oilseeds. Due to an increase in imports as part of trade liberalisation measures, there was a sharp decline in the area under cultivation and production of oilseeds. This can be seen from Table 3 where expansion in area under cultivation and growth rate of output of oilseeds had declined drastically in the 1990s as compared to the preceding decade. With the reintroduction of import duties on imports of oilseeds in 2001, and

more favourable prices in the domestic market, there was an increase in the area and production, post 2000 (Ramachandran 2011).

Import duty on crude edible oil was eliminated in 2010-11, from a high of 75per cent in 2004. This adversely affected domestic oilseed producers. Table 3 shows the decline in area, production and yield of different varieties of oilseeds between 2010-11 and 2014-15 (Sharma 2013). Of all the major crops studied in Table 3, cotton has registered the highest rate of growth in the post-reform period, specifically between 2000-01 and 2009-10. Trends in cotton production show that increases in yield were the main factors for growth of output in the 1980s and in the 2000s; increases in area under cultivation were mainly responsible for the growth of output in other periods. Sharp increases in the yield rate between 2000-01 and 2009-10 were due to the adoption of Bt cotton technology in cotton growing areas in India. However, growth of yield rate and production of cotton declined between 2010-11 and 2014-15. It was argued that the high costs and risks associated with Bt cotton technology, particularly for subsistence farmers in low yield areas made cotton cultivation unviable. Also, increased use of pesticides even with the adoption of Bt cotton meant that pests (like bollworm) that were not major threats in Indian varieties of cotton started to have an adverse impact on the yield rate of cotton (Gutierrez et al 2015).

Non-price Factors Affecting Agricultural Growth

Capital formation in agriculture: Capital formation is necessary for improving long-term growth potential in agriculture. The share of agriculture and allied activities in gross capital formation in the economy was increasing in the mid-1960s, and this trend continued till the late 1970s. Higher growth rates of agriculture witnessed in the 1980s were due to the lagged impact of increases in the share of agriculture and allied sector in gross capital formation during the late 1960s and 1970s (Tables 1 and 2). However, since the 1980s, the share has shown a declining trend. There was a mild recovery during the late 1990s till 2001-02, and then the share declined again. The declining trend since the 1990s implies that there has been lesser investment in agriculture as compared to the non-agriculture sector.

Chand and Kumar (2004) argued that public capital formation has a long-term beneficial impact on agriculture as compared to subsidies whose impact is short-term. They estimated that a rupee spent on public sector capital formation contributes to GDP growth in agriculture by Rs.35.21 over a period of 58 years. They contended that diverting one per cent of resources from subsidies to public investment raises output by more than two per cent and is highly desirable in ensuring growth of agriculture GDP (2004: 5611-16). The trend of aggregate capital formation in agriculture since 1981-82 is shown in Table 4.

Table 3 Capital Formations in Agriculture, 1981-82 to 2013-14
(Rs.Crore, 1999-2000 Prices)

Year	Public Investment	Percentage	Private Investment	Percentage	Total
1981-82	12,723	52.42	11,549	47.58	24,272
1982-83	12,665	48.47	13,467	51.53	26,132
1983-84	12,962	46.66	14,816	53.34	27,778
1984-85	12,488	49.12	12,938	50.88	25,426
1985-86	11,248	46.46	12,960	53.54	24,208

1986-87	10,667	44.97	13,051	55.03	23,718
1987-88	10,981	38.13	17,816	61.87	28,797
1988-89	10,302	39.83	15,564	60.17	25,866
1989-90	8,909	34.21	17,132	65.79	26,041
1990-91	8,938	23.49	29,116	76.51	38,054
1991-92	7,901	32.20	16,634	67.80	24,535
1992-93	8,167	26.32	22,862	73.68	31,029
1993-94	8,907	31.66	19,230	68.34	28,137
1994-95	9,706	36.10	17,183	63.90	26,889
1995-96	9,560	34.97	17,777	65.03	27,337
1996-97	9,225	30.94	20,589	69.06	29,814
1997-98	7,812	24.03	24,692	75.97	32,504
1998-99	7,949	24.16	24,956	75.84	32,905
1999-00	41,483	45.27	50,151	54.73	91,634
2000-01	8,085	17.78	37,395	82.22	45,480
2001-02	9,712	17.05	47,266	82.95	56,978
2002-03	8,734	15.69	46,934	84.31	55,668
2003-04	10,805	20.18	42,737	79.82	53,542
2004-05	16,187	29.70	38,309	70.30	54,496
2005-06	19,940	31.87	42,629	68.13	62,569
2006-07	22,987	34.23	44,167	65.77	67,154
2007-08	23,257	30.60	52,745	69.40	76,002
2008-09	20,572	23.19	68,137	76.81	88,709
2009-10	22,693	24.31	70,640	75.69	93,333
2010-11	19,854	21.57	72,181	78.43	92,035
2011-12	21,184	19.59	86,958	80.41	108,142
2012-13	23,886	21.28	88,371	78.72	112,257
2013-14	23,191	24.25	72,446	75.75	95,637

Source: Planning Commission of India and Agricultural Statistics at a Glance (2014).

Table 4 shows that aggregate capital formation remained stagnant in the 1980s. Private and public capital formations moved in divergent directions. Decline in public capital formation continued well into the 1990s, and it was only in 2004-05 that public investment exceeded the levels attained in 1981-82. Private investment was increasing at a faster rate than public investment in the 1990s, and it was instrumental in raising total investment during this decade. Private and public investments had registered increases from 2004-05 to 2012-13, though the former increased at a faster rate than the latter. While public investment doubled, there was almost an eightfold increase in private investment over the three decades between 1981-82 and 2012-13. The share of public capital formation in total capital formation in agriculture had gone down from 52per cent in 1981-82 to 21per cent in 2012-13.

Table 4 Productivity of Irrigation for Food grains in Indian Agriculture

(growth rates in %)

Year	1981-82 to 1989-90	1990-91 to 1999-00	2000-01 to 2009-10	2010-11 to 2012-13
Growth rate of gross irrigated area	2.07	2.28	1.11	1.36
Growth rate of output of food grains	2.8	1.75	1.03	0.66
Productivity of irrigation	0.73	-0.53	-0.08	-0.7

Source: Handbook of Statistics, Reserve Bank of India, Various years.

The agricultural sector will have a long-term adverse impact on growth rates with declining importance of public capital formation (Chand and Kumar 2004). There is a difference in the nature of public and private capital formation and contribution in the production processes, in which the former is mainly in the nature of public goods such as irrigation projects and road networks. These will not be provided by private capital. Thus, in terms of contribution to the production process, decline in public capital formation till 2004-05, is not adequately compensated by an increase in private investment in agriculture (Balakrishnan et al 2008).

In India, irrigation accounts for 90 per cent of gross capital formation in agriculture. Table 5 shows productivity of irrigation for foodgrains in Indian agriculture. It was argued that increase in the irrigated area under foodgrains was largely responsible for increase in foodgrains output, and hence growth of foodgrains output with respect to growth of irrigation is a good measure of changes in the productivity of irrigation water (Rao, 2002).

Table 5 shows that productivity of irrigation was highest in the 1980s. It was a period when green revolution was broadbased, with the inclusion of rice growing regions in eastern India. Growth rate of irrigated area increased marginally in the 1990s as compared to the 1980s; growth rate of output of foodgrains declined during this period. Decline in productivity of irrigation in the 1990s was due to a loss of momentum in the development of yield-increasing technologies such as cultivation of drought-resistant crops. This loss of momentum is directly related to the decline in public expenditure on research. Also, the political economy of irrigation from groundwater sources had a significant role in reducing productivity of irrigation in the 1990s. As Rao noted that, "there was a sharp decline in agricultural growth in east UP on account of severe cuts in the supply of power for pumping water, which was diverted to west UP to satisfy the powerful farm lobby" (2002: 1743). From 2000-01, growth rates of gross irrigated area and output declined sharply as compared to the preceding decades. Although, the fact that assured supply of water is crucial for high agricultural growth is acknowledged in policy circles, the response of the government in terms of allocation of resources for extension of irrigation facilities in India has been inadequate.

Table 5 Public Expenditure on Research and Extension in Agriculture and Allied Sector as Share of GDP of Agriculture and Allied Activities

Source: Balakrishnan et al (2008). Figures for 2009-10 and 2011-12 are computed by the author from Finance Accounts, Comptroller and Auditor General of India.

(in percentage)

Year	Research and Education	Extension
1960-62	0.21	0.09
1970-72	0.23	0.14
1980-82	0.39	0.11
1989-91	0.41	0.16
1992-94	0.40	0.15
1995-97	0.38	0.14
1998-00	0.44	0.15
2001-03	0.52	0.13
2004-06	0.52	0.13
2009-10	0.30	0.06
2011-12	0.32	0.05

Table 5 shows public expenditure on research and extension in agriculture and allied sector as a share of GDP of agriculture and allied activities. It shows that the share of public spending on research and extension in GDP of agriculture and allied activities was low since the 1960s, as well as in the subsequent decades. In other words, public spending on agricultural research and extension services did not increase after reforms.

Price Factors Affecting Agricultural Growth

It was expected that with agricultural trade liberalisation, India will emerge as a major exporter of agricultural commodities which will lead to inflows of scarce foreign exchange reserves in the economy due to elimination of bias against agriculture after reforms. In view of these arguments, it will be interesting to analyse trends in the movements of terms of trade in agriculture.

The terms of trade had started to move in favour of agriculture in the 1980s, and this trend continued till 1994-95. It was stagnant till 1998-99, and worsening mildly till 2008-09, falling further after 2010-11. There were improvements in the terms of trade between 2009-10 and 2011-12 after which there was again a decline till 2013-14. In all, there was no marked improvement in the terms of trade for agriculture as was expected with the onset of reforms. In fact, in certain phases in the post-reform period, the terms of trade for agricultural producers worsened.

Table 6 Annual International Prices of Selected Agricultural Commodities, 1981 to 2015

(\$ Current Prices)

Period	1981	1986	1991	1995	2000	2005	2010	2015
Commodities								
Wheat, USA	178	115	129	179	119	158	243	232
Wheat, Argentina	191	89	100	167	120	131	253	226
Rice, Thailand	483	210	314	322	204	288	521	380
Sugar (cents/pound)	9	6	9	13	8	10	21	13
Soyabean, US	288	209	240	259	212	275	450	390
Soyabean, oil, The Netherlands	507	343	454	625	338	544	1,005	757
Sunflower oil, EU	639	366	474	693	392	677	1,074	846
Groundnut oil, The Netherlands	1,043	570	895	991	714	1,060	1,404	1,337
Cotton, Egypt (cents/pound)	155	147	226	NA	109	101	170	NA
Cotton, US (cents/pounds)	89	57	82	104	66	59	103	75

Prices of sugar and cotton are in US cents/pound, the rest are in US dollars/tonne.

Sources: United Nations Conference on Trade and Development.

Furthermore, international prices of agricultural commodities are characterised by fluctuations in prices. Table 6 shows that international prices of most of the commodities, except for cotton (Egypt) and sugar, had declined in the 1980s. It recovered briefly till the mid-1990s, although international prices of most of the agricultural commodities in 1995 were lower as compared to 1981. Prices again went down in the late 1990s, and this trend continued till 2005. There was a brief recovery again between 2005 and 2010, after which prices declined. It can be seen that the price of all agricultural commodities in 2015 had gone down compared to 2010.

Ghosh (2010) points out that changes in regulations related to spot and futures commodity trading had given a major boost to speculative activities in commodity markets whereby speculators and financial firms—banks, pension funds, and hedge funds—increasingly entered the market in order to profit from short-term changes in prices. It meant that international prices of primary commodities, with a history of volatility, fluctuate more due to speculative activities of large financial firms to the detriment of a large agrarian population in developing economies like India.

In India, where almost 91 per cent of households are marginal, small and medium farmers who cultivate on less than 2 hectares (5 acres) of land, exposure to fluctuations in international prices through greater participation in trade of agricultural commodities will endanger livelihood security of substantial sections of the population in rural areas. In a survey of eight villages across different states of India between 2005 and 2007, it was observed that a significant proportion of households across villages located in different agro-ecological settings with different irrigation and cropping patterns had negative incomes mainly due to losses suffered in cultivation of agricultural crops. This shows that income generating capacity in agriculture is under serious threat (Swaminathan and Rawal 2011).

Conclusion

Agricultural trade policy reforms need to be accelerated much more than what has been done so far. The challenge is to make soften the inefficiency that exists in the Indian agriculture to close the gap between its potential and actual performance through a proper policy framework. It was argued that with the initiation of reforms in 1991-92, the bias against agriculture will be reduced, there will be a shift in the terms of trade in its favour, and price incentives will favour producers to increase production. This would enable the producers to increase the surplus from cultivation of agricultural crops that can be ploughed back to make long term improvements on land, undertake purchase of machines and farm implements that raise productivity of land. However, contrary to this expectation, the actual performance of the agricultural sector was not impressive in the post-reform period in comparison to the pre-reform period. Growth rates of the agriculture sector as a whole and across major crops cultivated in India have deteriorated, as has the importance of agriculture as an income generating activity. However, the sector remains the main source of employment in India. This implies that disparity in income generation between agriculture and other sectors, particularly services, has increased.

Non-price factors such as capital formation in agriculture (with an important role for irrigation), rural credit, and research and extension services were not given adequate importance in the post-reform period. Share of agriculture in gross capital formation started to decline in the 1980s, with no turnaround in the 1990s, the greatest casualty being public capital formation in agriculture. A similar pattern is witnessed for irrigation, where share of outlays in GDP and productivity have declined in the post-reform period. Trends in rural credit show that there has

been a steady decline in rural branches of commercial banks in line with financial liberalisation initiated after reforms. There was a decline in credit-deposit ratio in the 1990s as compared to the 1980s, adversely affecting supply of credit in rural areas.

The increase in the credit-deposit ratio, as well as the share of priority sector and agriculture in total outstanding credit since 2001 were largely due to definitional changes benefiting large agri-business corporations and large cultivators. Agricultural research and extension are seen to have been systematically neglected during the reform period. It needs to be mentioned here that it was neglected prior to the initiation of reforms as well; this neglect further accentuated after the 1990s.

Expectations regarding improvements in terms of trade for agriculture did not materialise after the reforms. Besides, agricultural trade liberalisation has exposed domestic producers to the volatilities of international prices of agricultural commodities that have turned agriculture into an unviable occupation. Studies carried out in different parts of India have also shown that a significant proportion of households were earning negative incomes from crop production. Neither there has been any significant movement in the terms of trade in favour of agriculture after reforms, nor have the cultivators gained from more exposure to international markets and prices.

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A STUDY ON INDIA'S OIL IMPORTS AND ITS IMPACT ON GREEN ECONOMIC GROWTH

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Abstract

This study examines whether energy fuels economic growth or vice versa in the Indian context. Also the study suggests that it is the economic growth that fuels more demand for both crude oil and electricity consumption and it is the only growth of coal consumption that causes economic growth. When influence of different components of energy on major two components of economic growth is tried with same causality test, none of the components of energy found to be significantly influencing the components of economic growth viz. private consumption and private investment. However, on the basis of application of statistical tools, the study with little more conviction could suggest for reducing oil and natural gas consumption for achieving higher rate of economic growth in the economy.

Keywords: Energy Consumption, Economic Growth, Economic Development

Introduction

Oil is a fossil fuel. Most of the oil extracted today has been formed from prehistoric organisms whose remains settled at the bottoms of oceans and lakes millions of years ago. As layers of sediment covered them, the pressure on them increased which in turn increased the temperature. This process changed their chemical composition, eventually transforming them into oil.

Generating electricity by burning oil is costly and releases a high level of greenhouse gases. Consequently, oil fired power stations are currently used only to provide backup power, when there is a chance that demand for electricity might not be met by less costly and carbon intensive energy sources.

Oil and the Economy: A Global Perspective Global Economic Growth

The impact of commodity prices on the macro economy has been the subject of a weighty body of academic research. In general terms, there are two key channels that are often discussed when assessing the impact of commodity price inflation on economic growth.

- The first is that an increase in commodity prices can lead to higher inflation and therefore result in tighter monetary policy than would otherwise have been the case. This tighter policy would, in turn, reduce the pace of economic growth.
- The second is that higher commodity prices can act as a “tax” on consumers and business, lowering profits and reducing consumption and investment. From a global point of view movements in commodity prices are in normal times a zero sum game, with some countries (companies) benefiting from higher revenues, while others face a deterioration in their terms of trade. Although there will be frictional issues consumers will feel the impact of higher prices more quickly than the companies and countries that benefit can spend the increased

income the ultimate impact would normally be more one of distribution rather than being negative or positive at a global level.

- However, although this is generally the case, in the current macroeconomic climate, as the global economy continues to recover from the “Great Recession,” the distributional issues related to rapid increases in commodity prices are likely to be more pronounced than normal.
- In simple terms, many of the countries that benefit most from increased commodity prices are in the emerging world (Saudi Arabia, Brazil, etc., although Canada and Australia are notable exceptions) and have rebounded strongly following the “Great Recession.” Given that these economies have little spare capacity, increased income from higher commodity prices contributed to the need to tighten policy in early 2011, as there was little scope for output to expand further.
- In contrast, many of the countries where economies remain fragile, primarily Japan and the mature North Atlantic, are those that have experienced a marked deterioration in their terms of trade from increasing commodity prices.

Given that the North Atlantic developed economies generally experienced large recessions and have big output gaps and weak and fragile growth, increased commodity prices (particularly oil) have had a significant effect on consumer behavior over the past year, with consumers remaining vulnerable to further price spikes.

In contrast, in emerging economies the main challenge from increasing commodity prices has been in ensuring that higher prices don't flow through to generalized inflation and inflation expectations. This is because these economies are now operating with little economic slack, and many may experience a boost to their terms of trade as natural resource prices increase. In simple terms, the current imbalance between growth in the emerging and developed economies has increased the impact of higher commodity prices on global growth, with the move higher a tax on the economies trying to stimulate growth (acting to depress growth) and a stimulus to economies that are already trying to slow growth. Consequently the positive effect has been limited by policy, while the negative effect has been exacerbated in the developed world by the lack of traditional policy firepower (interest rates are already low and fiscal policy is stretched).

Relation between Oil Price and Economic Activity

Recent developments in oil markets and the global economy have, once again, triggered concerns about the impact of oil price shocks around the world. This column wonders whether the fuss is really necessary. It presents evidence of relatively small negative effects of oil price increases.

Increases in international oil prices over the past couple years, explained partly by strong growth in large emerging and developing economies, have raised concerns that high oil prices could endanger the shaky recovery in advanced economies and small oil-importing countries. The notion that oil prices can have a macroeconomic impact is well accepted; the debate has centered mainly on magnitude and transmission channels. Most studies have focused on the US and other OECD economies. And much of the discussion has related to the role of monetary policy, labor markets, and the intensity of oil in production (Hamilton 1983, Barsky and Kilian 2004, Bernanke et al 1997, Blanchard and Gali 2007).

The manner in which oil prices affect emerging and developing economies has received surprisingly little attention compared with the large body of evidence for advanced economies. In an attempt to provide a broader and more encompassing view on the impact of oil price shocks,

we document in recent research (Rasmussen and Roitman 2011) key stylized facts that characterize the relationship between oil prices and macroeconomic aggregates across the world.

Objective

Growth is the basic for economic development, which is one of the main objectives of any society and also energy consumption is fundamental for economic growth and development as well. Main objectives can be summarized as:

1. To analyze the connection between energy imports and economic growth,
2. To study the correlation between oil imports and its impact on economic activity and,
3. To analyze the growth rate of Petroleum, Crude and Products imports and its impact on economic growth,

Currently, energy is one of the most critical international issues; it affects political and economical relations of countries, and plays significant role in the real growth of the economy and development. It is considered as one of the most important factors of production, too.

Data Description & Methodology

The study considers the annual data from 1990-91 to 2010-14. The source of these data is www.indiastat.com and Central Statistical Organisation (CSO). The study considers growth of various forms of energy consumption such as coal, natural gas, crude petroleum and Products.

The growth of energy variables in the empirical analysis has been related to the simple growth rates of GDP as well as different major components of growth rates of GDP such as private consumption and private investment. Growth rate of GDP is defined as the change in the GDP in two consecutive periods divided by its initial period value.

The percent change from one period to another is calculated from the formula:

Where:

$$PR = \frac{(V_{Present} - V_{Past})}{V_{Past}} \times 100$$

PR = Percent Rate
 $V_{Present}$ = Present or Future Value
 V_{Past} = Past or Present Value

The annual percentage growth rate is simply the percent growth divided by N, the number of years.

The same formula is also followed for computing growth rates of rest of the variables. Private investment refers to the gross private capital formation and private consumption refers to gross private final consumption as reported by CSO.

The data considered for the study is from 1991 to 2011 of imports of petroleum, crude and product in India. In the below table is shows the year wise imports of petroleum, crude and products.

Table 1 India's Petroleum, Crude and Products (Rs in Cores)

Year/Petrol	Petroleum, Crude and Products (Rs in Cores)
1990-91	10816.1
1991-92	13126.7
1992-93	17141.7
1993-94	18046.2
1994-95	18612.6
1995-96	25173.6
1996-97	35628.5

1997-98	30341.2
1998-99	26919.3
1999-00	54648.6
2000-01	71496.5
2001-02	66769.9
2002-03	85367.0
2003-04	94520.0
2004-05	134094.0
2005-06	194640.0
2006-07	258571.8
2007-08	320654.5
2008-09	419967.6
2009-10	411649.1
2010-11	482714.3

In the below table 2 shows that, the growth rate of imports of petroleum, crude and products in India. This result shows that change in growth rates and imports rates do not affect the growth of Indian oil imports.

Table 2 Growth rate of India’s Petroleum, Crude and Products (Rs in Cores)

Year/Petrol	Petroleum, Crude and Products (Rs in Cores)	Growth Rate (P2-P1/P1)
1990-91	10816.1	--
1991-92	13126.7	0.21
1992-93	17141.7	0.31
1993-94	18046.2	0.05
1994-95	18612.6	0.03
1995-96	25173.6	0.35
1996-97	35628.5	0.42
1997-98	30341.2	-0.15
1998-99	26919.3	-0.11
1999-00	54648.6	1.03
2000-01	71496.5	0.31
2001-02	66769.9	-0.07
2002-03	85367.0	0.28
2003-04	94520.0	0.11
2004-05	134094.0	0.42
2005-06	194640.0	0.45
2006-07	258571.8	0.33
2007-08	320654.5	0.24
2008-09	419967.6	0.31
2009-10	411649.1	-0.02
2010-11	482714.3	0.17

The decomposition of growth rate of oil consumption reported in Table 2 shows that the variation in electricity growth rate is initially being explained by its own shock but from 3rd horizon onwards, growth rate of GDP to a certain significant degree explains the variation in the growth rate of electricity consumption demand. This implies that with the growth of oil imports, there is an increasing demand for energy consumption in the economy.

Figure 1 India's Petroleum, Crude and Products Growth Rate (1990-2011)

In the above figure 1 shows that, the year wise growth rate of imports of petroleum, crude and products. From the above decomposition analysis, it could be noticed that there is no causal relationship of growth of crude oil and growth of natural gas with GDP growth rate. However, there exists a bi-directional causal relationship between electricity consumption and economic growth rate and a unidirectional causal relationship from coal consumption to economic growth.

Conclusion

The paper examined the linkage between various forms of growth of energy consumption and economic growth in India. Besides direct impact of energy consumption on economic growth, it also examined the influence of various forms of energy consumption growth on private consumption and private investment growth as different components of GDP growth. Hence, the study provides mixed and contradictory evidence on the relationship between energy consumption and GDP growth rate as compared to the previous studies carried out in the Indian context.

However, with little more conviction from application of both the statistical tools, the study could suggest for reducing oil and natural gas consumption for achieving higher economic growth as these sources are not contributory to economic growth rather the consumption of these are growth driven, which may have adverse impact on the balance of payment position of the economy in the future.

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AN EMPIRICAL STUDY ON QUALITY OF WORK LIFE OF EMPLOYEES IN BSNL, CHENNAI

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Abstract

The success of any organization is highly dependent on how it attracts, Recruits, motivates, and retains its workforce. Today's organizations need to be more flexible so that they are equipped to develop their workforce and enjoy their commitment. Therefore, organizations are required to adopt a strategy to improve the Employees' 'quality of work life' (QWL) to satisfy both the organizational Objectives and employee needs. This case lets discuss the importance of Having effective quality of work life practices in organizations and their impact on employee performance and the overall organizational performance. By keeping this in mind the project "A STUDY ON QUALITY OF WORK LIFE IN BSNL CHENNAI" Survey has been studied and findings, suggestions And recommendations are made to help the company to increase the moral of the employee. For survey due to time constraints, Human resource Department is Selected in BSNL at CHENNAI.

Introduction

Quality of work life refers to the "quality of relationship between employees and the total working environment". Quality of work life promotes individual learning and development. It provides individuals with influence and control over what they do it. It also made available to the individuals interesting and meaningful work as a source of personal rewards. Quality of work life refers to a concern about the impact of work on people as well as on organizational effectiveness. Qualities of work life create an idea of participation in organizational problem solving and decision-making. The safety measures, job satisfaction, suitable environment condition and other facilities with the help of here factors we can identify condition of quality work life in the organization.

QWL provides more humanized work environment. It attempts to serve the higher order needs of the workers as well as their more basic needs. It seeks to employ the higher skills of workers and to provide an environment that encourages improving their skills.

Q - Quest for excellence

U - Understanding

A - Action

L - Leadership

I - Involvement of the people

T - Team spirit

Y- Yard stick to measure progress

The Study of the Birth and Growth of Telephone Service in Chennai

Telephone came first to India in 1875. In Madras State, the first telephone exchange to be installed was in Madras city with 24 connections on 30.1.1882. After 43 years, telephone service was made available to the CHENNAI, the 2nd biggest town in Madras state. On 01.09.1924 a manual exchange of 200 lines capacity, working on central battery system, with automatic ringing and secret service facilities was installed with 92 direct connections and 14 extensions.

Telephone came to CHENNAI before the town was late with electricity. Department had installed primary cells for providing the electrical energy to the exchange. CHENNAI SSA consists of revenue district of CHENNAI, DINDIGUL and THENI.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the quality of work life of employees in BSNL, CHENNAI.
2. To study the employees opinion about their responsibilities and duties in BSNL.
3. To know the working environment of employees this leads to favorable and unfavorable quality of work.
4. To suggest possible measures to improve the quality of work life of BSNL employees, CHENNAI.

Meaning of quality of work life

The term QUALITY OF WORK LIFE (QWL) refers to the favorableness or unfavorableness of a total job environment for people. QWL programs are another way in which organizations recognize their responsibility to develop jobs and working conditions that are excellent for people as well as for economic health of the organization.

The quality of working life is a generic phrase that covers a person's feelings about every dimensions of work, including economic rewards and benefits, security, working condition, organizational ad interpersonal relationships and its intrinsic meaning in a person's life.

According Walton defines QWL as a process by which an organization responds to employee needs for developing mechanisms to allow them to share fully in making the decisions that design their lives at work.

Principles of QWL

- Principles of security: working condition must be safe; employee does not have fear etc
- Principles of equity: eliminate discrimination between people doing same work
- Principles of individualism: individual have the opportunity to develop his potential
- Principles of democracy: greater authority & responsibility to employees

Techniques for Improving QWL

- Flexible work schedules :flextime is a system of flexible working hours, staggered hours schedule means that different groups of employees begin & end at different intervals
- Job rotation :improves quality of work, satisfies higher level needs of employees
- Opportunity for development: employees are provided with opportunities for their advancement & growth
- Autonomous work groups: called self managed work teams, freedom of decision making to employees
- Employee's participation in management: Quality circles, suggestion system etc helps to improve QWL
- Job security: stability of employment
- Equitable justice: partiality & biasness at any stage discourage the workers

Effects Quality of Work Life

- **Job involvement:-** indicates the extent of peoples identification with or ego investment in the job

- **Sense of competence**:-it denotes the feelings of confidence that one has in ones own competence.
- **Job satisfaction**:-it is a set of favorable or unfavorable feelings with which employees view their jobs, more specifically the nature of jobs they do, the quality of supervision they receive, co-workers pay and perks and promotional avenues.

Quality of Work Life

Constructs of QWL

- **Health & Wellbeing**: QWL refers to physical& psychological aspects of an individual in any working environment.
- **Job Security**: There is a dramatic change in organizations due contemporary work environment.
- **Job Satisfaction** is one of the heavily studied construct of QWL. IT is defined as an employee's level of positive effect towards job or job situation that enhances QWL.
- **Competency Development** is to enhance the skill sets in order to remain employable. There should be task variety & skill development opportunities to foster the competency development among the workforce.
- **Work & Non work Life Balance** is a major component of QWL which is important for both the employees, is the relationship b/w work& home life.

Benefits of Quality of Work Life

- More positive feeling toward one's self.
- More positive feeling towards the organization.
- Improved physical and psychological health.
- Greater growth and development of the individual as a person and as a productivity number of the organization.
- Decreased absenteeism and turnover, and fewer accidents.
- Higher quality and quality of output of goods and services.

Research Methodology

1. Research Type - Descriptive research Studies often involve the description of the extent of association between two or more variables.
2. Sampling Technique -
3. Sampling design - Due to BSNL employees, we confined our study using Convenience Sampling. Due to the population is very large; we took some samples only and collected data.
4. Sample Size - Number of Respondents: 50.
5. Research Instrument - *Questionnaire*.
6. Contact Method - The contact method used in our study is *personal* method.
7. Data Sources - Data collection methods used for the study are primary and secondary.
8. Statistical Tools:

Percentage Analysis

Chi-square test

Weighted Average Ranking method

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1 Classification of Job schedule

S.No	Job schedule	No. of Respondents	% of Respondents
1	Highly satisfied	22	44
2	Satisfied	20	40
3	Some extent	6	12
4	Dissatisfaction	2	4
	Total	50	100

Inference

From the above table, it is clear that 44% of respondents are highly satisfied with their job content.

Chart 1

Table 2 Communication prevailing in the entire organization

S.No	Options	No. of Respondents	%of Respondents
1	Excellent	18	36
2	Good	22	44
3	Not bad	10	20
4	Poor	0	0
5	Very poor	0	0
	Total	50	100

Inference

From the above table, it is clear that most of respondents are having good communication in entire organization.

Chart 2

Statistical Tools**Chi-Square Test****Comparison of training program improves quality of work life and experience**

N.H (H₀) : Training program improves quality of work life and employees experience is independent.

A.H (H₁): Training program improves quality of work life and employees experience is not independent.

Observed frequency

Experience	Must improve	Improve	Total
Below10 yrs	1	3	4
11-20 yrs	3	19	22
21-30yrs	3	16	19
31& above	1	4	5
Total	8	42	50

Expected frequency

0.64	3.36
3.42	18.58
3.04	15.96
0.80	4.20

Calculation

Observed frequency	Expected frequency	$[(O_i - E_i)^2]/E_i$
1	0.64	0.20
3	3.42	0.05
3	3.04	0.00
1	0.80	0.05
3	3.36	0.04
19	18.58	0.01
16	15.96	0.00
4	4.20	0.01
Total		0.36

$$\text{Chi-square} = (O - E)^2 / E = 0.36$$

$$\text{Degrees of freedom} = (r-1)(c-1)$$

$$= (4-1)(2-1)$$

$$= (3)(1)$$

$$= 3$$

Tabulated value is 7.815

Here the calculated value is less than tabulated value, so it is accepted.

H₀ - null hypothesis is accepted
Training program improves quality

of work life and employees experience is independent

Weighted average method

$$\text{Weight average } A = \frac{\sum (w_i x_i)}{\sum w_i}$$

Here

A = weighted average mean

W_i = weighted allotted for each factor

X_i = frequency of respondent

Calculation

Scale	Weight	Respondents	Weight score
Highly satisfied	3	28	84
Satisfied	2	20	40
Dis satisfied	1	2	2
Total			126

Total number of respondent = 50

Total weight score = 126

Total weighted average = $\frac{\sum (w_i x_i)}{\sum w_i}$

$$= 126/50$$

$$= 2.52$$

Conclusion

From the above table showing that the respondent's opinion on the satisfaction of the responsibilities and duties it is concerned that the most of the employees are highly satisfied with the satisfaction of the responsibilities and duties of the organization.

Findings

- It is found that most of employees are aged between 45 and above.
- It is observed that majority of the employees are male.
- It is identified that most of the employees are clearly understand their responsibilities and duties.
- It is clear that majority of the employees are highly satisfied with their work schedule.
- It is found that most of the employees are having the work freedom and autonomy in planning their work.
- It is identified that most of the employees are got reward or promotion in the present work life.
- It is found that most of the employees are satisfied with their organization's welfare facilities.
- It is observed that most of the employees are satisfied with their training program improves their quality of work.

Suggestion

Responsibilities and Duties: Employees must know their responsibilities and duties. It is useful to increasing the quality of work. It is lack with poor communication and proper human relation and no proper schedules it should be corrected by the clear approach of employer then issuing proper schedules to each and every employee.

Job schedule: The job schedules must be issued but the schedule is to be practically possible one is important. Before issuing the schedule reference of employees past performance and capabilities and qualification is useful to contract the schedule for particular employees.

Relationship among employees: It must be increased by the meetings, parties and vacations etc. it is important to develop the co-operation in work.

Superior relationship: The strained relationship is affected the mutual understanding between the superior and subordinate. It affect the free flow of communication the good communication is possible for transfer the information.

Participation in management: The employee's suggestion is important to develop the organization. Employees want to give suggestion while meeting, complicated satiations

Motivation: Reward and promotion are most important motivating factor. Satisfaction arises to the maximum extent mainly due to reward and promotion.

Communication: Transfers of information are possible only when there is a proper communication. So it leads to attain organization goal easily.

Conclusion

As QUALITY OF WORK LIFE is a vital role in the scenario of management the people factor is very important and crucial for the organization. This project work was undertaken in this area. This work has been successful in considering almost all the factors that were found to be relevant of the topic. The whole of the project work is carried at BSNL, CHENNAI. Among the many variable employees are the only resources, which are capable of self-important and fulfillment.

Hence it has become imperative to improve employee's morale, and pave way for industrial democracy. Training program should be organized to fill up gaps between present and desired levels with regard to skills, knowledge and behavior of the employees. The management has to precede necessary action to improve the quality of work life. So research study will lead to establish a practice procedure for improvement of performance of employee's satisfaction in their work life. It is believed if the organization takes the suggestion provided in the work it shall bring in changes in the work life of the organization.

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“A STUDY ON VARIOUS INVESTMENTS AVAILABLE IN INDIA”

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Abstract

It is human nature to plan for rainy days. An individual must plan and keep aside some amount of money for any unavoidable circumstance which might arise in days to come. Future is uncertain and one must invest wisely to avoid financial crisis in any point of time. Let us first understand what is investment? Investment is nothing but goods or commodities purchased today to be used in future or at the times of crisis. An individual must plan his future well to ensure happiness for himself as well as his immediate family members. Consuming everything today and saving nothing for the future is foolish. Not every day is a bed of roses, you never know what your future has in store for you.

Keywords: Risk and Return, Bonds, shares, Tax

A Study on Various Investments Available in India

Financial system plays vital role in the economic growth of a country. It intermediates between the flow of funds belonging to those who save a part of their income and those who invest in productive assets. It mobilizes and usefully allocates scarce resources of a country.

It is complex, well-integrated set of subsystems of financial institutions, markets, instruments, and services which facilitates the transfer and allocation of funds, efficiently and effectively. The financial systems of most developing countries are characterized by coexistence and cooperation between the formal and informal financial sectors.

The coexistence of these two sectors is commonly referred to as financial dualism. The formal financial sector is characterized by the presence of an organized, institutional and regulated system which caters to the financial needs of the modern spheres of economy.

The informal financial sector has emerged as a result of the intrinsic dualism of economic and social structures in developing countries, and financial repression which inhibits the certain deprived sections of society from accessing funds. One of the important functions of a financial system is to link the savers and investors and, thereby, help in mobilizing and allocating the saving efficiently and effectively. By acting as an efficient conduit for allocation of resources it permits continuous up-gradation of technologies for promoting growth on a sustained basis.

A financial system not only helps in selecting project to be funded but also inspires the operators to monitor the performance of the investment. Financial markets and institutions help to monitor corporate performance and exercise corporate control through the threat of hostile takeovers for underperforming firms. It provides a payment mechanism for the exchange of goods and services and transfers economic resources through time and across geographic regions and industries.

One of the most important functions of a financial system is to achieve optimum allocation of risk bearing. It limits, pools and trades the risk involved in mobilizing saving and allocating credit. An efficient financial system aims at containing risk within acceptable limits. It reduces risk by laying down rules governing the operation of the system.

Risk reduction is achieved by holding diversified portfolios and screening of borrowers. Market participants gain protection from unexpected losses by buying financial insurance services. Risk is traded in the financial markets through financial instruments such as derivatives. Derivatives are risk shifting device, they shift risk from those who have it but may not want it to those who are willing to take it. The Indian financial system can broadly be classified into the formal/organized and informal/unorganized system. The formal financial system comes under the purview of the Ministry of Finance (MOF), Reserve Bank of India (RBI), Security and Exchange Board of India (SEBI), and other regulatory bodies. The informal financial system consists of:

- i. Individual moneylenders such as neighbors, relatives, landlords, traders and storeowners.
- ii. Groups of person operating as funds or associations. These groups function under a system of their own rules and use names such as fixed fund, association and saving club.
- iii. Partnership firms consisting of local brokers, pawnbrokers and non-bank financial intermediaries such as finance, investment and chit fund companies.

Features of Financial Instruments Risk, Return, Security, Liquidity, Tax Benefits, and Maturity Risk: All Financial instruments have some risk. It may be due to Maturity period. Risk is composed of the demands that bring in variations in return of income. Risk is influenced by External and Internal considerations. For example the longer the maturity period more will be the risk. The typical features of instruments can also cause variability in risk. Government securities have less risk than Private securities or Debt security will have less risk than Ownership security.

Return: Investments are made to have some Returns. All investors are interested in return in the form of a continuous return like yield, interest, and dividend and capital appreciation. Risk and Returns are inseparable. General belief is that higher the Risk greater the Reward. Investors are interested in a good return with minimum risk. Individual investor has to balance between the features of risk and return.

Security: Here security means the safety of the amount of investment. The investment amount should be received in time on the date of maturity without any delay. The investor has to balance between complete safety and low rate of return with some securities of higher risk for higher return.

Liquidity: Liquid instruments are those instruments which can be easily marketed or realized. Tradable equity shares which have an active sale in the stock market is Liquid. Fixed deposits can be made liquid with some loss in terms of interest. Investments like National Savings Scheme and Public Provident Fund are not Liquid Assets.

Tax Benefits: Investors prefer financial instruments which have tax benefits. Tax benefits change according to government policies. In order to attract more investment for the productive use in economic development there are certain tax saver schemes. The investor has to evaluate and find out which bonds or instruments are tax free to make the investment.

Maturity: Different kinds of maturities are an important feature of financial instruments. Bonds and securities have a maturity date whereas Equity shares do not have a maturity date. Bonds have stable return through interest and Equity shares provide stability through dividends. Investors find equity shares attractive due to capital appreciation, Investors have to keep on their portfolio with securities having a maturity date as well as those which do not have a maturity date.

Real & Financial Assets: Real Assets refers to tangible assets which have physical appearance, which can be movable or immovable may be marketable or non-marketable. Example: Land & Building, Furniture, gold, silver, diamonds etc.

Financial Asset (Paper Securities) represent a claim on the income generated by real assets of some other parties. Financial assets are usually between two parties. It can be easily traded as they are marketable and transferable. Example: Shares, bonds, debentures, bills, loans, lease, derivatives, fixed deposits etc.

Difference between Real Assets & Financial Assets

Real Assets

Financial Assets Tangible Assets which can be movable or Immovable Paper Securities as they deal with claims generated on the Issuer. Land, Building, Furniture, Machinery, Gold, Silver, Diamond Shares, Debentures, Bonds, Derivates, Bills, Fixed Deposits, Loans, Lease Used for production of goods and services Financial claims represented by securities.

Various Investment means Available in India

The investment alternatives are as follows:

Equity Shares: Ownership securities- classified into different categories like Speculative shares, Growth Shares, Income Shares, Blue chip Shares etc.

Money Market Instruments: Commercial Papers, Treasury Bills, Certificates

Bonds: Debt Securities - Government Bonds, Debentures, Bonds of Financial Institutions.

Mutual Funds: Growth funds, Income funds, Index funds, Sector funds

Life Insurance Companies: Endowment Policy, Whole life policy, Money Back Policy, Term Policy, Retirement Policy

Post Offices: Fixed Deposit, Public Provident Fund, Indira VikasPatra, KissanVikasPatra, Savings Bond, National Savings Certificate

Real Estate: Commercial Property, Residential Land, Apartment, Agricultural Land
Precious Metals & Art Objects --- Gold, Silver, Precious Stones

Features of Investment Programme

1. Safety of Principal
2. Liquidity
3. Income Stability
4. Appreciation and Purchasing Power Stability
5. Legality
6. Freedom from Care

Finance Vs. Investment

Finance is the activity through which funds can be collected and Investment is the activity by which resources are committed to some productive units. Finance and Investments are complementary to each other.

Relationship of Finance and Investment

Finance: Investments Finance is concerned with sources of money It is concerned with the use of money Finance locates the most economical source of money. Investment locates the optimum rate of return Planning of resources and finding out the total money required. It is the study of avenues where the money can be utilized. Finance helps in optimum costing it helps in optimum return Finance aims at finding out the time span of requirement of money it aims at making proportion of the total money into different assets maturing at different time period.

Investment Decision Making

Investment decisions are influenced by risk group, risk perception, attitude and tax positions of the investors.

Profile of Indian Investors

Generally Indian investors are interested in high return even though they are Risk averse. Surveys conducted by various organizations like central statistical organization, RBI, Society for Capital market & Research Delhi on Indian Households 'investment preferences.

The following are certain important indications showing profile of Indian Investors.

- Low income group generally prefers bank fixed deposits, Post office recurring deposits, Recognized chit funds.
- Middle income group prefer mutual Funds for regularity of income or Life insurance policies.
- High income group prefer Equity shares, Real Estates as well as Government Bonds to reduce the tax burden
- Lower income group & High income group give more importance to safety and liquidity of the investment as compared to high income group. □ Shares are significant investment for not only the High Income Group but also for retired people, housewives and students due to online share trading facility made available which helps in making short term profits,
- The IPO (Initial Public Offering) is more popular than the secondary market.
- Investors in India are mainly in the urban areas and rural areas are yet to be tapped. □ Investments in Gold & Property is a high priority irrespective of the type of investors.
- Life Insurance Policies are preferred by all middle income groups.

Factors Influencing Investment Decisions

Risk Group; Income Group; Tax positions; Risk perception and Attitude

Risk Group

There are three risk groups:

Risk Averter: people who avoid Risk (will pay less for an uncertain action)

Risk Neutral: people who take some risk (will pay equal to expected return of uncertain action)

Risk Takers: People who take High Risk (will pay more than expected value for an uncertain action.)

Return after tax

Example 1

A bond has a rate of interest of 10% and the investor pays income tax at 30% calculate the after tax rate of return?

After tax return = coupon rate (1- tax rate)

= 10/100 (1- 30/100)

= .10 (1 - .30) = .10 x 0.70 = 0.07 or 7%

Example 2

Tax -free rate is 6% and the investor pays a tax rate of 20%. Calculate taxable equivalent yield?

Taxable Equivalent Yield = Tax Free Rate

(1- Tax rate)

= 0.06

(1- 0.20)

= 0.075 or 7.5%

Risk

Risk is composed of the demands that bring in variation in return of income. It can be defined as a situation where the possible consequences of the decision that is to be taken are known. Uncertainty is generally defined to apply to situations where the probabilities cannot be estimated.

Risk and return are inseparable and very important in construction of a portfolio. First the Risk and Return coincident with the individual securities must be determined. These estimates must be used to form portfolio that best meet the needs of the investor. This decision is called the –trade off between risk and expected return.

Types of Risk

1. Systematic Risk
2. Unsystematic Risk

Systematic Risk

It is due to the influence of external factors on an organization .Normally uncontrollable from the organization's point of view. It is Macro in nature. It affects large number of organizations operating under a similar stream or same domain, cannot be planned by the organization. Systematic risk is the uncertainty inherent to the entire market or entire market segment.

Types of Systematic Risk

1. Market Risk
2. Interest Risk
3. Purchasing Power Risk

Market Risk: It is associated with consistent fluctuations seen in the trading prices of any particular shares or securities which are listed in the stock market. Investor's reaction towards tangible and intangible events is the chief cause affecting market risk. Price variation will create emotional instability causes fear of loss or create an undue confidence relating to the possibility of profit. Market risk cannot be eliminated but can be reduced through diversification.

Interest Risk: It arises due to variability in the interest rates from time to time. This is one of the most prominent risks to which debt funds are exposed to. This particularly affects Debt securities as they carry fixed rate of interest. It can be Price Risk or Reinvestment Risk. There are four kinds of movements in prices of stocks in the market--- Long term, Cyclical (Bull& Bear Market), Intermediate or within the cycle and short term. Prices of all securities rise or fall depending on the change in interest rates. In India combination of factors made it difficult to find out changes in interest rate accurately. Difference between actual and expected inflation, monetary policies, industrial recession in economy are the factors responsible for the changes in the interest rates. Interest rate risk can be reduced by diversifying in various kinds of securities and also by buying securities of different maturity dates.

Purchasing Power Risk / Inflation Risk: It arises out of change in the price of goods and services. In India Purchasing power risk is associated with inflation and rising prices in the economy. Inflation has been either cost push or demand pull. Consumers sacrificing their present consumption level to purchase commodities in future cannot adjust their prices because they were faced with rising prices and shortage of funds for allocation according to their preference.

Unsystematic Risk: Risk due to internal environment of a firm or those affecting a particular industry due to factors like labour strike, consumer preferences and management policies. It is due to the influence of internal factors prevailing within an organization. Such factors are normally

controllable from an organization's point of view. It is micro in nature and affects only a particular organization.

Types of Unsystematic Risk

1. Business Risk or Liquidity Risk
2. Financial or Credit Risk
3. Operational Risk

Business Risk

Every organization has its own objectives and goals and aims at a particular Gross Profit and Operating income. Once it identifies its operating level of earnings the degree of variation from the level measures as business risk. For example operating income is expected to be 15%. Business Risk will be low if operating income varies between 14% and 16%. If it is as low as 10% or as high as 18% it would be said that the business risk is high.

Business Risk is associated with risks directly affecting the internal environment of the firm or those of circumstances beyond its control. Risk associated with internal environment is known as internal business risk and circumstances beyond its control is called external environment.

Financial Risk or Credit Risk: It is associated with the method through which it plans its financial structure. If capital structure tends to make earnings unstable company may fail financially.

How the company raise funds will have an impact on its future earnings and on the stability of earnings. As long as earnings of the company are higher than cost of borrowed funds earnings per share on common stock increases. Variations in returns for shareholders in borrowed fund company is higher than less leveraged firms. Variance in return is the financial risk.

Operational Risk: It is the risk of loss resulting from inadequate or failed internal processes, people and systems or from external events. It will change from industry to industry. It can be employee errors, system failures, fraud or other criminal activity or any event that disrupts business processes.

Measurement of Risk: Risk and Return are inseparable. Return is a statistical term and it is measurable whereas Risk is not a precise statistical term. Risk can be measured scientifically both through probability distributions and statistical measures of standard deviation and beta. Investors are aware that there is uncertainty in returns because there is risk associated with it. To measure risk, an investor should first understand the fact that risk cannot be measured accurately because it is surrounded with complex environmental factors and social, economic and political forces. The variability of return around the expected average is thus a quantitative description of risk.

As risk arises out of variability Standard Deviation & Variance is the most useful method for calculating variability.

The riskiness of stocks in terms of systematic and unsystematic components is tested through the market model. According to the market model, the return on any stock is related to the return on the market index in a linear manner. This market model is based on Empirical Testing. This measure of quantifying risk is also referred to as Beta analysis. Beta concept is done through the use of regression equation. The most important part of the equation is Beta. It is used to describe the relationship between the stock's return and market index's returns.

Yield is calculated for a particular period to find out the return on the amount that is invested.

Current Yield = $\frac{\text{Cash income}}{\text{Expected income}} \times 100$

Amount Invested

Example

An investor buys a 20 year bond at Rs.800 It carries 100 worth of coupon and its par value is Rs.1000. Calculate its current yield.

$$\text{Current Yield} = \frac{100}{800} \times 100 = 12.5\%$$

800

Yield to Maturity (YTM)

$$\text{YTM} = \frac{C}{N} + \frac{M - P}{N}$$

N x100

M + P/2

C = Annual Coupon

M=Maturity value of the Bond

P =Purchase Price

N = Number of years to maturity.

Example

An investor buys a bond at Rs. 900. It has a maturity value of 10 years and par value is Rs.1000. It fetches Rs.90 every year. Calculate current yield and yield to maturity.

$$\text{Current Yield} = \frac{90}{900} \times 100 = 10\%$$

$$\text{YTM} = \frac{C}{N} + \frac{M - P}{N} \times 100$$

M +P/2

C =90; P =900; M =1000; N=10

$$= \frac{90}{10} + \frac{1000 - 900}{10} \times 100$$

1000+900/2

$$= \frac{100}{950} = 10.5\%$$

Conclusion

In the current scenario, investing is very important and investing in stock markets is a major challenge ever for professionals. The young people should start investing earlier so that they can reap the benefits of investing in future. People should keep their eye open and keep updating themselves about various investment avenues so that they can get safe returns

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A STUDY ON THE EVOLUTION AND GROWTH OF MEDICAL TOURISM IN TAMILNADU

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Introduction

Medical tourism can be broadly defined as provision of cost-effective private medical care in collaboration with the tourism industry for patients needing surgical and other forms of specialized treatment. This process is being facilitated by the corporate sector involved in medical care as well as the tourism industry- both private and public.

Medical tourism is becoming a common form of vacationing. In those days, people used to travel for site seeing but why most people go for a vacation is for refreshment. Hence medical tourism mixes leisure, fun and relaxation together with wellness and healthcare.

Medical tourism, where foreigners travel abroad in search of low cost, world-class medical treatment, is gaining popularity in India particularly in cities like Chennai, Bangalore and Bombay.

Apollo Hospitals, started at Chennai, is one of the earliest corporate hospitals in India catering to foreign tourists looking to the medical tourism industry in India for cheap medical treatment, and this group has its presence in over six countries, and operates about 35 hospitals across India. Escorts Hospital is one of the best hospitals for cardiac ailments in the world and is one of the top hospitals in India catering to the medical tourism industry.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this research paper are to:

1. Trace the evolution and growth of medical tourism and understand its significance on host economies;
2. Review the state of medical tourism in India and the opportunities and challenges facing the country; and
3. Devise strategies to service market in India as the destination for medical tourism.

Tamil Nadu Tourism Development

Tamil Nadu's tourism industry is the second largest in India, with an annual growth rate of 16%. Tourism in Tamil Nadu is promoted by Tamilnadu Tourism Development Corporation (TTDC), a Government of Tamil Nadu undertaking. The tagline adopted for promoting tourism in Tamil Nadu is Enchanting Tamil Nadu. Approximately 1,753,000 foreign and 50,647,000 domestic tourists visited the state in 2007.

Tamil Nadu is the land of the Tamils and it has a history that dates back to several thousand years. It is a land where traditions and culture blend and people continue to live in harmony. The

state abounds in monuments and temples that are ancient and each has its own story of religious, artistic and cultural accomplishment.

Tamil Nadu has a long coastline that stretches nearly a 1000 kms. The Coromandel Coast, along the Bay of Bengal, boasts of many ideal locations for sun and surf. Golden sands of the beach are dotted with coconut palm and caesarians groves. The sea washes ashore pebbles and shells and the gentle breeze sways the yachts and catamarans into the deeper waters of the sea and the waters form small dunes on the shore. Crabs play hide-and-seek by coming out of one burrow, and taking refuge in another. Sea gulls hover in the sky and then rest on the sails of the fishing boats. There are many more breathtaking sights that will please you and hold you spell bound in Tamil Nadu.

Competition (Neighboring Countries)

Countries that actively promote medical tourism include Cuba, Costa Rica, Hungary, India, Israel, Jordan, Lithuania, Malaysia and Thailand. Belgium, Poland and Singapore are now entering the field. South Africa specializes in medical safaris-visit the country for a safari, with a stopover for plastic surgery, a nose job and a chance to see lions and elephants. Thus India has enough competition from the international market. This will be one of our major threats in bringing up and developing the health tourism industry.

Insurance Backup

One good way of tapping the foreign customers is tying up with Insurance companies abroad who could provide a genuine database of target customers. They can benefit from us by our services. Thus this would become a way of mutual marketing tactics between the Indian health tourism industry and the foreign Insurance agencies.

Tourism and Hospitality

The booming tourism industry has had a cascading effect on the hospitality sector with an increase in the occupancy ratios and average room rates. While occupancy ratio is around 75-80 per cent, the average increase in room rates has been hovering around 22-25 per cent. And with the continuing surge in tourist inflow, this sector is likely to offer tremendous opportunity for investors. For example, while the estimated number of required hotel rooms is around 240,000, the current availability is just 90,000 rooms - leaving a shortfall of 150,000 rooms to be provided. With such a huge potential available in this segment, several global hotel chains like the Hilton, Accor, Marriott International, Berggren Hotels, Cabana Hotels, Premier Travel Inn (PTI), InterContinental Hotels group and Hampshire among others have all announced major investment plans for the country. The Government's move to declare hotel and tourism industry as a high priority sector with a provision for 100 per cent foreign direct investment (FDI) has also provided a further impetus in attracting investments in to this industry. It is estimated that the hospitality sector is likely to see US\$ 11.41 billion in the next two years, with around 40 international hotel brands making their presence in the country by 2011. Simultaneously, international hotel asset management companies are also likely to enter India. Already, US-based HVS International has firmed up plans to enter India, and industry players believe others like Ashford Hospitality Trust and IFA Hotels & Resorts among others are likely to follow suit. After Information Technology (IT) and Information Technology enabled Services (IteS), which are currently good contributors to our nation's GDP, the next big thing happening (already begun!!!) could be 'medical tourism', which

has enormous potential, if rightly tapped, to make great contributions to the nation's GDP. The following will illustrate a few valid points by way of expert's questions vs. opinions offered, current statistics available with future projections and a few suggestions for making best use of medical tourism towards the development of the country's economic prosperity.

Existing offers available for medical tourists

Currently, the offers available today for similar patients are specialized services ranging from cardiology and cardiac surgery (angioplasty, bypass, valve replacement), to oncology and onco-surgery, organ transplants (liver and kidney), bone marrow transplants, joint replacements, eye surgery and in-vitro fertilisation. The cost differential is significant, as it was for Marshall, for the patients.

Swot analysis of Tamil Nadu medical tourism

Strengths

- World class quality of services.
- 2. Tamil Nadu is very rich in heritages & culture.
- Economical and Affordable Pricing.
- Worldwide Yoga is gaining significance as 'the best' method of health management
- Large pool of qualified doctors
- Strong presence in advanced healthcare e.g. cardiovascular, organ transplants - high success rate in surgery
- International recognition and reputation of hospitals and Doctors
- Skilled, well behaved, professional nursing staff
- Diversity of tourism destinations.

Weaknesses

- Lack of uniform pricing policy.
- Poor infrastructure in Govt Aided hospital.
- Poor promotion, India not properly promoting as a medical tourism destination.
- Low awareness among the target tourists.
- No strong government support / initiative to promote medical tourism
- Low Coordination among the various service providers in the industry- airline, hotels, travel agents and hospitals
- Only 17 JCI accredited and 198 NABH accredited hospital in India

Opportunities

- Sharp rise in medical as well as tourism Industry.
- Medical staff speaks fluent English.
- Globalisation and Internet technology providing visibility to the service providers.
- Growing health concerns across the world Increased demand for healthcare services
- From countries like US, UK with aging population
- Fast-paced & stressful lifestyle increases demand for wellness tourism and alternative cures
- Deficiency of supply in National Health Systems in countries like U.K, Canada
- Demand from countries with underdeveloped healthcare facilities
- Demand for retirement homes for elderly people especially Japanese

Threats

- Lack of foreign accreditation.

- Foreign player may enter into the market.
- Strong competition from Malaysia, Thailand and Singapore.
- Insecurity of tourist due to rising terrorism and naxalism attack.
- Lack of international accreditation overseas medical care not covered by insurance providers
- Low-investment in health infrastructure

Conclusion

The growth of Medical Tourism in India contributes for the development of infrastructure in medical facilities, Medical science, GDP, and employment opportunities. The standards and infrastructure of hospitals in Tamil Nadu are now at par with global best practices.

The Medical tourism sector is now playing a major role in the economic development of many countries. The growth of private sector in emerging economies has resulted in better quality banking, hospitality, communication and transport facilities. The ever changing customer preferences and shorter breaks make it essential for the medical tourism industry to constantly innovative its products and services in line with changing trends and customer requirements. Constant innovation is the key to sustain growth and enhance competitiveness in the market.

Tamil Nadu has long been a centre of ancient healing traditions based on herbal medicine and holistic treatments that have evolved from folk knowledge as well as Asian well-being therapies such as Indian Ayurvedic and Allopathic practices. With the growing popularity of holistic healing techniques that restore balance and rejuvenate mind, body and spirit, in addition to conventional medical treatment, Tamil Nadu offers a one-stop shop that leaves you looking good and feeling great from Hospital to Hospitality.

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ORIGIN OF THE PRE –RAPHAELITES

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Introduction

Relying on the long research *edutpicturapoesistradition*, the argument demonstrates that parallelism between the arts still remains open to discussion as an issue that is not fully established theoretically. Modern interdisciplinary theories are used in this study to facilitate exploration of the painting-poetry correlation in a way that leads, as I believe, to new findings. These findings are made possible by an approach to the correspondence of the arts that treats poetry and painting as codification systems; such a line of study emphasizes the process of generating and functioning of the resulting structures in both arts. Throughout the argument, poetry and painting are analyzed from the perspective of their representational value. Therefore, the study does not merely identify visual features of verbal language or linguistic features of visually. It is not the aim of the present research to pursue the recurrence and imitation of themes in the two arts, but to investigate the intellectual operations that allow artists to achieve similar or identical goals by means of dissimilar tools, methods and material. Concurrently, the study shows how each of these two forms of artistic expression translates into the other medium, how they share each other's features, and how each of those forms can imitate the other.

The general method of this thesis is the application of similar intellectual tools to a comparative study of two seemingly dissimilar arts. This requires a series of theoretical assumptions of which the most important is the treatment of poetry and painting as "secondary modelling systems."¹ The distinction between primary and secondary modelling systems, which was introduced by Jurij Lot man in the 1960s, has been recently proposed by, for instance, SewerynaWystouch, as a method which leads to a valid comparative study of painting and poetry. The primary systems, i.e the verbal (ethnic) language code and the visual code, are composed of sets of basic elements that can be syntagmatically and paradigmatically arranged - through the sets of rules complementing the system - into larger entities, images(signs). Consequently, the signs weave texts - separately visual and verbal - but they are also able to create interests of indistinguishable verbalism and visuality of their components. At this point a major reservation has to be made. One of the basic differences between the codes relates to the dissimilar character of those rules: while the rules of the verbal code are highly rigorous, the visual code allows for greater arbitrariness and non-standardisation. What is crucial is the impossibility of defining a common set of norms applying to all painterly creations (except for a few, e.g. perspective, canons common to a painter's work, school, epoch or artistic tradition.) At the same time, the question of the articulation of the two systems arises; as Umberto Eco claims, the notion of double articulation needs further enquiry as there are codes which do not necessarily require the second level of articulation.

An implication that follows from the above suppositions is that of the divisibility of visual images. Whereas the elements of the verbal code are naturally isolatable (in the terms of both

linguistic and literary analysis), the treatment of the visual code as potentially divisible into smaller meaningful units remains a more contentious issue. However, the tradition of considering visual representation as divisible dates back to the fifteenth-century theories of Leon Battista Alberti, and has recently been taken up, with various emphases, by Rudolph Arnheim, Ernst Gombrich, Meyer Schapiro, W. J. T. Mitchell, Nelson Goodman and Umberto Eco. Such a view of visual images makes it easier to consider them as having a textual nature, and indeed, according to the semiotic approach, pictorial representation can be treated as an ordered system of signs comparable to that connected with verbal representation. Both visual and verbal systems are analysed in this dissertation in terms of the mechanisms of their functioning and their mutual penetration in the form of - depending on the term applied by a given theoretician - interference (Caws⁶), oscillation (Nancy⁷) or intertextuality dissemination (Dziadek⁸)

The dissertation does not assume, however, that visual and verbal expression are identical. Rather, they are comparable in structural, semantic and semiotic function. A parallel aim of my research is to show the similarities fusing these two methods of representation and, simultaneously, to reveal the differences between them; the latter has recently been a more valid research target.⁹ The basic differences are unquestionable: in Foucault's words, "the relation of language to painting is an infinite relation"; thus, it is not the aim of this research to "[reduce] one to the other's terms": But the relation of language to painting is an infinite relation. It is not that words are imperfect, or that, when confronted by the visible, they prove insuperably inadequate. Neither can be reduced to the other's terms: it is in vain that we say what we see; what we see never resides in what we say. And it is in vain that we attempt to show, by the use of images, metaphors, or similes, what we are saying; the space where they achieve their splendour is not that deployed by our eyes but that defined by the sequential elements of syntax.

The methodology of my research relies on the treatment of painterly and poetic images as comparable units of expression, but this is not to claim that *any* image and *any* (verbal) text are always comparable. Such a misleading view of the painting -poetry relationship often provides an easy target for the critics of these arts' sisterhood. Nelson Goodman, for instance, quite rightly claims that "pictures" have an analog nature: they are syntactically and semantically continuous and lack differentiation and articulation, unlike words and texts that are composed of letters, each of which can be easily singled out and identified. In Goodman's words, pictures are "dense" whereas words are "differentiated."¹¹ Mitchell, discussing that part of Goodman's theory, uses the example of Mona Lisa's nose: "A particular spot of paint might be read as the highlight on Mona Lisa's nose, but that spot achieves its significance in the specific system of pictorial relations to which it belongs, not as a uniquely differentiated character that might be transferred to some other canvas." Mitchell contrasts that quality of painting with the system of the alphabet in which, obviously, each letter serves as a unique unit, easily distinguishable and, regardless of context, remaining the same letter. Also, it is not important *how* this letter is written, since its physical form does not change its meaning. There is no denying that the above assertions are true with regard to verbal language and visual images, but Goodman's application of those basic differences to poetry and painting, as secondary modelling systems, becomes an overstatement. Nonlinguistic systems differ from languages, depiction from description, and the representational form from the verbal, paintings from poetry, primarily through lack of differentiation - indeed through density and consequent total absence of articulation) - of the symbol system. To exploit Mitchell's example, let us compare the fragment of da Vinci's painting which shows Mona Lisa's nose with its verbal equivalent "the highlight on Mona Lisa's nose" and treat it as a fossilized verbal image.

Both images appear in a given context which is immediately clear, and both are plainly differentiated and unique. To put it trivially, there's only one Mona Lisa and only one Mona Lisa's nose. In the micro-context of the painting, the highlight can be easily separated visually; in the linguistic context, however, the verbal image retains its signification even if used in a completely *different* context, as in the following sentence: "The highlight on Marilyn Monroe's face in this photograph resembles the 'the highlight on Mona Lisa' snose'." As it turns out, the verbal image is as "dense" as the visual one. This effect is conditioned by a handling of such verbal images that dispenses with the necessity to strip the verbal down to its basic elements - but understood as *linguistic* rudiments: words (which are ambiguous when standing alone), letters, phonemes, etc. Still, even individual words can be treated as such distinct images: the representation of an apple in Rossetti's canvas *Venus Verticordia* corresponds to the word "apple" used in his poem accompanying the painting. As was mentioned earlier, the present study follows an approach that takes into account meaningful units of poetry and painting as systems of representation *built on* linguistic and visual fundamentals.

Pre-Raphaelites

The first thing likely to strike anyone looking at poems and paintings by Pre-Raphaelite artists is that they have little in common. The label "Pre-Raphaelite" leads a reader or viewer to expect some uniformity arising from a common aesthetic philosophy, technique, or goal, but the Pre-Raphaelites rarely provide such uniformity, despite the heroic efforts of later critics to locate it. Even within the literary and artistic work of a given member, it is easy to find a variety of styles and approaches that prevents easy generalizations.

Yet it would be wrong to conclude that the term "Pre-Raphaelite" is meaningless. On the contrary, the phenomenon of the group label is one of the most interesting things about the Pre-Raphaelites, even though the artists who originally came up with the name did so in a relatively joking spirit. Early in the nineteenth century, when labels had been applied to groups of artists, they were often a dismissive mark of hostile criticism. The point of the criticism was that great artists did not belong to schools, either because they were individual geniuses who transcended group identities or because all good artists recognized common, well-established aims, so that forming a distinctive school was a mark of inferior artistry. Nothing is more important about the Pre-Raphaelites than their ability to turn the group label, which had been an image in criticism for inferior art, into a self-conscious badge of rebellion.

The Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood

During the first phase of the Pre-Raphaelite movement, the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood was formed in 1848 by a group of young painters attending the Royal Academy Schools. The Royal Academy, founded in 1768, had been a critical institution for raising the respectability of painting and of painters in Britain as a professional class. In the nineteenth century, it continued under the burden of representing British national values, especially in the paintings that the Academicians chose for public exhibition. Yet the actual education given to the students at the Royal Academy was relatively uninspiring: students spent months copying works, receiving occasional criticisms from teachers, and hearing dry lectures on such topics as perspective or art history.

Given the Academy's claustrophobia, it was hardly surprising that some young students would be eager to rebel against its strictures. Three gifted artists studying there, Dante Gabriel Rossetti, William Holman Hunt, and John Everett Millais, agreed to create a secret society dedicated to

taking the arts in a new direction. Later, Rossetti's brother William Michael, a critic; the sculptor Thomas Woolner and the painters James Collin son and Frederic George Stephens joined the group. Rossetti's teacher and lifelong friend, Ford Maddox Brown, part of an older generation of painters, was also closely associated with it, though he was never an actual member. The adjective "Pre-Raphaelite" seems to have been Hunt's idea, while Rossetti added the "Brotherhood." Rossetti's *Girlhood of Mary Virgin* (1849) was the first painting to include the actual initials "PRB" after his signature to denote membership in the group. Although what the initials stood for was supposed to be secret, their meaning quickly became common knowledge once the paintings began to attract the attention of art critics in London.

To further consolidate the group's identity, the members planned a periodical entitled *The Germ: Thoughts towards Nature in Literature, Poetry, and Art*. Although *The Germ* lasted only four issues, it was notable in several respects. Unlike almost any other periodical of the day, it featured mostly poetry and essays on aesthetics, rather than the standard fare of book reviews, political essays, or serializations. It was an "in-group" publication, by artists for artists, as was underscored by the title chosen for its last two issues: *Art and Poetry: Being Thoughts towards Nature, Conducted Principally by Artists*. It also broadened the significance of the Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood by insisting that its importance was not confined solely to painting: it included literature and essays on aesthetics as well. An organ through which to formulate an aesthetic manifesto and to expand into other modes increased the perceived intellectual seriousness and weight of the Pre-Raphaelites' endeavors. In it, important early poems by Dante Gabriel Rossetti ("The Blessed Damozel" and "My Sister's Sleep") and Christina Rossetti ("Dream Land") first appeared, as well as essays on art by Frederic George Stephens and Ford Maddox Brown. The core of the Pre-Raphaelites' program in some ways recalled that of Wordsworth; their goal was "an endeavor to encourage and enforce an entire adherence to the simplicity of nature" (Rossetti, 1851, p. [X2]). Yet the Pre-Raphaelites' invocation of nature, especially in relation to painting, had a particular edge, though not one made explicit in their manifestos: art had to recognize the challenge posed by technical developments in photography by developing higher standards of verisimilitude.

Though the results may seem less innovative now than they did in the 1850s, early viewers responded with real shock. Innovation and experimentation were not what they had come to expect from the staid exhibitions of the Royal Academy. Although early reviews were scorching, the Pre-Raphaelites were lucky to find a somewhat unexpected champion in the most distinguished aesthete of the age, John Ruskin, who, as the scholar Isobel Armstrong notes, "Probably managed to give ... a more coherent account of Pre-Raphaelite principles than they could themselves" (Armstrong 1993, p. 233). Partly through the prestige of Ruskin's work, hostility toward the Pre-Raphaelites diminished rapidly, and they quickly became some of the most praised artists of the day. The close association of the Brotherhood, however, was over by 1853.

While the label "Pre-Raphaelite" came to be something of an embarrassment for most in the Brotherhood, it deserves careful scrutiny. It was a self-consciously difficult term, one that presupposed considerable knowledge about the history of European art. The Italian Renaissance painter Raphael (1483-1520) had long been held up in England and in the Royal Academy as the model for aspiring artists. In a peculiar twist of events, a set of cartoons that he produced as designs for tapestries had an extraordinary afterlife in England; they were copied as paintings for Hampton Court, widely disseminated through engravings and copies, and became models for neoclassical taste. Lecture after lecture at the Royal Academy held up Raphael and his cartoons as

ideals and as the source for what were easily felt to be arbitrary rules about good painting: all figures in a painting needed to be placed in an S-shape; the principal figure needed to have the most light; one corner always had to be in the shade; and others.

A suggestive ambiguity in the adjective “Pre-Raphaelite” characterizes exactly how the artists related themselves to Raphael. One interpretation is that the painters wished to associate themselves with whatever was before “Raphaelitism.” The members of the Brotherhood understood “Raphaelitism” as a shorthand for the perceived regasification of Raphael’s influence, rather than for Raphael himself. As Holman Hunt wrote in his memoir, “Pre-Raphaelitism is not Pre-Raphaelism” (1905/1984, p. 23). The suffix “ite” marked the distinction in a mocking echo of Biblical usage (“Israelite,” “Canaanite,” “Moabite”), as if followers of Raphael were a lost tribe, keeping an allegiance to values sadly out of place in a modern setting. Through their label, the Pre-Raphaelites unmasked the Royal Academy’s precepts not as universally recognized aesthetic truths, but as products of a worn-out and derivative school, Raphaelitism.

In this context, the “pre-Raphaelite” had more of the force of “anti-Raphaelite” or even “post-Raphaelite.” The hallmark of this rejection of Raphaelitism in early Pre-Raphaelite paintings is an almost hallucinatory attention to detail, combined with the abandonment of traditional schemes for organizing painted figures, as in Holman Hunt’s *The Awakening Conscience* (1853-1854) and Millais’s *Ophelia* (1851-1852). Such aggressive precision in the representation of detail was the quality most often noted by their early admirers. In their art, this realism went hand in hand with a marked assertion of Englishness, as if avoiding the “Raphaelite” meant avoiding turning away from the continent. Unlike J. M. W. Turner (1775-1851) and his famous images of Venice, the Pre-Raphaelites painted English people, English scenery, and scenes from English literature, so that even their Italian scenes, as in Holman Hunt’s *Valentine Rescuing Sylvia from Proteus* (1851), were from English authors. A notable facet of this Englishness was the willingness of the Pre-Raphaelites to champion English poets who were still virtually unknown in Victorian Britain, including John Keats and William Blake.

After the Brotherhood

While “Pre-Raphaelite” could signal a rebellion against Raphaelitism, it also had a different meaning, in which it denoted instead a self-conscious imitation of artists who came before Raphael. In this reading, discarding the Academy’s promotion of Raphael pointed to medieval art as a preferable model. In fact, few of the Brotherhood had direct contact with early Italian art, for very little of it was available for viewing in England, and most of the painters had not traveled on the Continent to see it. Nevertheless, *The Germ* foregrounded the medievalizing aspects of the label through such works as Rossetti’s *Hand and Soul*, a short historical fiction imagining the life and struggles of a medieval Italian painter, and Frederic George Stephens’s essay on early Italian art. The choice of the term “Brotherhood” itself was also a potentially medievalizing gesture, insofar as it gave the group defiantly Catholic associations, in a period when the Oxford movement had given Catholicism a particular allure as intellectual forbidden fruit.

This medievalism emerged most strongly after the breakup of the initial Brotherhood in 1853, when Rossetti and some fellow artists traveled to Oxford in the summer of 1857 to paint Arthurian murals on the walls of the Oxford Union Society. Unfortunately, they did not prepare the walls of the Union well for mural painting, and their work began to decay almost immediately. What mattered more was that, while at Oxford, Rossetti cemented his already existing friendships with the artist Edward Burne-Jones and the artist and poet William Morris, and that he met Algernon

Charles Swinburne, who nearly a decade later would emerge as the most famous and scandalous poet in England. Whereas no single member of the original Pre-Raphaelite Brotherhood had really stood out as a leader, the second wave of Pre-Raphaelitism was dominated by Rossetti. The young Oxfordians copied Rossetti so exactly that they started a journal like *The Germ*, the *Oxford and Cambridge Magazine*, which lasted for twelve issues; it even reprinted Rossetti's "The Blessed Damozel" from *The Germ*.

As the subject of the Union murals indicates, medievalism was a more prominent, though never exclusive, motif in the second wave of Pre-Raphaelitism than it had been for the Brotherhood itself. Elsewhere in Victorian literature, medievalism came burdened with a heavy weight of political and religious associations. Thomas Carlyle had used the chronicle of a medieval abbey as a model for charismatic leadership in *Past and Present* (1843); John Ruskin in "The Nature of the Gothic" in *The Stones of Venice* (1851) had treated the perceived grotesqueness of medieval art as a model of alienated labor. The Pre-Raphaelite medievalism of Rossetti, Morris, and Burne-Jones is often seen, in contrast, as a dreamy escape from contemporary reality into a fantasy past. But for the Pre-Raphaelites, the medieval was less an escape into fantasy than a representational style that let them reject mid-Victorian conventions of didacticism, religiosity, domesticity, and sentimentality. After the tortured psychological self-examinations of poets like Tennyson or Arnold, poems like Rossetti's "Sister Helen" and "The Staff and Scrip" or Morris's "The Defense of Guinevere" and "The Haystack in the Floods" were refreshingly dry, impersonal, and even brutal. They drew instead on the conventions of the literary ballad as exemplified by writers like Walter Scott, in which action dominated character analysis. Far from being otherworldly fantasy, these poems cut through layers of respectable conventions to focus on tense drama and elemental passions.

Aside from medievalism, the other major development in the second wave of Pre-Raphaelitism was the growing artistic and intellectual significance of women. The most important woman writer associated with the Pre-Raphaelites was Dante Gabriel's sister, Christina Rossetti, at once one of their closest associates and harshest critics. She published in *The Germ* and claimed to have benefited from her brother's criticism of her poetry. Yet her poetry also offers a quiet but persistent critique of the Pre-Raphaelite treatment of female subjectivity. Her sonnet "In an Artist's Studio" describes an artist who paints a woman "not as she is, but as she fills his dream," thereby underlining the chasm between Pre-Raphaelite idealization and the actual woman involved. At the same time, it would be unfair to Christina Rossetti to view her work solely as a reflection on the work of the Pre-Raphaelites; her many books of theology, for example, need to be interpreted in quite different contexts. In addition to Christina Rossetti, many women artists contributed to the development of Pre-Raphaelitism, although their works were not always as publicly visible as those of the male artists: Rossetti's wife Elizabeth Siddall; Joanna Boyce; Anna Mary Howitt; and others.

In the final decades of Rossetti's life, partly at the instigation of his patrons, his paintings increasingly turned toward obsessive fixations on female beauty, the long succession of what Swinburne called "stunners." He sold most of these paintings directly to patrons, often newly rich urban industrialists eager to distinguish themselves from an older, aristocratic tradition of collecting the works of European Old Masters. The paintings therefore received no public exhibition, increasing the aura of mystery around them. What may be most "stunning" today about this series of works is the eerie solitude of Rossetti's women: they rarely have context outside themselves, and the poems that Rossetti sometimes wrote to accompany them only reinforces

their solitude. The paintings rivet attention on female faces, perched precariously between haunting beauty, blank prettiness, and idiosyncratic ugliness; the label “Pre-Raphaelite” is often used to refer particularly to this distinctive feminine appearance. Details of Rossetti’s biography further heightened his mystique: his wild life in London, living at times with Swinburne, the poet and novelist George Meredith, and the painter Simeon Solomon; Siddall’s suicide in 1862; his burial of his poems with her—and the even more dramatic exhumation of them in 1869; his affair with Morris’s beautiful wife; the scandal created by the attack on his collected poems (1870) in Robert Buchanan’s essay “The Fleshly School of English Poetry” (1871); and his final descent into depression and drug addiction.

After Rossetti’s death in 1882, his reputation was consolidated by a range of reviews, memoirs, and evaluations. Although the work of many of those associated with Rossetti, including Swinburne, Meredith, and Morris, took quite different directions after their initial Pre-Raphaelite associations, Rossetti’s work itself did not go out of date as the century progressed, either because, as in the case of *The Bride’s Prelude*, he did not publish it until the end of his life or because, as in the case of “Sister Helen,” he continued to revise previously published versions. Moreover, much of Rossetti’s art was not widely known because it never received public exhibition. As a result, knowledge of his art acquired an enviable edge of distinction, since it was only available to a small elite. More than any other artist, he bridged the art of mid-Victorian Britain and the Aesthetic and Decadent movements of the fin de siècle: almost all the artists associated with these movements, including Oscar Wilde, Aubrey Beardsley, and William Butler Yeats, acknowledged their debt to Rossetti. Even T. S. Eliot, so often seen as a key figure in turning away from all that Rossetti represented, chose as the epigraph to his poem *The Waste Land* lines from Petronius that Rossetti had translated decades earlier.

More than any of the original Brotherhood could have predicted, the Pre-Raphaelite label turned out to be a canny piece of marketing. The aura of mystery surrounding the initials “PRB” fostered an explanation industry: commentaries, reviews, and evaluations that set out to teach the uninitiated just what Pre-Raphaelitism was. As early as the 1850s, this apparatus gave the Pre-Raphaelites a particular aura of intellectual rigor and interest, and it helps to explain how a rather small group of paintings and painters came to acquire such an enormous, unlikely influence. Dante Gabriel Rossetti, for example, became one of the most famous painters and poets in England, even though he had completed very few paintings or poems. Despite a revulsion against Pre-Raphaelite aesthetics in the first half of the twentieth century, Pre-Raphaelite images, with their unsettling ability to hover between kitsch and high art, have turned out to be one of the most enduring legacies of the Victorian era.

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NEEDS OF TRAINING FOR UNDEREMPLOYED GRADUATES IN TAMILNADU

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Abstract

Underemployment, or disguised unemployment, refers to a job that is insufficient in some important way for a worker, relative to a standard, which results in the under-utilization of the worker. It refers to the condition in which people in a labor force are employed at less than full-time or regular jobs or at jobs inadequate with respect to their training or economic needs. This paper analysis about the inadequate skills of workers and the different training methods needed to the employees to develop the skills.

Keywords: *Training needs, underemployment.*

Introduction

Underutilization of skills. Workers in occupations that underuse their experience, training, and skills are underemployed. These workers might be receiving salaries below what they believe they can earn; they might also be unsatisfied with their jobs or work fewer hours than they desire. It is generally assumed that underemployed workers could leave their current position for another job where their characteristics are better used. Thus, the underemployed are believed to present a significant pool of untapped labor because they are expected to respond to job opportunities that are better matches to their skills, training, and experience. In other words, underemployment describes the employment of workers with high skill levels and postsecondary education who are working in relatively low-skilled, low-wage jobs. In the past few years, this kind of job dislocation has accelerated—as more qualified workers have bumped the slightly less qualified from their jobs. As the effect trickles down the occupational scale, productivity often drops because highly qualified workers are more likely to be dissatisfied with the jobs they are forced to take, and thus tend to be more bored, resentful, and distracted than their less-educated counterparts.

Training Needs for Underemployment

Coaching

Coaching is a one-to-one training. It helps in quickly identifying the weak areas and tries to focus on them. It also offers the benefit of transferring theory learning to practice. The biggest problem is that it perpetrates the existing practices and styles.

Job rotation

This training method involves movement of trainee from one job to another gain knowledge and experience from different job assignments. This method helps the trainee understand the problems of other employees.

Job Instructions

It is also known as step-by-step training in which the trainer explains the way of doing the jobs to the trainee and in case of mistakes, corrects the trainee. It is a systematic, fast, and effective method for teaching your workers to do a job correctly and safely. This method of training workers through a simple breakdown of steps is easy to understand and complete. By providing such

training for your workers, you could reduce the risk of an injury or death to a worker, prevent costly equipment repairs, or avoid lost work time.

Committee assignments

A group of trainees are asked to solve a given organizational problem by discussing the problem. This helps to improve team work.

Internship training

Under this method, instructions through theoretical and practical aspects are provided to the trainees.

Apprenticeship

Apprenticeship is a formalized method of training curriculum program that combines classroom education with on-the-job work under close supervision. The training curriculum is planned in advance and conducted in careful steps from day to day. Most trade apprenticeship programs have a duration of three to four years before an apprentice is considered completely accomplished in that trade or profession.

Lectures

This will be a suitable method when the numbers of trainees are quite large. This is also called as classroom training wherein the employees are given lectures about the job requirements and the necessary skills required for implementing the job.

There is generally a classroom or a workshop wherein the complete job knowledge is given to the workers by the experts or specialists from the professional institutes. The main purpose of this training is to make the employees well informed about their job roles and discussing their queries arising out of the lectures.

Simulation

Under this training, the trainee is required to learn the operations of machines and equipment, that are reasonably designed to look similar to those installed at the actual work floor. This is one of the most common method of training wherein the worker learns to operate tools and machinery

Vestibule Training

This type of training is specifically given to the technical staff, office staff and the employees who learn the operations of tools and equipment assembled at a place away from the actual work floor.

Case study method

Usually case study deals with any problem confronted by a business which can be solved by an employee. The trainee is given an opportunity to analyse the case and come out with all possible solutions. This method can enhance analytic and critical thinking of an employee.

Role play

In this case also a problem situation is simulated asking the employee to assume the role of a particular person in the situation. The participant interacts with other participants assuming different roles. The whole play will be recorded and trainee gets an opportunity to examine their own performance.

In-basket method

The employees are given information about an imaginary company, its activities and products, HR employed and all data related to the firm. The trainee (employee under training) has to make notes, delegate tasks and prepare schedules within a specified time. This can develop situational judgments and quick decision making skills of employees.

Business games

According to this method the trainees are divided into groups and each group has to discuss about various activities and functions of an imaginary organization. They will discuss and decide about various subjects like production, promotion, pricing etc. This gives result in co-operative decision making process.

Suggestions

- By adopting the above training method underemployed can be developed to the suitable employment.
- Individual should plan early and should choose the right field and right industry to reduce underemployment
- A combination of slow-growing wages and price inflation has led to a reduction in the real value of take-home pay this can be avoided
- Focusing on continuous learning culture helps to reduce underemployment

Conclusion

Creating new jobs and training workers with skills needed in existing and emerging labor markets are the two major challenges in the economy. While conceptually, a person working in a job below his qualifications or capability can also be deemed in a sense to be “underemployed”, in practice this is difficult to measure because of the subjectivity involved. A gap between Individual skills and industrial skills can be reduce by proper training methods

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A STUDY ON GREEN MARKETING AWARENESS AMONG THE CUSTOMERS

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Introduction

Green marketing is an emerging marketing strategy that incorporates broad range of activities; it can be viewed both as a type of marketing and a marketing philosophy. As a type of marketing it is like industrial or service marketing and is concerned with marketing of a specialized kind of product, i.e. green product (including green goods such as fuel efficient cars or recycled products as well as green ideas such as “save oil” or “conserve natural habitat”). It is a part of Corporate Social Responsibility

Definition

According to **American marketing association (AMA)**, green marketing is the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe; it incorporates several activities as product modification, changes to production process, and packaging, advertising strategies and also increases awareness on compliance marketing among industries.

Objectives of the Study

- To study on green marketing and its concepts.
- To investigate the level of awareness of customers about green products and practices.
- To study the importance and future scope of green marketing.
- To study the problems associated with green marketing.

Need for the Study

Green Marketing is the most latest and popular trend market which facilitated for the environment-friendly in individual, animal and planet. The paper attempts to study the terms and concepts of green marketing, to examine the future scope and problems with green marketing.

Limitations of the Study

- **Unawareness-** people are unaware of green marketing.
- **Time constraint-** the time duration for doing the research on the topic green marketing was very limited. Green marketing a broad topic which requires in depth research and analysis.

Review of Literature

POLONSKY 2011, Environmental marketing, more popularly known as green marketing or sustainable marketing can be defined as 'all activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchanges intended to satisfy human needs or wants such that the satisfaction of these needs and wants occurs, with minimal detrimental impact on the natural environment'.

Research Methodology

It is the way to systematically solve the research problem by logically adopting various steps.

Research Design

Descriptive research design is used in this study. Descriptive research is also known as statistical research. Refers to research that provides an accurate description of characteristics of a particular individual, situation, or a group. In short descriptive research deals with everything that can be counted and studied, which has an impact of the lives of the people it deals with.

Data Collection Tools

Types of Data

- Primary data
- Secondary data

Sampling Size

The sample size is 100 customers.

Sampling Method

Sampling method used for the data collection is **convenient sampling method**.

Statistical Tools

- Percentage analysis
- Weighted average
- Bar chart

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Level of Awareness on Green Marketing

Options	Respondents	Percentage
Low	29	29%
Average	43	43%
High	17	17%
Very high	11	11%
Total	100	100%

Inference

From the above table, it is inferred that maximum percentage of respondents has average awareness on green marketing.

Factors Affecting Green Marketing

Options	W	Number of Respondents	WX	Rank
Social responsibility	5	22	110	1
Absence of marketing	4	18	72	3
Expensive	3	32	96	2
Not easily available	2	17	34	4
Indifference attitude	1	11	11	5

$$\Sigma W=15 \quad \Sigma WX=323$$

Weighted Arithmetic Mean

$$= \frac{\Sigma WX}{\Sigma W} = \frac{323}{15}$$

Inference

From the above extract, 22% of respondents consider Social Responsibility as the most affecting factor of green marketing.

Future Consumption of Green Products

Options	Respondents	%
Not at all	16	16%
Consider to use sometimes	25	25%
Intend to use in future	37	37%
Consider to use always	22	22%
Total	100	100%

Inference

From the above table, it is inferred that out of 100 respondents, 37% of respondents intend to use green products in future and 16% of respondents have no idea to purchase green product.

Findings

- It is found that 29% of respondents have awareness on green marketing and 11% respondents have very high knowledge on green marketing.
- It is found that 43% of respondents have average knowledge on green marketing.
- It is found that 37% of respondents intend to use green product in future and 16% have no idea to purchase green products in future.
- It is found that social responsibility is the major factor affecting green market
- 32% of respondents consider green products are expensive and 17% consider they are not available easily.

Suggestions

Green marketing is a continuous process that requires constant inputs from the suppliers, government legislations and policies and the people. Businesses should concentrate on focusing on developing and marketing a green product that have a demand from the general public. Eco-labeling criterion should be standardized so that consumers may not be confused about claims of green products. Green marketing should not be considered as just one more approach to marketing, but has to be pursued with much greater vigor, as it has an environmental and social dimension to it. It is extremely important that green marketing becomes the norm rather than an exception or just a fad.

Conclusions

Increasing awareness on the various environmental problems has led a shift in the way consumers go about their life. There has been a change in consumer attitudes towards a green lifestyle. People are actively trying to reduce their impact on the environment. However, this is not widespread and is still evolving. It is clearly evident that the majority of the consumers still lack 'green' knowledge and because of such low awareness towards green products, organizations are still not pushing towards developing more green products nor are they working hard on green packaging. Most of the people are ready to accept, but the entrepreneurs and government has to take initiative for promoting and implementing the green marketing and green products.

IMPORTANCE CROSS CULTURAL TRAINING TO MEET GLOBAL COMPETENCIES

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Abstract

Modern global employees are required to possess a set of competencies or multiple intelligences in order to meet pressing global challenges. Hence, expanding global employees, competency is becoming an important issue. In this study efforts have been made to describe the competencies and skills required for global employees to deal effectively with different organizational climates and cultures among different countries. Cross Cultural training is only the way of fulfilling the global competency for global workers. The paper presents a importance of cross culture training and explain what are all the competencies needed for global employees.

Introduction

Harrison and Hopkins (1967) [1] suggested that among the requisite soft skills associated with effective cross cultural experiences, the expatriate must master the abilities to communicate verbally and nonverbally. working in the global marketplace multiplies the variables and interdependencies. In the context of employees have deal with different nationalities and work in different countries, but also face an increasing complexity of organizational structures, innovations in information and communication technology. So the cross cultural training helpful to meet the global competencies.

Methodology

This paper was prepared based on the secondary data from the academic literature and scholarly journal. The concept of cross culture training need to meet the global competency required to possess in order to meet global challenges of today's multinational companies.

Objective of the Study

- To know about importance of cross culture training to meet the global competency.
- To know about what are competency skill required for global employees.

Importance of cross cultural Training

Cross cultural training only the way of employees to meet the global competency. Cross cultural training develop the awareness between people where common cultural framework. It is important for every multinational company to deal with different countries they must give cross cultural training to their employees to work effectively, without proper cross cultural training to the employees did not work effectively to meet the global competencies.

Following the what all are the competency skill needs for global employees;

Global competencies required for Global Employees

Multinational corporations require different set of competencies among their employees to complete their global assignments. Typically these include aspects such as adaptability, flexibility,

and conflict resolution skills, cross cultural awareness, communication ability, emotional maturity, cultural sensitivity, negotiation skills and team building. The above skills and competencies can be classified as core skills and augmented skills both skills are important for employees to working for different countries.

Basic Competency structure used by International organizations

- **Core Competencies:** include those key competencies that all employees in the organization must possess to achieve its mandate and vision.
- **Technical/ Professional Competencies:** include the specific skills and know how to perform effectively within the jobs of the stream. (e.g. ability to use particular software, knowledge in particular area.)

A successful international working employees would need all the skills that are needed in domestic business operations

Each country having its own ethos, values, business and social culture, he or she has to be a generalizing specialist as well as specializing generalist, adding depth to the breadth of the knowledge and ability as one moves from one. Hence global employees require following competencies:

Knowledge of one's own country: To understand the culture of other countries better, one should know one's home country well. Appreciation of one's history and cultural values, understanding of current social and political issues and business situation are necessary.

A Global Perspective: A global employees must have a global working perspective and an understanding of how the world works. Learning, unlearning and relearning are integral parts of the knowledge intensive global business. Aspiring global employees have to be mentally ready to cope with surprises, mistakes, misunderstandings and even blunders in their cross cultural interactions.

Understanding of International Business Environment: To do business in other countries one must know the rules of business, acquire in depth knowledge of the stated and prevailing practices of the business. One must acquire through knowledge about the other country in areas such as tax rules, labour laws, social benefits to be provided to employees, Government and public attitude towards foreign business executives and workers, foreign business investment and ownership.

Knowledge of the silent and spoken International language: Spoken and silent languages are the main channels of communication in any culture. While each country may have one or more official languages, there are many variations in the use of spoken and silent languages within regions of each country. Edward T. Hall in his theory of cultural context explained the relevance of the indirect style of communication and nonverbal behavior in creating and interpreting communication.

Interpersonal Awareness: The ability to gain others' support for ideas, proposals, projects and solutions depends on the ability to notice, interpret and anticipate others' concerns and feelings and to communicate this awareness empathetically others.

Competencies dealing with Business

Building Collaborative relationships: The ability to develop, maintain and strengthen partnerships with others inside or outside the organization who can provide information, assistance and support.

Customer Orientation : The ability to demonstrate concern for satisfying one's external and internal customers. Every expatriate must have the ability to quickly and effectively solve customer problems and must find ways to measure and track customer satisfaction.

Analytical thinking and Technical expertise : Technical job skills refers to the talent and expatriate a person possesses to perform a certain job or task. Managers need an in depth understanding of competitive products and services within the marketplace.

Entrepreneurial Orientation: It shows the ability of a parent country national to look for and seize profitable business opportunities in Host country environment also the willingness to take calculated risks to achieve business goals.

Self-management competencies

Such competencies mainly includes skills related to management of self and the inner motivation:

Self Confidence- Faith in one's own idea and capability to be successful, willingness to take an independent position in the face of opposition.

Stress Management- the ability to keep functioning effectively when under pressure and maintain self control in the face of hostility or provocation.

Emotional Intelligence and Time Management. The above skills and competencies are based on the pre-departure and post-departure training provided to the employees by different firms following Geocentric, Polycentric or even Ethnocentric approach. (<http://www.shrm.org>)

Conclusions

A lack of cross culture management training and development may contribute ultimately to a lack of international growth and success. Most of the multinational corporation provides cross cultural training to their expatriates and employees emphasizing mainly on leadership skills, flexibility and technical skills. Every organization has to develop intercultural competence among their employees is important of today's modern organization. CCT is the only the way of develop the global employees. Cross-cultural training is fulfilling the all competencies to meet the global challenge. Cross cultural training is important of global employees to work in different countries to work effectively.

கணிமேதாவியாரின் விழுமியங்கள்

பேரா. ஞா.சேகர்

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திருவண்ணாமலை மாவட்டம்

முன்னுரை

மனித வாழ்க்கைக்கு வேண்டிய அரிய பல செய்திகளை கணிமேதாவியார் நமக்கு எடுத்துரைத்துள்ளார். அவ்வாறு சங்க காலத்தில் வாழ்ந்த மனிதனின் திறமைகளை வெளிக்கொணர்வதோடு மட்டுமல்லாமல் ஆழ்ந்த கருத்துக்களை விதைத்து சென்றுள்ளதை அவர் எழுதிய நூலின் வாயிலாக காண்போம்.

மனிதனுடைய நம்பிக்கைகள், எண்ணங்கள், அறநெறி கருத்துக்கள் என்பனவற்றின், நீதி, ஆசாரங்கள் இவற்றை ஒட்டுமொத்தமாக சுட்டுவதே விழுமியம் என்பர். அவற்றின் அடிப்படையில் ஏலாதி 80 செய்யுளைக் கொண்டுள்ளது. அந்த நூலில் ஒவ்வொரு செய்யுளிலும் ஆறு கருத்துக்களையும், திணைமாலை நூற்றைம்பது 153 செய்யுளைக் கொண்டுள்ளது. அந்நூலில் ஐந்திணையின் ஒழுக்கங்களை கோர்வையாக அமைத்து மாலைபோல் நமக்கு எடுத்துரைக்கின்றார்.

அறம் என்ற சொல்லின் பொருள்

அறநெறி என்ற சொல்லின் பொருளை ‘அறு என்னும் பகுதியின் அடியாக அவை, அறம், சொல், அறவு, அறவை, அறதல், அறுதி, அறுத்தல், அறுப்பு, அறும்பு, அறுகால் அல்லது அறுதாள், அறுவை, அறை, அற்றம், அற்றை, ஆறு’ முதலிய சொற்களால் பிறக்கின்றன என்று வே. முத்துலக்குமி கூறுகின்றார். தனி மனிதனையும், சமுதாயத்தையும் செந்நெறிப்படுத்தும் ஒழுக்க நெறியாக அறத்தைக் கருதுகின்றனர். இவ்வலக வாழ்விற்கும் முன்னேற்றம் அடைவதற்கும் மனப்பண்பிற்கும் அறவாழ்வு இன்றியமையாதது என்று கருதப்படுகின்றது. பதினெண்கீழ்க்கணக்கு நூல்கள் பல நேரடியாக அறங்களை மட்டுமே கூறின.

ஏலாதியில் அறநெறிகள்

ஒருவனுடைய வாழ்க்கை மேம்பட வேண்டுமென்றால் இவற்றை கடைபிடித்தால் போதுமான ஒன்று. ‘மெய், வாய், கண், மூக்கு, செவி என்னும் ஐம்பொறி உணர்வுகள் சுவை, ஒளி, ஊறு, ஓசை, நாற்றம் என்னும் ஐந்து அவாவினையும் மன உறுதி தளராமல் அறுக்க முற்படுவனின் தகுதி சிறந்து மிளிரும்’ என்பதனை,

“அவா அறுக்கல் உற்றான் தளரான் அவ்ஐந்தின்
அவா அறுப்பின் ஆற்ற அமையும் அவா அறான்
ஆகும் அவனாயின் ஐங்களிற்றின் ஆட்டுண்டு
போகும் புழையுள் புலந்து”.

என்ற பாடல் விளக்குகின்றது. ஐம்பொறிகளின் வழியால் வரும் நினைப்பையும் ஆசையையும் அடக்கிக் கொள்வதே மிகவும் சிறந்தது.

விருந்தோம்பல் தமிழரின் சிறந்த பண்பாடு. நமது வீட்டிற்கு அனைவரும் விருந்தினரல்லர். ஆகவே நமது வீட்டிற்கு வரும் விருந்தினர் முன்பின் அறியாத புதியவர்களேயாவர். அவர் எந்நாட்டினராயினும், எம்மொழியினராயினும் நட்புக் கொள்ளும் நல்லெண்ணத்துடன் வீடுதேடி வருவார்களாயின் அவர்களை வரவேற்பார்கள் தமிழர்கள். விருந்தினரை வரவேற்று உபசரிப்பவர்களே மறுமையின்பத்தைப் பெற முடியும் என்ற நம்பிக்கையும் தமிழரிடம் குடிகொண்டிருக்கின்றது. விருந்தினரை வரவேற்று, உபசரிக்க வேண்டும் என்பதைப் பின்வரும் செய்யுள் நமக்கு விளக்கிக் காட்டுகின்றது.

“இன்சொல் அளவால் இடம் இனிது ஊன் யாவர்க்கும்

வன்சொல் களைந்து வகுப்பானேல் மென்சொல்
மருந்து ஏய்க்கும் முள்போல் எயிற்றினாய் நாளும்
விருந்து ஏற்பர் விண்ணார் விரைந்து”

இறகின் அடியை ஒத்த கூரிய பற்களையுடைய பெண்ணேளு தன்னை நாடி வந்தவரை இனிய சொற்களால் உரையாடி அவர்களுக்குத் தங்குமிடமும், அறுசுவை உண்டியும் அளித்து உதவ வேண்டும். கடுஞ்சொல்லற்ற இனிய மொழிகளையே எந்நாளும் பேச வேண்டும். இவ்வாறு விருந்தினரை உபசரிப்பவர்களைத் விண்ணுலகத்தாரும் தமது விருந்தினராக ஏற்றுக்கொள்வார்கள்.

“இல்லறத்தில் கணவனும் மனைவியும் இணைந்து ஆற்ற வேண்டிய அறம் விருந்தோம்பல் ஆகும். இது பற்றி தொல்காப்பியம் நன்கு விளக்கியுள்ளது. இவ்வாழ்க்கை நடத்தும் கணவனும் மனைவியும் தம் உற்றார் உறவினரைக் காக்க கடமைப்பட்டவர். அதுமட்டுமல்லாமல் தம் இல்லம் நாடிவரும் பிறரையும் உண்டியாலும் உறையுளாலும் உபசரித்தல் அவர்தம் கடமை என்று அறநூல்கள் கூறுகின்றன என்று மா. இராசமாணிக்கம்” குறிப்பிடுகின்றார்.

இதனைப் பற்றி ஏலாதியில் கூறுவது. ஆதரவற்ற எளியோருக்கு உண்ண உணவு, உடுக்க உடை மற்றும் தங்குவதற்கு இடம் யாவும் தந்து உதவும் இயல்பினைக் கொண்டவர்கள் அறிஞர் பெருமக்கள் எனப் போற்றப்படுவர். பிறர் மீது சினங்கொள்ளாமல் தன்னை நாடி வந்தவர்க்குத் தன்னால் இயன்ற பொருள் தந்து உதவுவதைத் தேவரும் விரும்பி நாடுவர் என்று ஏலாதி குறிப்பிடுகின்றது.

“விருந்தினரைக் கண்டால் முகமலர்ந்து வரவேற்கும் தமிழர்களின் சிறந்த பண்பினை அதாவது இரவு நேரத்தில் விருந்தினர் எவராவது வருவது உண்டா என்று காத்திருந்து வாயிற் கதவை அடைப்பதை பண்டைத்தமிழர் வழக்கமாகக் கொண்டிருந்தனர் என்பதை குறந்தொகை குறிப்பிடுகின்றது”.

தூதுவனுக்கு வேண்டிய தகுதிகள்

அண்டை நாடுகளுக்கிடைய நல்லுறவை வலுப்படுத்துவதற்கு சங்ககாலத்தில், ஒற்றர்கள் என்று சொல்லக்கூடிய தூதுவர்கள் இருந்தார்கள். அதனால் தான் மன்னர்களுக்கிடையே பூசல்கள் இருந்தாலும், நல்லிணக்கத்தை கடைப்பிடித்தனர். ஒரு நாட்டின் பிரதிநிதியாகச் சென்று மற்றொரு அரசாங்கத்துடன் பேசுவோரைத் தூதுவர் என்பர். இத்தகையோருக்குத் தகுதிகள் என்னென்ன என்று ஏலாதி ஒரு செய்யுளில் விளக்குகின்றது.

“மாண்டு அமைந்த ஆராய்ந்தமதி வனப்பே வன்கண்மை
ஆண்டுஅமைந்த கல்வியே சொல்லாற்றல் பூண்டுஅமைந்த
காலம் அறிதல் கருதுங்கால் தூதுவர்க்கு
ஞாலம் அறிந்த புகழ்”

தூதுவர்கள் ஒழுக்கம் சிறந்தவராகவும், நாட்டு நிலைமையை ஆராயத்தக்கக் கூடிய அறிவு நிறைந்திருக்க வேண்டும். பிறரை மதிக்கக்கூடியவராகவும் மற்றும் அழகிய தோற்றமும் வேண்டும். பல துறையைப் பற்றிய கல்வியறிவு வேண்டும். ஆணித்தனமாகப் பேசக்கூடிய பேச்சாற்றல் நிறைந்தவராக இருக்க வேண்டும். இத்தகைய ஆறு குணங்களும் இருந்தால் அவை தூதுவர்க்கு உலகறிந்த புகழைத் தரும் என்றும் தூதுவனுக்கு இருக்கக்கூடிய தகுதிகளாகக் கூறுகின்றது. தமிழர்கள் அந்நிய அரசாங்கத்துடன் தொடர்பு கொண்டிருந்தனர் என்பதற்கு இச்செய்யுள் ஒரு உதாரணம் காட்டுகின்றது.

அரசர்கள் மேற்கொள்ள வேண்டாதவை

“போகம் பொருள்கேடு மான்வேட்டம் பொல்லாக்கள்
சோகம் படும் சூதே சொல்வண்மை சோகக்
குடுங்கதத்துத் தன்னிடம் அடங்காமை காப்பின்
அடுங்கதம் இல் ஏனை அரசு”¹⁴

இன்ப நுகர்ச்சியும், பொருளுக்கு கேடு விளைவித்தலும், விலங்குகளை வேட்டையாடுதலும், பொல்லாத கள்ளினை உண்ணுதலும், அழிவைத் தரும் மற்றும் சூதாடலும், வன்சொல் வழங்கலும் எனும் இவைகளைப் பேணாமல் இருப்பது மன்னனுக்குரிய தகுதி என்று ஏலாதி குறிப்பிடுகின்றது.

குடிமக்களைக் காத்தல், ஆள் வினைத் திறம், நூற்புலமை, கூஞ்சகமும், சோம்பலும் நிகழாதவாறு, காக்கும் ஆற்றல் அரசாட்சியை பாதுகாப்பது ஆகியன மன்னனுக்கு இருக்க வேண்டிய தகுதிகள் ஆகும். “நீதியில் தவறாமல் நின்று, குற்றங்களைப் போக்கி, விரத்தில் குறையாத பெருமையுடையவன் சிறந்த அரசனாவான் என்று குறள் கூறுகின்றது”.

“அறனிழுக்கா தல்லவை நீக்கி மறனிழுக்கா
மானம் உடைய தரசு”

கல்வி கற்றவரின் பண்புகள்

பிறர் செய்யும் நன்மைகளை நாம் பலருக்கும் வெளிப்படையாகப் பேச வேண்டும். பிறர் செய்த தவறுகளைக் கூறுவது அறிவுடையாரின் செயல் அல்ல. பிறருக்குத் தீமை செய்வதை மனத்தால் விரும்பக்கூடாது.. பிறர் நமக்குச் செய்த தீமைகளை மறந்துவிட வேண்டும். பிற உயிர்களுக்குத் துன்பம் வருவதைக் கண்டு பாதுகாத்து நிற்பல் வேண்டும். பிறர் பொருளை வஞ்சித்துக் கவர எண்ணுவது அறிவாகாது. இதனை சிறுபஞ்சமூலம்,

“நல்ல வெளிப்படுத்துத் தீய மறந்தொழிந்து
ஒல்லை உயிர்க்கு ஊற்றும் கோலாகி - ஒல்லுமெனின்
மாயம் பிறர்பொருட்கண் மாற்றுக மானத்தான்
ஆயின் அறிதல் அறிவு”

என்று குறிப்பிடப்படுகின்றது. சான்றோர் பிழை செய்தல் அரிது, நல்வழியைச் சார்தல் எளிது என்று ஏலாதி குறிப்பிடுகின்றது.

மனிதனுக்கு வேண்டிய பண்புகள்

வீட்டில் இன்பம் தவறுமாயின் பிறவித் தொடர்தல் எளிது. அப்பிறவித் துன்பம் நீக்குதல் மிக அரிது. காம நுகர்ச்சியை விரும்பாதவன், காரணமின்றி சினம் கொள்ளாதவன், கொலைத் தொழில் புரியாதவன், பிறரை வெறுப்பதை தன்னிடம் நீக்கியவன் ஆகிய குணங்களை உடையவனாக இருக்க வேண்டும் என்று ஏலாதி குறிப்பிடுகின்றது. திரிகடுகம் இதனை,

“இல்லார்க்கு ஒன்றுஈயும் உடைமையும் இவ்வுலகில்
நில்லாமை உள்ளும் நெறிப்பாடும் எவ்வுயிர்க்கும்
துன்புறும் செய்யாத தூய்மையும் இம்மூன்றும்
நன்று அறியும் மாந்தர்க்கு உள.”

என்று குறிப்பிடுகின்றது.

வறியவர்க்கு செல்வம் கொடுப்பது நற்பண்பு ஆகும். இவ்வுலகில் உள்ள பொருள்களின் நிலையாமைப் பற்றி நினைக்கும் நல்லொழுக்கம், எவ்வுயிர்க்கும் துன்பம் தரும்படியான கொடுமையைச் செய்யாத நற்குணம் ஆகிய பண்புடையவர்கள் அறநெறியினைப் பற்றி அறிந்தவர்கள் என்று திரிகடுகம் குறிப்பிடுகின்றது.

துறந்தாருக்கு வேண்டிய பண்புகள்

இன்றைய காலச்சூழலில் சாமி என்ற பெயரில் பல்வேறு தீய செயல்களைச் செய்து வருகின்றார்கள். அவர்களுக்கு சவுக்கடி கொடுக்கும் வகையில் கணிமேதாவியார், சான்றோர் என்று பேர் படைத்தல் அரிது, நற்செயலை ஏற்றல் எளிது, வாய்மையைக் காத்தல் அரிது, அதில் நிலைத்தல் அரிது, இம்மை மறுமையில் ஏற்படும் தீவினை, பழிபகை சாவு, பொருட்கேடு, அச்சம் ஆகியவை முனிவர்க்கு சாபமொழி போலத் தன்னையே சாரும்.

“கூத்தாடுமிடம், கொலைக்களம், ஆரவாரமிக்க போர்க்களம் ஆகிய இடத்தில் ஞானியர் சேராமல் இருப்பது கற்றிந்த ஞானியர் பண்பு ஏலாதி குறிப்பிடுகின்றது.”

நன்பனாக வேண்டிய பண்புகள்

நண்பனுக்கு வேண்டிய பொருளைக் கொடுத்து உதவுதல், இனிய சொற்களைப் பேசுதல் ஆகிய பண்புகள் நண்பனுக்கு உரியவை என்று ஏலாதி குறிப்பிடுகின்றது. ஒருவனுக்கு இலக்கண இலக்கிய கல்வி அறிவே உண்மையான அழகு என்று வலியுறுத்துகின்றது.

உடற்பயிற்சி

மக்கள் அனைவரும் திடமாக வாழவேண்டும், உடற்பயிற்சி உரம் அளிப்பவை ஆகும். உரம் உள்ளவர்கள் நோயின்றி வாழலாம். இக்கருத்தைக் கொண்ட செய்யுள் ஒன்று உடற்பயிற்சியைப் பற்றி,

எடுத்துரைக்கின்றது.. எந்தெந்த வகையிலே செய்ய வேண்டும் என்றும் அச்செய்யுள் விளக்கிச் சொல்கின்றது.

“எடுத்தல், முடக்கல், நிமிர்த்தல், நிலையே
படுத்தலோடு, ஆடல், பகரின் - அடுத்து உயிர்
அறுதொழில் என்று அறைந்தார் உயர்ந்தவர்
வேறு தொழிலாய் விரித்து.”

கையை ஊன்றி உடம்பை மேலே தூக்குவது தண்டால் என்றும், கை கால்களை முடக்கியிருத்தல் ஆசனம் என்றும், அவற்றுடன் நிமிர்ந்து நின்றல் தலைகீழாக நின்றல்., படுத்துந் செய்யும் பயிற்சி, குதித்தல் இவைகளே உடற்பயிற்சிகளாகும். இவைகளின் சிறப்பைக் கூறவேண்டுமானால், பெரியோர்கள் உடம்பில் உயிர் அமைதியோடு வாழ்வதற்கான தொழில்கள் என்றும், இவைகளையே வேறு வேறு தொழில்களாகத் தனித்தனியே கூறினார்கள். இச்செய்யுளில் மூலம் தமிழர்கள் நீண்ட காலமாக உடற்பயிற்சி செய்து வந்தனர் என்று இப்பாடல் நமக்கு நன்கு எடுத்துரைக்கின்றது.

திணைமாலை நூற்றைம்பதில் இடம்பெறும் செய்திகள்

காதலை பற்றி எடுத்தியம்புகின்ற நூல்களே அதிகம். நாங்கள் காதலர்கள், எங்கள் காதலானது தெய்வீகமானது என்று இன்றைய காதலர்களின் வசனமாகும். பார்ப்பவர்கள் மனது சபலப்படும் வகையில் நடந்துகொள்ளும் காதலர்களை கணிமேதாவியார் மிகவும் சாடுகின்றார். காதலர்கள் காதலை வெளிப்படுத்தவும், இருவரும் சந்திக்கக் கூடிய இடங்கள் யாருடைய மனதையும் புண்படுத்தாதபடிக்கு நாகரிகமாக காதல் புரிந்தார்கள் திணைமாலை நூற்றைம்பதில் ஆசிரியர் குறிப்பிடுகின்றார்.

இந்நூலில் ஒவ்வொரு திணைக்கும் 30 செய்யுளாகத் தொகுத்துக் கூறுகின்றன. அவை குறிஞ்சித் திணை 31, நெய்தல் திணை 31, முல்லைத் திணை 31, பாலைத் திணை 30, மருதத் திணை 30 எனப் பாடல்கள் மொத்தம் 153 வெண்பாக்களைக் கொண்டவையாகும்.

திணைமாலை நூற்றைம்பதில் தோழி, தலைவி, தலைவன், பாங்கன், கண்டோர், செவிலி, நற்றாய், விரலி, வாயிலோன் போன்றவர்களின் கூற்றுக்களாகவே இந்நூல் அமைந்துள்ளன. இரவுக்குறி, பகற்குறி மறுத்தல், சிறைப்புறம் கூறல், வரைவு கடாயது(திருமணம் செய்து கொள்ளும்படி கூறுதல்), அறத்தோடு நின்றல், தலைவியை வற்புறுத்துதல், தலைவனைப் புகழ்தல் 56 பாடல்களும், தலைவி கூற்று, வாயில் மறுத்துல் ஈறாக 57 பாடல்களும், தலைவன் கூற்று 22 பாடல்களும், பாங்கன் கூற்று நான்கு பாடல்களும் (28,45,47,144), கண்டோர் கூற்று 5 பாடல்களும் (69,71,72,89,149), செவிலிக் கூற்றாக 4 பாடல்களும் (14,62,65,81), நற்றாய் கூற்றாக மூன்று பாடல்களும் (15,75,90), விரலி கூற்று ஒரு பாடலும் (134), வாயிலோன் தலைவனுக்கு கூறியது ஒரு பாடலும் (146) போன்ற நூற்றைம்பத்தி மூன்று செய்யுள்கள் திணைமாலை நூற்றைம்பதில் இடம்பெற்றுள்ளன.

காதல் வாழ்க்கை மனித வாழ்வில் பின்னிப் பிணைந்தவையே ஆகும். காதல் வாழ்க்கைப் பற்றி சங்க இலக்கியப் பாடல்கள் வரிகள் கூடுதல் இடத்தைப் பெற்றுள்ளன. பல கவிதைகளும் காதல் பற்றிய செய்திகளைக் கூறுகின்றன. காதல் பற்றி அக இலக்கியங்களில் மட்டுமே அதிக செய்திகள் காணப்படுகின்றன.

கீழ்க்கணக்கு நூல்களில் காதல் திறம்

“காதலியை காதலன் இயற்கைச் சூழலில் காண்கிறான். காதலியைப் பார்த்த உடனேயே உள்ளத்தை பரிகொடுக்கின்றான். ஒவ்வொரு திணையிலும் அந்தந்த இனத்தைச் சார்ந்த ஆணும் பெண்ணும் காதலிக்கின்றனர் என்று கீழ்க்கணக்கு நமக்கு எடுத்துரைக்கின்றன. இவ்வாறு காதலர்கள் சந்தித்த உடனே தங்களுடைய மனதிற்குள் காதலை வளர்த்துக்கொண்டு காதலில் மூழ்கிவிடுகின்றனர். தலைவியை சந்திக்கும்போது பல்வேறு தடைகள் வருகின்றன. அதாவது பகல் நேரத்திலும், இரவு நேரத்திலும் காதலர்களுக்கு தடை ஏற்படுகின்றது.” ஆடவன் திணைப்புணத்தை காவல் செய்வதற்கு காதலி வருவாள் என்று எண்ணி அங்கு சென்று பார்க்கிறான். அந்த இடத்தில் தனது மனதிற்குரியவள் இல்லையே என்ற ஏக்கம் அவனை துன்புறுத்தியது. என் காதலி எனக்கு கிடைக்க வேண்டும், இல்லையென்றால் மடலேறுதல் செய்தாவது எனது காதலியை அடைவேன் என்பதை,

“நாணாக நாறு நனைகுழலா ணல்கித்தன்
பூணாக நேர்வளவும் போகாது - பூணாக
மென்றேன் இரண்டாவ துண்டோ மடன்மாமேன்

இன்றேன் மறுகிடையே நோந்து.” (தி.மா.நா-16)

இன்றைய சூழலில் காதலர்கள் எவ்வாறெல்லாம் தனது காதலனோடு உரையாடுவதும் காதலை வெளிக்காட்டுவதும் தொலைபேசி, அலைபேசி (செல்லிடப்பேசி), தொலைநகலி(பேக்ஸ்), இணையம் (இண்டர்நெட்) போன்ற ஊடகங்கள் வாயிலாக முகம் தெரியாத ஆணும் பெண்ணும் காதலிக்கின்றனர். இவ்வாறு காதலிக்கும் காதலர்கள் சேர்ந்து வாழ முடியாமல் பல்வேறு இன்னல்களுக்கு ஆளாகின்றனர். காதலியோடு சேர்ந்து வாழ முடியவில்லையென்றால் தற்கொலையும் செய்து கொள்கின்றனர். இவ்வாறு இல்லாமல் பெற்றோரின் சம்மதத்தோடு முறைப்படி திருமணம் செய்து கொள்ள வேண்டும் என்பதை வலியுறுத்துவதே மடலேறுதல் ஆகும். ஒரு பெண்ணின் பார்வை பல விதங்களில் உண்டு. ஆனால் ஆடவனைப் பார்க்கும் பார்வையானது வேலைப் போன்று தன் உள்ளத்தில் ஊடுவி தன் காதலை வெளிப்படுத்தும். ஒரு காதலுக்கு உள்ளம் தான் முக்கியம் வேறு எதுவும் தேவையில்லை என்பதை திணைமாலை நூற்றைம்பது கூறுவது.

“பாலொத்த வெள்ளருவி பாய்ந்தாடிப் பல்பூப்பெய்
தாலொத்த ஐவனம் காப்பாள்கண் - வேலொத்துஎன்
நெஞ்சம்வாய்ப் புக்கொழிவு காண்பானோ காண்கொடா
அஞ்சாயற் கேநோவல் யான்.” (தி.மா.நா-19)

பகல்குறி

பகல்குறி என்பது காதலன் காதலி ஆகிய இருவரும் தோழியின் உதவியால் பகல் நேரத்தில் சந்தித்து உரையாடுகின்ற நேரத்தை பகல்குறி எனலாம். இத்தகைய நிலை சங்க இலக்கியத்திலும் கூறப்படுகின்றது. கணிமேதாவியாரும் தனது நூலில் குறிப்பிடுகின்றார்.

தாழை மரங்கள் நிறைந்திருக்கும் பூஞ்சோலைகளும், கருவாடு காய்ந்து கொண்டிருக்கின்ற இடமானது பகல் பொழுதில் சந்திப்பதற்கு ஏற்ற இடம் என்று தோழி எடுத்துரைக்கின்றார்.

“கடும்புலால் புன்னை கடியந் துறைவ
படும்புலாற் புட்கடிவான் புக்க - தடம்புலாந்
தாழைமா ஞாழற் றதைந்துயர்ந்த தாம்பொழி
லேழை மா னோக்கி யிடம்.” (தி.மா.நா-44)

மீனை காயவைத்து அதனை வியாபாரத்திற்கு எடுத்துச் செல்வர். அதாவது அனைவரும் கூடி வியாபாரம் செய்கின்ற இடமான சந்தை, மற்றும் அடப்பம் கொடிகள், முளைப்பாலிகைகள் பூத்திருக்கும் பூஞ்சோலை இடமும், பல வலைகள் நிறைந்திருக்கின்ற இடத்திலும் பகல் பொழுதில் தலைவியை சந்தித்து உரையாடுவதற்கு ஏற்ற இடம் என்று ஆசிரியர் குறிப்பிடுகின்றார்.

இரவுக்குறி

இரவுக்குறி என்பது காதலன் காதலி இருவரும் சந்தித்து பேசக்கூடிய இடம் இரவுக்குறி என்று கூறுவர். இவை வீட்டின் பின்புறம் சந்திக்கின்றவையாகும். தலைவி வீட்டிற்குப் பின்னால் உட்பங்கழிகள் சூழப்பட்டிருக்கின்ற இடமும். புன்னை மரங்களின் இதழ்களிலே வாழ்கின்ற அன்றில் பறவைகள் மற்றும் பனைமரம் நிறைந்துள்ள இடத்தில் தலைவியை சந்திக்கலாம் என்று தோழி தலைவனிடம் கூறினாள்.

“கடற்காணற் சேர்ப்ப கழியுலாஅய் நீண்ட
வடற்காணற் புன்னை தாழ்ந்தாற்ற - மடங்கான
லன்றி லகவு மணிநெடும் பெண்ணைத்தெம்
முன்றி லிளமணன்மேன் மொய்த்து.” (தி.மா.நா-56)

முடிவுரை

பல அறநெறிக் கருத்துக்களை மனிதனுக்கு பயன்படும் வகையில் சமுதாயத்திற்கு சொல்வதாக ஏலாதி நூலில் ஆசிரியர் குறிப்பிடுகின்றார். ஒரு தனி மனிதன் எத்தகைய பழக்கவழக்கங்கள் வேண்டுமென்பதை திணைமாலை நூற்றைம்பது என்னும் நூலின் வாயிலாக இச்செய்தியை கட்டுரையின் மூலமாக அறியமுடிகின்றது.

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OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES FACED BY WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN INDIA

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Abstract

In the words of APJ Abdul Kalam "Empowering Women is a prerequisite for creating a good Nation, when women are empowered, society with stability is assured. Empowerment of women is essential as their thoughts and their value systems lead to development of good family, good society and ultimately good nation". Women entrepreneurship is gaining attention and importance in light of the evidence of the importance of new business creation for economic growth and development. Entrepreneurship refers to the act of setting up a new business so as to take advantages from new opportunities. Entrepreneurs are responsible for shaping the economy and they help in creation of new wealth and new jobs by inventing new products, process and services. We all understand that economic development of the today's woman is crucial for economic development of any country specially a country like India. The dependency on service sector has created many entrepreneurial opportunities for women that they can utilize to enhance their social standing and reputation. In this paper, an attempt has been made to study the opportunities and challenges related with entrepreneurship that the woman of our country faces in the present times

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, woman, economy, economic development, challenges, economic growth, opportunities of women entrepreneurship.

Introduction

Women's entrepreneurship need to be studied separately for two main reasons. The first reason is that women's entrepreneurship has been recognized during the last decade as an important untapped source of economic growth. Women entrepreneurs create new jobs for themselves and others and by being different also provide society with different solutions to management, organization and business problems as well as to the exploitation of entrepreneurial opportunities. However, they still represent a minority of all entrepreneurs. Thus there exists a market failure discriminating against women's possibility to become entrepreneurs and their possibility to become successful entrepreneurs. This market failure needs to be addressed by policy makers so that the economic potential of this group can be fully utilized. The main purpose of the paper to examine the constraints and opportunities facing women entrepreneurship in developing countries at micro-level and macro-level perspectives and seeks to provide a detailed account of opportunities and constraints brought by entrepreneurship. According to **Kamala Singh**, "A women entrepreneur is a confident, innovative and creative woman capable of achieving economic independence individually or in collaboration generates employment opportunities for others through initiating establishing and running an enterprise by keeping pace with her personal, family and social life. According to Government of India—An enterprise owned and controlled by a women having a minimum financial interest of 51% of the capital and giving at least 51% of the employment generated by the enterprise to women.

Objectives of the Study

1. To discuss the problems faced by women entrepreneurs in India.
2. To study the major factors affecting the development of women entrepreneurship among various countries.
3. To solve the measures needed to improve the state of women entrepreneurship in India.

Review of Literature

Bowen & Hisrich, (1986), evaluated many research studies done on women entrepreneurship. It included that female entrepreneurs are relatively well educated in general but are not having proper Opportunities and Challenges faced by Women Entrepreneurs in India management skills, high in internal locus of control than other women in their values & are likely to have had entrepreneurial fathers. **Cohon, Wadhwa & Mitchell, (2010)**, present a detail about men & women entrepreneur's background and experiences. The study is based on the data collected from primary data where surveys were conducted to collect data from established & successful women entrepreneurs.

The study identified top factors motivating women to enter into the field of entrepreneurship. The factors found were desire to build the wealth, the wish to capitalize own business ideas and to move ahead in life. The challenges are more related with entrepreneurship rather than gender.

Studies have found that most of the women establish enterprises before the age of 35 after gaining some job experience somewhere. The Women network report on Women in Business & in Decision Making focus on women entrepreneurs, about their problems in starting & running the business, family back ground, education, size of business unit. **Darrene, Harpel and Mayer, (2008)** performed a study & established a relationship between human capital and self-employment. The study showed that self-employed women differ on most human capital variable as compared to the salary and wage earning women. The study also revealed the fact that the education attainment level is faster for self employed women than that for other working women.

Problems Faced by Women Entrepreneurs in India

There are some umpteen problems faced by women at various stages beginning from their initial commencement of enterprise, in running their enterprise. Their various problems are as follows:

1. Lack in focus on Career Obligations

Indian women do not focus on their career obligations in the same manner as they do on their family and personal life. Despite having excellent entrepreneurial abilities, they do not focus on their career obligations. Their lack of focus towards their career creates a problem in promoting women entrepreneurship.

2. Instability of Economic

The economic stability of Indian women is in a very poor state as they lack proper education that is crucial for becoming self-dependent. Women in rural areas can't take any entrepreneurial.

3. Lack of Risk taking ability

Our educational system is very primitive and creating awareness about woman's capacities and their hidden powers to handle economic activities. Most of the women are not performing entrepreneurial activities because they are not having the proper capacities and risk making ability.

4. Arrangement of Finance and other Resources

Arrangement of finance is a major problem that is faced by women entrepreneurs. Their access to external sources of finance is very limited because of their poor economic condition in the society .As such; they find it difficult to be an entrepreneur as they lack the risk taking ability because of poor financial assistance. Another problem faced by them is shortage of raw-material and difficulty faced by the women entrepreneur in arranging good quality raw material at competitive prices.

5. Cut-throat Competition

Women entrepreneurs have to face tough competition not only from industry but also from their male Counter parts. Surviving this cut-throat competition and achieving the aim of producing quality product at competitive price is not an easy task for the women entrepreneurs.

6. Low levels of literacy rates

Illiteracy is the root cause of socio economic biased less that prevails in the society and that doesn't let women achieve economic independency. Due to lack of Knowledge of latest technology and proper education, it becomes difficult for women to set up their own enterprises.

7. Problems in getting financial assistance by banks & other Financial Institutions

Banks and financial institutions help finance small and medium size firm operators to get financial assistance .But these banks and financial institutions don't readily provide credit to women entrepreneurs because they doubt the credit worthiness of women entrepreneurs. The irony is that according to a report by the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO), woman's loan repayment rates are higher than men's but still financial institutes doubt their loan repayment abilities.

8. Marketing Problems

Women entrepreneurs face problems in marketing of their products as this area is mainly dominated by males and women fail to make a mark in this area. Women entrepreneur also find it difficult to capture the market and make their products popular and they often take the help of middlemen in marketing their products who often charge high commission from them.

9. Less support

In business women have to devote long hours and as a result, they find it difficult to meet the demands of their family members and society as well. As such they become incapable in attending to domestic work, attending to the needs of their children which lead to conflict in their personal lives and they find it difficult to work as an women entrepreneur.

10. More Cost of Production:

High cost of production adversely affects the development of women entrepreneurs. The high cost of factors of production & the raw material makes it difficult for the women entrepreneur to operate in the industry. Government assistance in the form of grant and subsidies to some extent enables them to tide over the difficult situations. Other than the high cost of production, women entrepreneurs also face the problems of labor, human resources, infrastructure, legal formalities, overload of work, mistrust etc that are associate with every business enterprise.

11. Lack of self-confidence and self-esteem amongst women:

A strong mental outlook and an optimistic attitude amongst women are required amongst women to be an entrepreneur. But it has been noticed that women lack these qualities required in setting up their own enterprises. Thus, not having the required confidence that is needed by today's women to move ahead creates resistance in their being a good entrepreneur.

Insights about Women's Entrepreneurship Development

The following are the facts and insights about Women's Entrepreneurship Development:-

- a) Entrepreneurship can be an effective means to create employment and empower women and promoting women's entrepreneurship and gender equality helps to empower women in the society.

- b) Women lack confidence in their entrepreneurial abilities as such along with training women entrepreneurs should be provided with strategic partnerships, networking and programs that help in overall entrepreneurship development.
- c) Infrastructure that supports entrepreneurship opportunities should be provided for women's success.
- d) In all countries women still represent a minority in the area of entrepreneurship, are self-employed, or are small business owner-managers and their full potential has yet not been utilized properly.
- e) Women's entrepreneurship is not very successful because they face lots of challenges because of lack of education, lack of role models in entrepreneurship, gender issues, weak social and economic status etc.

Measures to Improve Women Entrepreneurship

Women entrepreneurship in India faces many challenges and requires a radical change in attitudes and mindsets of society. Therefore, programs should be designed to address changes in attitude and mindset of the people. Women of the present times should be made aware regarding her unique identity and her contribution towards the economic growth and development of the country. Course Curriculum should be designed in a manner that will impart the basic theoretical knowledge along with its practical implication and help impart skills required to be an entrepreneur.

At the same time, there are various schemes like the World Bank sponsored programmes that can be undertaken for such purposes. Programmes can be conducted in which established and successful women entrepreneurs can advise and warn for the coming women entrepreneurs against the challenges they will face against being entrepreneur to boost the morale and confidence level of the upcoming entrepreneurs. Government should also play an important role by setting up policies and plan that supports entrepreneurship opportunities. Setting up good infrastructure is also required to build entrepreneurship opportunities.

It is not easy to promote women entrepreneurship in India as it requires elimination of various obstacles that includes changing the traditional attitudes and mindsets of people in society towards women. To provide opportunities of women entrepreneurship in India one needs to make aware the women regarding her position towards the value she can add towards economic growth and development of country.

Education can play a crucial role in promoting women entrepreneurship and promotion of women entrepreneurship can be achieved by designing course curriculum that will impart the basic knowledge along with its practical implication regarding setting up of your own enterprise. Vocational training can also help by training, motivating and assisting the upcoming women entrepreneurs in setting up & managing of a new enterprise. Apart from vocational training sessions women can be trained on Information Technology to take the advantage of new technology in running their startups. Education has been instrumental in increasing the participation of women in entrepreneurial activities. Proper education not only helps in acquisition of requires knowledge but also imparts knowledge about the different opportunities available in different sectors. Good education makes women confident in dealing with problems in business in an effective manner.

Also women entrepreneurs who have successfully set up their enterprises can act as advisors for the upcoming women entrepreneurs. The advices taken from these successful entrepreneurs

can prove beneficial for the upcoming women entrepreneurs by resulting in better involvement of women entrepreneurs in their enterprises.

Some Successful Leading Business Women in India

- AkhilaSrinivasan, Managing Director, Shriram Investments Ltd
- ChandaKocchar, Executive Director, ICICI Bank
- EktaKapoor ,Creative Director, Balaji Telefilms
- KiranMazumdar-Shaw, Chairman and Managing Director, Biocon
- Ranjana Kumar ,Chairman, NABARD
- RenukaRamnath, CEO, ICICI Ventures
- Ritu Kumar ,Fashion Designer
- ShahnazHussain, CEO, Shahnaz Herbals

Facts & Figures about Women Entrepreneurship

- 1) Women own one-third of small business in USA and Canada and the number is likely to be 50% in the coming century.
- 2) Women account for 40% of the total work force in Asian countries.
- 3) Women outnumber men by at least two lines in China.
- 4) The percentage of women entrepreneurs has increased from 7.69% in 1992-93 to 10% in year 2000-01, but the number still is significantly low as compared to overall work participation rate i.e. 25.7%.
- 5) The number of women in technical courses, professional courses and in engineering stream has shown a tremendous rise. Polytechnics and IITs have only 15% girls out of total enrolled students and very less join and set their own enterprises.
- 6) Around 8% of women have an interest in starting an enterprise or are giving it serious thought, compared with 13% of men.
- 7) Around one in five women come into self-employment from unemployment compared with around one in fifteen for men.
- 8) Only 2% of men cite family commitments as a reason for becoming self-employed, compared with 21% of women.

Conclusion

Women entrepreneurship in India faces many challenges and requires a radical change in attitudes and mindsets of society. Therefore, more programs should be designed to address changes in attitude and mindset of the people. It is important to promote entrepreneurship among women to improve the economic situation of the women. This can be made possible with the help of education as education is a powerful tool in bringing out the entrepreneurship qualities in a human being. Moreover, attempts to motivate inspire and assist women entrepreneurs should be made at all possible levels. Proper training should be given to the women by establishing training institutes that can enhance their level of work-knowledge, risk-taking abilities, enhancing their capabilities. After setting up training institutes, there should be continuous monitoring, improvement of training programs so that they can improve upon the quality of the entrepreneurs being produced in the country.

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